

Editorial

(Published on 02.04.2025 -- Revised on 16.05.2025)

The Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy* / Ma Durga For healing the entire Universe

By

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Presented to:

Their Excellencies Shri @NarendraModi Bhai @PMOIndia & Shri @AmitShah Bhai @HMOIndia
& Shri @RajnathSingh Bhai & Smt @NSitharaman @FinMinIndia & Smt Draupadi Murmu,
President of India on behalf of the Govt. of India

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
@DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN
@BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

* Ma Bagavathy may be spelt differently in various places in the document, but all different spellings imply the same ancient energy source worshipped as Ma Bagavathy in India.

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Interministerial task force under instruction from @PMOIndia/@HMOIndia may please invite self-nominations from Scientists (from multi-disciplinary & inter-disciplinary realms) of Bharatiya Origin residing in Bharat to serve on the Research Team for the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga for healing the Universe.....	24
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Requesting @MIB_India to please devise mechanisms for brainstorming people on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please, for instance a better coverage of the Waqf Bill Amendment 2025 might have garnered better people support with consequent better “for” votes in Parliament. 124

A new Constituent Assembly, a new Constitution and a new National Anthem & a new Parliament with no opposition benches (coz all political parties will be sharing seats on the treasury benches) for Bagavathy Desh/ Durga Desh aka India aka Bharat, matched/outmatched by shipments of Gold, Frankincense & Myrrh from H.H. @Pontifex & the Islamic Brotherhood from H.E. @AlimamAltayeb, challenged by negative tax by H.E. @Potus, rivalled by gifts of shipments of crude oil & technology from @KremlinRussia_E attempted to be outraced by H.E. Dr @MKStalin due to the synchronous phonetic of H.E. Smt Durga Stalin with Durga Desh – A World War of love, peace, unity and compassion – where everyone wins & mankind scales the peaks of immortality..... 126

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- Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia & Thanks to Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @CGM_BSNL_TN & @BSNL_TN for their willingness to transfer required Radio Equipment and query for location to transfer via email on Apr 5, 2025, 3:36 PM 129
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Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding <Are the Waqf protests meant to safeguard the Waqf lands that have become private holdings? Was that a miscalculated “foot in the mouth” embarrassing moment by those who planned it? @MIB_India, some peace & harmony efforts please?> to The Secretary, Ministry of Minority Affairs, Govt. of India and Thanks to the Secretary & Officials @MOMAIndia.....187

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A New Bharatiya Science & Technology Commission -- While Ma Bagavathy enjoys playing “Snake & Ladder” with western scientists & while they are debating whether they were wrong again, lets go forward into the quantum future with facility to influence the past, with the grace & blessings of Ma Bagavathy, leading us in Her Radio Signal form..... 289

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Editorial

Initial Set of Suggestions (submitted Jan 26, 2025)

Need or necessity:

1. Climate Change effects & Pollution
2. Food Security & Nutrition, Water Security & Health Security for the Population
3. Post Covid Scenarios (Post pandemic handling and pre-pandemic handling for next pandemic)
4. Rise in Per Capita Expenditure on Healthcare
5. Increase in mortality rate in middle age (accompanied by sudden heart attacks and declared dead on arrival at hospital within a short time)

Introduction:

The above factors present a formidable challenge to governance when read together. The Nation will require some patronage to deal with the above effectively. When many other Nations of the World are also battling Climate Change effects, India, will have to find its own solutions without depending on other Nations overtly. We will have to become self-sufficient and also attempt to help other Nations too. Self-sufficiency, not only in scientific terms but also in a confluence of scientific and spiritual terms.

Its always better to depend on God than man and hence this initial set of suggestions presents the Mother of God, Ma Bhagawathy/Ma Durga as the one-solution-heals-all.

Ofcourse, we can be ridiculed as being superstitious or old-fashioned, and hence, we also need to modify our approaches to the current day.

Lets envisage a scenario where the Mother of God can be obtained as a Radio/UV signal. We can amplify/attenuate (as required) and beam Her back to the Earth to heal all, accompanied with clinical and related scientific observation to document and analyse the healing with reference to humans, plant life/agriculture, forests and environment, animals, wildlife, nature and the atmosphere, rainfall, etc.

One of the easiest methods of detection would be via Firefly(Ref:1), but that may also be the most costliest method of detection too, though we can use Firefly for secondary targeted investigations.

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One less costly solution would be the use of the Military Signals Division. We can initially start from Kashmir, Bengal, Punjab and Haryana (zones of erstwhile conflict), for there would be records of spurious radio detection in battlefield zones. Once we get the locations in latitude and longitude of those locations, we can get Firefly to investigate those locations and the surrounding area, to check if those spurious radio signals are present still. Assuming that the radio signals are present in those locations still, we can get Firefly based or landbased radio signal acquisition and measurement.

An AI backend to analyze the acquired signal can be set up to check for similarities and corroborations among signals from various locations.

This cycle can be repeated until we get a radio signal from near a Bagawathy or Durga Temple. Once that radio signal is obtained, all previously obtained signals can be checked for similarity and corroboration and labelled based on % match.

Once we have reached this point in the investigations, the rest can be done via Firefly.

However, our personal presence will be mandated at every step for invocation of the Ma Bagawathy or Ma Durga, and link to Her via quantum means and receive Her as an electromagnetic signal.

Then we can get some volunteers who'd volunteer to be exposed to the electromagnetic radiation from Ma Bagawathy or Ma Durga and do clinical investigations on their healing. At the same time, we can use other ISRO satellites to beam the signal on the geographical surface area of the Nation and observe improvement/healing.

This will take some time. Once we have established the healing power of the electromagnetic radiation of Ma Bagawathy or MaDurga, we can extend the same healing to the entire planet and the Universe too, linking with other satellite constellations of various Nations (based on their consent).

Wherever required, pujas and aartis may be done please.

Addendum to Initial Set of Suggestions submitted on January 26, 2025 (submitted on Jan 28, 2025)

Addendum:

It was formerly suggested the following states of Kashmir, Bengal, Punjab and Haryana, which were zones of erstwhile conflict. The following states of Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka,

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Cultural Organization

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Editorial

Telangana and Andhra Pradesh may also be considered for reasons of ancient Devi Temples and a rich cultural heritage. Its quite possible that the Radio Signal of Ma Bhagwathy/Ma Durga (also known as “Amman” in South India) may be obtained from some ancient temple here too. So, we may be able to detect the Ma Bhagwathy/Ma Durga as Protector in zones of erstwhile conflict & Nurturer in the Southern States of Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka, Telangana & Andhra Pradesh.

References:

1. <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1883470434924187964>
2. <https://www.news18.com/india/what-is-firefly-india-based-pixxels-satellite-constellation-pm-modi-mentioned-in-mann-ki-baat-9194077.html>

**Initial Request for establishment of research infrastructure for the project:
(submitted on 05.02.2025)**

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1887048659642278205>

@NarendraModi Bhaiya & @AmitShah Bhaiya

Inter-ministerial task force:

In humility suggesting creation of an inter-ministerial task force comprising of Senior Secretaries of the Govt. of India reporting directly to the @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia for the

Search for the Radio/UV Signal of the Ma Bhagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe.

AIIMS as test centers for volunteer study samples:

Further, suggesting including of all AIIMS as test centres for studying rate of healing of the population, registering as volunteers for healing by the Radio/UV Signal of the Ma Bhagavathy/Ma Durga.

Guests (Visitors & Scientists) from WHO, UNO, EU, etc:

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Also, will require provision of welcoming guest visitors & guest scientists from @WHO and other @UN Agencies, @EU_Commission Agencies and other world bodies and help them participate in our work.

Crowd handling:

Crowd handling may please be allocated to officials who have experience in handling huge crowds as in Kumbh Mela

Ofcourse, there's going to be a huge rush of a very large fraction of the population of India & other International Visitors too, after we are able to tap the Radio/UV signal of the Ma Bhagavathy/Ma Durga, but crowds during investigation cant be ruled out too; for we will have many devotees, who will want to grab the first electromagnetic manifestation of Ma Bhagavathy/Ma Durga.

We are embarking on a voyage of a huge cosmic magnitude. May Ma Bhagavathy & Ma Durga grant us the strength to stand as Her instruments in bringing Her from Her cosmic manifestations into electromagnetic manifestation in Radio/UV range.

Digital Archives:

Since, this will be a rare journey in the History of the World, suitable provision may be made to document it in Media, Libraries and in our much loved Cinema too.

Further, this will also be one of the rarest occasions in the History of India, where all Political Parties, all Organizations, etc. will stand together as one, for the benefit of mankind, Nature, the Planet and the Universe.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Interministerial task force & Revenue sharing with other Nations

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1888521188764422444>

@NarendraModi Bhai & @AmitShah Bhai

Ref1: <https://x.com/aguivaldi/status/1887558723582754869>

Ref2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1887048659642278205>

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

May we thank President Trump @POTUS for the precedence created by the Executive Task Force (Ref1).

So, with thanks to him, we form an interministerial task force for the Detection & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bhagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe (Ofcourse, our beloved @DrSJaishankar will always find a suitable and convincing answer if anyone questions us)

In humility, i do not intend to propose the quantum of revenue sharing with other Nations consequent to successful tapping of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga and post successful testing on volunteer human population to assess rate of healing accompanied with a prospectively global network of hospitals specializing in healing via Radiation Therapy; coz those areas may please be handled by the Govt and its external affairs policies; but in my humble opinion, i would suggest that India may be pleased to share a portion of the revenue with every nation in the world (friend and foe alike); so that all Nations can be benefitted to some extent. Also, there will arise no necessity to any individual or group or ideology or school of thought to sabotage this attempt, coz it will be in the best interests of all Nations to help/support us in our initiative of healing the Universe through the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga and share the blessings and prosperity that Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga showers upon us.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Request to Finance Ministry for evaluation of this project proposal

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1889190972556230895>

@NSitharaman Didi

In humility the following request please.

Your esteemed attention is requested to the proposal "Healing the Universe through the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bhagavathy/Ma Durga" presented to Shri @NarendraModi Bhai & Shri @AmitShah Bhai.

In my humble opinion,

the returns of this project, after being implemented as Radiation Therapy healing via upgradation of Tertiary District Hospitals in India, and creation of new Hospitals in various Nations in revenue sharing model, should be able to project India

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Editorial

into a more comfortable position than a 5 trillion dollar economy,

help in achieving surplus budgets

establishment of a Zero Tax, Zero Inflation, Zero Excise duty, Zero Import duty, Zero GST Nation and

adoption of the Indian Rupee as the Global Reserve Currency

and other benefits too for the citizens and the Nation at large,

ushering in a golden era of health and prosperity.

It will take us considerable time to tap Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga as Radio/UV Signal and translate into a Radiation Therapy Equipment, accompanied with clinical tests on rate of healing in reputed Indian Hospitals on volunteer population.

So, if it would please the Finance Ministry to evaluate my proposal at the earliest and submit your esteemed recommendations to @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia, they will be able to take a decision at the earliest, and we can start immediately, in time for the Saturn Transition in March 29, in time for the Jupiter transition in May.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Acknowledgement:

Thanks to @SotiDr Didi, @RakhiRoyHalder1 Didi & @CKandasamy52986 Bhai for their esteemed views, incorporated herein

Additional details for Finance Ministry evaluation

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1890001402988310685>

@NSitharaman Didi

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1889190972556230895>

Resending pls morning's message sent via mobilephone that was erroneously deleted. Now sending via laptop pls.

W.r.t. cited earlier communication in Ref, in humility the following suggestion please.

The project may pls be treated as a Govt. of India project and the project funds be handled by the Govt. of India & the profit/returns from the project may be received in the Govt. of India Treasury. My role will be Principal Investigator, though, I would NOT wish to handle funds of the project.

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Publications and patents may pls be co-authored with the Govt. of India, so that the Nation, the World and the Universe will be able to continue to reap the benefits of pursuit of Radiotherapy healing using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga post my death too.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @NarendraModi @AmitShah @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Preparatory Requests

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891393941838160008>

@NarendraModi Bhai @AmitShah Bhai & @RajnathSingh Bhai

In humility the following submission please

Subsequent to submission of

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1888521188764422444>

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1889190972556230895>

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1890001402988310685>

the following is submitted to ur esteemed attention please.

Since the proposal to tap the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga & apply for healing via Radiation Therapy, seems to have potential of ushering in a new medicine system via Radiation Therapy, also earning a huge sum of money for the Govt of India to the extent of having a tax free Nation, we need to take precautionary safety measures, to safeguard against sabotage, conspiracy, etc.

In my humble opinion, it would be best to rely only on military infrastructure (conventional & information technology related), coz civilian infrastructure can be subjected to stress due to sabotage, conspiracy, etc.

- Consequently, the selected/identified temples in multiple states of India may have to be handed over to the Defence Ministry.
- The complete area within the temple and a few hundred meters radially outward from the temple may have to be electronically swept to remove any electronic receivers or transmission equipment.
- Since jammers may interfere with the experiment, jammers cannot be pressed into service.
- Until official declaration of initiation of experimentation, electronic devices may be permitted to be carried inside the temples; but after official declaration of initiation of

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experimentation, a security check will be mandated by defence personnel prior to entry at the temples, and devotees may please ensure that their electronic devices are safely locked up in their vehicles outside the temple or deposited at the security check locker along with their aadhar or biometric scan (fingerprint or iris) verification. This may be done so that spurious signals from electronic devices don't get captured by the experimental setup inside the temple.

- The experimental setup may be connected by secure/encrypted wired or wireless data lines to servers in the Defence Ministry.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @DRDO_India @NIA_India @RashtrapatiBhvn

DRDO in-house production of Radio Detector & Radiation Therapy Equipment for Detection & Application of Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891492640882852192>

@NarendraModi Bhai @AmitShah Bhai & @RajnathSingh Bhai

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891393941838160008>

In humility the following submission please.

I've requested help from a friend for a radio detector design and 3d drawing of proposed radiation therapy equipment. He's promised to help.

Once the radio detector design and or 3d drawing is ready, shall present to u please.

We can manufacture both the radio detector and radiation therapy equipment in-house in the @DRDO_India

UV Cameras alone we may need to buy from outside, but if the DRDO can manufacture UV cameras also, then we are technically self-sufficient for the Radio Detection & Application of the Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe.

Ofcourse, quantum links to Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga via consciousness fields have to be invoked personally on site-only.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

www.ijbst.org

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Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Editorial

Request to send in direct the Radio Detector Design and 3D drawing of proposed Radiation Therapy Equipment

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891752442628382918>

@NarendraModi Bhai @AmitShah Bhai & @RajnathSingh Bhai

Ref:

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891492640882852192>

In humility the following submission please.

I shall request my friend to send in the Radio Signal detector design & 3D drawing of proposed Radiation Therapy Equipment for use in the Detection & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga in healing the Universe directly to you please.

Coz I don't want to stand in between him and you.

Let him have his recognitions directly from u please.

Coz quantum links to Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga via consciousness fields have to be invoked personally on site-only, its better that I don't carry the work of anyone else in my hands and I stand clean before Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga in invoking Her to descend in ways convenient for us to tap and help us Heal all of mankind, all life forms, Nature, Environment, the Planet and the Universe through the @Space_Station or any other International Space Station that India might be pleased to place in orbit for this dedicated purpose please..

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891821927267967176>

sarvamaṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi.

Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn.

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

Ref: Copy of Email fwd from President's Secretariat to Finance Secretary, Govt. of India the request for Finance Ministry approval for the proposal to Search & Apply the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the entire Universe, including all of mankind, all life forms, Nature, Planet, and the Universe.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Live Secure/Encrypted Satellite Connectivity between Temple & Radiation Therapy Equipment

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892138510850851089>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai & @RajnathSingh Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

The Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga may be a quantum signal and hence may not be following the natural laws of electromagnetics/physics. Consequently, we may have difficulty in storing the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga, coz She may not be manifesting Herself as a sequence of zeros or ones (in digital parlance), but She may be manifesting Herself in a sequence of zeros and ones (existing in multiple states simultaneously). Ofcourse, if it will please you, we can initiate research on quantum processors, quantum devices and quantum connectivity for use at a later stage. But (for immediate purposes) to reduce the cost factor and the time involved, its suggested that a live secure/encrypted satellite connectivity may be explored between source and target, *ie.*, between the temple and the Radiation Therapy Equipment. We'll surrender to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga and declare that that's all that we got, and She in Her infinite mercy may descend and manifest in accordance with the resources present in our Nation. But at the same time, we can initiate research on quantum devices, quantum processors, quantum connectivity and quantum transportation (which might be helpful to @ISRO space missions also).

In consultation with Professor Mamidala Jagadesh Kumar @mamidala90, @UGC_India can offer through the various Indian Universities/Institutions, masters and doctoral programs in quantum technology (ranging from quantum processors to quantum transportation) and we can apply the designs & prototypes at a later date in future, when we gain the potential to tap the Quantum Radio Signals of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

May Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga bless us and guide us in our journey, so that mankind may be blest to travel to the far dimensions of the Universe and undertake pilgrimage to the abode of

Editorial

Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga (not the earthly abode but the heavenly abode) and also heal alien civilizations on contact or on engagement please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @ISRO @Mamidala90, @UGC_India

Submitting consolidated file for Fin Min Access for evaluation please. With Thanks to @BSNL_TN for restoring FTTH connectivity in just a few minutes please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892146971604906366>

Submitting consolidated file for Fin Min Access for evaluation please. With Thanks to @BSNL_TN for restoring FTTH connectivity in just a few minutes please.

Ref:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: Shri FS <secy-fs@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Feb 18, 2025, 4:26 PM

subject: Fwd: Requesting finance ministry evaluation for project proposal please.

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & @NSitharaman Didi

In humility the following submission please.

With due respect to reference cited above, i'm herewith furnishing detail of consolidated proposal file for ease of evaluation by Fin Ministry please.

Consolidated file is available at

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Since these files link to pdf files on @Microsoft365 @onedrive & @googledrive, further addendums will also be updated on the same files and may be accessible via the same links please.

Editorial

If at any time, due to any technical glitch or error, the links change, I shall be humbled to provide the updated links please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @ISRO @Mamidala90, @UGC_India

Thanks to @BSNL_TN for restoring FTTH connectivity in just a few minutes please.

When Pope is discharged, shall record that Pope Francis is 1st celebrity patient healed by Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga (invoked via human consciousness fields) & has been communicated thus to Pope Francis please

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892462680104915225>

sarvamaṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

Ref1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892043019961897181>

Ref2: <https://www.catholicnewsagency.com/news/262227/pope-francis-hospitalized-live-updates> (as on 12:00 noon IST 20.02.2025)

Waiting for the news that u are recovered and/ or discharged from hospital.

We shall be humbled to record you as our First Celebrity patient healed by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga with just a prayer/invocation to Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga (invoked via human consciousness fields even without sufficient electronic experimental setup) as evidenced by communication cited as Ref1 above.

In any scientific experiment, allowance should also be given for an unfavorable result too.

Hence allowing allowance for an unfavorable result, we shall be humbled to record that your physical ailments due to your aged earthly body have become too much for you to bear that Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga drew you to Herself thereby helping u to shed your aged ailing earthly body.

This is shared with you while you are aware and conscious (Ref2), just to maintain transparency.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @NarendraModi @PMOIndia @AmitShah @NSitharaman @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

Electricity generation using Radio Frequency excitation from Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892810142732718357>

Ref: <https://www.ece.cmu.edu/news-and-events/story/2019/05/rectennas-converting-radio-waves-into-electricity.html>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & @NSitharaman Didi

In addition to healthcare, quantum technology etc., the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga may also have potential for electricity generation. We can attempt to assemble huge Radio Frequency Generators, slowly phasing out Nuclear Reactors with Radio Frequency Generators generating electricity using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga. In addition to it, we can also explore portable radio frequency electricity generators as that can be used in Vehicles. Radio Frequency excitation signal can be provided via the mobile tower network with suitable modifications, as necessary. The vehicles can run on electricity generated live via portable devices in cars, buses and trucks, wherever there is good signal strength, and can run on batteries (charged with radio frequency excitation generated electricity) wherever there is poor signal strength. It can be a Govt. policy decision to provide electricity free (for residential and industry/business use) within the Nation. Export of such technology will again be a Govt. policy decision.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

A New Economy Model for Bharat post Free Energy/Free Electricity or Near Zero Charges for Energy/Electricity & Transportation achieved via Electricity generation using Radio Frequency excitation from Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & @NSitharaman Didi

Assuming that with the blessings of Ma Bagavathy /Ma Durga, we are able to generate electricity far greater than the current installed capacity of 4,17,668 MW (both fossil & non-fossil fuel vide <https://powermin.gov.in/en/content/power-sector-glance-all-India>), it will lead us to an energy surplus situation, and we will have to provide Electricity free of charge for all citizens (inclusive of residential, institutional, industry and business processes).

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Editorial

Read together with the possibility of running transportation via portable radiofrequency excitation devices, transport cost also comes down drastically; which will bring down the prices of all agricultural produce and commodities, very much.

Private players cannot handle the stress of such low prices and consequently, the Govt may have to modify its policies and enter into the National market as a single player. At the same time, the Govt. will also have to provide suitable room for the private players. Consequently, Govt. policy may be updated to include the Govt. as the sole player in the National, State & Local Market, while private players can be provided Govt. support to venture into the International Markets; to the extent that every village in the nook and corner of Bharat can be exporting one or more products internationally. Due to very low cost of electricity/energy, the products exported will also be able to be given at a very competitive price in the International market, attracting the International consumers to depend on Indian exporters to a greater extent. Of course, it may take considerable time to achieve it, but it's a question of Faith & effort. If we have Faith on Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga and if we can match our faith with sincere effort, we can sure achieve the above.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Increased FDI inflows & allocation of SEZs for foreign industry to set up manufacturing in India – Addendum to the new Economy Model for Bharat

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893329412608684412>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & @NSitharaman Didi

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893179548402937890>

In addition to the aforesaid benefits arising out the proposed new Economy Model for Bharat post Free Energy/Free Electricity or Near Zero Charges for Energy/Electricity & Transportation achieved via Electricity generation using Radio Frequency excitation from Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga, a significant beneficial outcome that may be witnessed is that foreign industry may shift their industry to India coz production cost might become very low in India. This consequently enhances increased FDI inflow into India. Therefore, we may have to create Special Economic Zones for each industry type, so that the foreign companies can establish their manufacturing units in identified locations. Transfer for Technology, as reciprocal goodwill gesture to Bharat may be welcome.

Thanks to @CKandasamy52986 Bhai for pointing out enhanced FDI inflows as a consequence of the new Economy Model

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United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia
@HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Unemployment rate & employability rate becomes an insignificant factor of merit – Addendum to the new Economy Model for Bharat

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893568041633661173>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893329412608684412>

Ref 2: <https://www.forbesindia.com/article/explainers/unemployment-rate-in-india/87441/1>

Ref 3: <https://www.financialexpress.com/jobs-career/indian-graduates-employability-drops-to-42-6-mercere-mettl-report-highlights-skill-gaps-3756671/>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai & @NSitharaman Didi

“the unemployment rate in India stood at 7.8 percent in September 2024” (Ref 2) and “A recent report by Mercer Mettl has revealed a concerning dip in employability among Indian graduates, falling from 44.3% in 2023 to 42.6% in 2024” (Ref 3).

The above unemployment rate and employability rate arise when our people try to adapt themselves to a western or globalistic corporate culture. However, when we have our own home grown Economy model (as in Ref 1), people don't have to fit themselves into an alien culture and alien way of life. With Govt. patronage (arising out of surplus funds generated on application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga for healing the Universe, with consequent surplus revenues generated via Free Energy/Electricity Generation & savings due to low cost), every citizen residing in India, can individually or collectively be part of a commodity export group. In such a context each citizen can work somewhere and can also be part of a commodity export group, which will raise the employment proportion beyond 100%, in which case, unemployment rate ceases to be a metric. Similarly, employability rate also ceases to be a metric, coz they don't have to be trained to earn massive profits for a foreign corporate organization and be ranked lower on international metrics, but can be trained locally to export commodity individually or collectively and ranked higher on national metrics.

Declaration:

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

As I'm led, I've shared my views. Thanks to the President's Secretariat for forwarding to the Finance Secretary, Govt. of India

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: Shri FS <secy-fs@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Feb 18, 2025, 4:26 PM

subject: Fwd: Requesting finance ministry evaluation for project proposal please.

Since human consciousness links play a major role in assisting electronic devices in tapping the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga, I hereby assure that I shall devote myself in-person to realization/fulfilment of objectives as outlined above. Shall wait for suitable offers/G.Os./ordinances/policy documents from the Govt. of India regarding my role as Principal Investigator in the above project please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

Consolidated File Access:

Consolidated file is available at

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Thank you for your time and respected attention

With Respectful Thanks & Warmest Regards

(Dr Prabhu Britto Albert)

www.ijbst.org

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Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Annexure

Thanks to President's Secretariat for forwarding consolidated file of "Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe"

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893979898160521416>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @Raj Nath Singh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following communication please.

Thanks to President's Secretariat for forwarding consolidated file of "Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe" to The Secretary, Department of Telecom please.

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy-dot@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Feb 24, 2025, 3:57 PM

subject: Fwd: Submitting consolidated file for Fin Min Access for evaluation please. With Thanks to @BSNL_TN for restoring FTTH connectivity in just a few minutes please.

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India

Ref:

Consolidated File Access:

Consolidated file is available at

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

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Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Copy with Respects:

@AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity

Thanks to Jayalalitha Amma, Thanks to God, Thanks to Devi, Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893979898160521416>

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1894003689985040595>

Replying to @NarendraModi

Incidentally its Amma's Birthday today.

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1893979898160521416>

Thanks to Jayalalitha Amma, Thanks to God, Thanks to Devi, Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn

Editorial

Proposed Broad outline for initial starting of the project

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1894293697786757139>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please – proposed broad outline for initial starting of the project.

Preparatory period:

- Temples identified by the Govt. of India may be notified through an extraordinary Gazette notification and handed over to the Defence Ministry.
- A 48 day preparatory period for the identified research team is suggested, wherein, the research team will wait in front of one or more identified Devi Temples, stay in temple provided location (or at home, if nearby), and also have only temple provided satvik food or home cooked satvik food and beseech Blessings of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, and then start the project, in accordance with time and dates notified by the Govt. of India
- In the 48 day preparatory period, the Defence Ministry may ensure that the entire temple premises and surrounding 100 m radial area is swept off electronic detectors/transducers/communication/electronic equipment and all CCTV networks in and around the temple will be taken over by teams of Defence personnel, coz there's no rule that says that Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga may descend only as a Radio Signal. She may choose to descend in the visible spectrum also, and can be shifted electronically to the desired bandwidth or frequency spectrum.
- Also, the 48 day preparatory period, will help Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to complete immediate or urgent tasks at Her hand, and then walk ahead of us/ walk with us, for many centuries or millenia to come; in the present and in the future.
- Also the 48 day preparatory period will help the interministerial task force to assess the current situation, and also prepare ahead to handle the situation; coz initially, the research activity will start at one temple identified by the Govt. of India, but in due course of time, so many temples will be researched simultaneously, and that will create a huge anticipation among the people.

News & Status Updates:

- Periodic updates on research activity may be provided by the inter ministerial task force via approved channels of information dissemination.

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Food for the Research Team:

- The Research Team, aware of the tremendous responsibility before them, should ensure that they have only identified satvik food provided to them or have home cooked satvik food for the entire duration of the research, as approved/notified by the interministerial task force.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India

Consolidated File Access:

Consolidated file is available at

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Statutory Warning on Potential High Energy Burnout:

The potential risk of high energy burnout for the research team is hereby declared. Ofcourse Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga will be aware of the -80 db threshold for biological tissue damage and may descend at lower energies only, but even otherwise, accidents can happen due to human error and potential risk of high energy burnout for the research team may be there. Though possibility of high energy burnout for the research team may be near zero, but still, it is good that the research team is aware of the potential risk of high energy burnout. Consequently, the interministerial task force, may please concentrate on high energy fire hazards and its handling.

Consent, Last wishes & Dying Declaration by participating Scientists of the Research Team:

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1894633566321218025>

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@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please – Consent, Last Wishes & Dying Declaration by participating Scientists of the Research Team.

In Tamil, there's a saying “கண்டவர் விண்டிலர் விண்டவர் கண்டிலர்” which might imply that the eyes that have seen God ceases to communicate eternal universal truths. A possible explanation of this could be that once the native beholds God, there might be a sync of Universal truths between that of the God consciousness and human consciousness of the Native. Since some of the eternal truths are hidden in this human life, that Native who has sync'ed with the Consciousness of God is forbidden from sharing it with those who are still alive. An unexpected outcome would be that the soul of the Native may choose to leave the human body and go with God, caused due to a sudden and fatal cardiac arrest due to heightened states of altered consciousness or could be accompanied with a high energy burnout of the body into ash or dissolve into thin air as aerosol type nano particles.

Whether it happens as outlined above, or takes on an unexpected new trajectory, the conclusion remains the same and that is, there is a very high possibility of death of the participating scientists of the Research Team. Consequently, a need for consent, last wishes and dying declaration needs to be obtained from the participating Scientists of the Research Team prior to starting the project of the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe. At the same time, the Govt. of India is also duty bound to honor the memory of those Scientists who walked into the project, willingly giving up their life for the good of the Nation, the World and the Universe. Consequently, the Govt. of India may be pleased to provide a State funeral for the deceased Scientist, along with full Military Honors; and offering a dignified education & life for the nominee of the deceased Scientist; It would be the pleasure of the Govt. of India to provide an ex-gratia amount to the nominee of the deceased Scientist.

Suggested Template for Consent, Last Wishes & Dying Declaration by Scientists of the Research Team:

Consent, Last Wishes & Dying Declaration

I _____, hereby solemnly affirm that I am joining in as a Scientist in the Research Team of The Search for the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe of my own volition and not compelled to do so.

I am aware that on beholding the original manifestation of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga, my soul may get overjoyed and leave my body behind, in which case, I may be dead.

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

In the event of my death, in pursuit of the aforesaid project, I hereby authorise the Govt. of India to take over my dead body, and do my last rites as a State Funeral with full military honors.

I am also aware, that if I have been born into another religion, my last rites at the State funeral may not be the same as that of the religion that I have been born into and consequently, my family, relatives and friends are kindly requested not to inconvenience the Govt. of India in changing the modalities of my last rites and let it happen according to the Hindu religion & its procedures.

I hereby declare _____ as my nominee to receive the full benefits from the Govt. of India, including Govt. support until completion of tertiary academic degree (doctoral level), and a suitable job in the Govt. of India (In case the nominee is a minor as on date of the Scientist's death, the Govt. job may be given to the surviving guardian of the nominee based on his/her academic qualifications)

Contact Details of Nominee:

Nominee Name: _____ Aadhar number (if available): _____

Is Nominee Minor (as on date of this declaration)? Yes/No

If Yes, name of surviving guardian of Nominee: _____

Aadhar number (if available) _____

Mobile phone numbers, email ids and relevant postal address:

Last Wishes, if any:

Signature: _____

(Name: _____)

Date: _____

Editorial

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimanAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
@DoT_India

Consolidated File Access:

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108emLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Shift in Global Economic Power Balance & Consequent hurdles necessitating 24x7 surveillance of scientists in the research team postulating consent by Scientists in Research team for continuous surveillance by Military Intelligence.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895088425696665651>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

The population of India is 145 crores and still counting higher

(<https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/india-population/>). Such a huge population might have been a burden on various factors. But as regards The Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe, this huge population is a blessing indeed. Apart from healing, it also offers scope for a huge untapped potential in Wellness. Even if services are offered at a subsidy, still, it has potential for roping in a huge revenue. Since this proposal advocates revenues/returns into the Govt. of India Treasury, this revenue can also be used by the Govt. of India to address other areas that need attention. Consequently, a wholesome improvement in the Quality of Life maybe achieved on various metrics as in Human Development Index (HDI), Gini Coefficient, Poverty Rate, Employment Rate and Job Quality, Access to Education, Healthcare Access and Quality, Housing Quality and Affordability, Safety and Security, Environmental Quality, Social and Political Stability, Life Satisfaction and Happiness. These improvements in the Quality of Life may reflect in

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better health and prosperity of the Nation; consequently causing changes in the economic power structures of the world; and we can be sure that NOT all vested groups will accept the changes in the economic power structures of the world; elevating India as a very prominent Nation in terms of economic power of the next few centuries. Hence we will have to face obstacles and hurdles to achieving our objectives, and it will be in our best interests to safeguard our assets; our first and primary assets being the Scientists involved in the Search for the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga in healing the Universe. Since the previous sections have already recommended placing the identified temples for experimentation under protection of the defence ministry; a natural follow up would be to place the Scientists involved in the aforesaid effort also under protection of the defence ministry. Consequently, every Scientist in the Research Team will have to provide consent for continuous 24x7 surveillance by Military Intelligence until the end of the project. The author is aware that this will cause a bottleneck in the diversity of Scientists in the Research Team and the Research Team may have to be constituted only by Scientists of Indian Origin residing currently in India, but at the same time, it will also be a blessing in disguise, as will be outlined in the next section.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
@DoT_India

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Interministerial task force under instruction from @PMOIndia/@HMOIndia may please invite self-nominations from Scientists (from multi-disciplinary & inter-disciplinary realms) of Bharatiya Origin residing in Bharat to serve on the Research Team for the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga for healing the Universe

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895178606177067283>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

Originally, it was intended to invite Scientists from across the World, so that good diversity in knowledge and expertise can be had in tapping the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe.

But, as the proposal developed, it was understood that there is a glaring possibility of Mukti, wherein the soul happily departs and unites with the Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga, resulting in death of the concerned Scientist on the Research Team. Accompanied with the fact that the memory of the concerned Scientist needs to be honored by the Nation with a State Funeral and full Military honors; therein lies an inconvenience that the Home Nation of the Scientist (if he/she is of foreign Nationality/Citizenship) should also agree for a State Funeral and full Military honors, so that the funeral may be a joint exercise between the militaries of Bharat and the home Nation of the deceased Scientist, done at the home Nation of the deceased Scientist. Else, deceased body of the concerned Scientist has to be embalmed, then packed in a Coffin and sent via Civilian aircraft after handing over to the nearest family member or relative. Further complexities arise with 24x7 surveillance by Military Intelligence for the Scientists serving on the aforesaid Research Team. If the Scientist does not reside in Bharat and is not of Bharatiya origin, then differences of opinion regarding personal space, privacy, diet, etc. start elevating as conflict, which complicates the situation. Consequently, we are now constrained to populate the Research Team with Scientists of Bharatiya origin currently residing in Bharat only. Now here again, we face a difficulty. How does a Scientist earn his/her position as a Research Team member on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe? Is it Scholastic aptitude? If Scholastic aptitude alone was key, then we may not be here discussing this at all, coz someone with a very high scholastic aptitude might have completed this research work and brought it out as a new method of Medicine long long ago, and it wouldn't have waited for us to even contemplate it. So, Scholastic aptitude might only be a screening or threshold criteria, but the actual criteria for earning a position in the Research Team for the aforesaid project might be something else. For a Scientist, what other criteria could be there? Lets ponder for a moment. Perhaps, it could be moral ground. The Scientist who earns his/her position as a Research Team Member on the aforesaid project should have earned the moral ground to stand in front of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to tap her into an electronic device built for the purpose. And from where can this moral ground be earned? Beyond the financial returns or profits of this project, which human

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beings alone can contribute, can animals, plants or nature or environment or the planet or the Universe pay for services received in healing them through the Radio /UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga? It is not possible. So beyond the financial returns of this project, the quantum of service to plants, animals, nature, environment, the planet and the universe outweigh the money earned through subsidized clinical treatment to human beings. Consequently, this moral ground as applicable to the aforesaid project might be a moral ground earned through service to mankind or society or nature or the environment or the planet or the universe, over a prolonged period of time in the past, upto now. Consequently, when self-nominations are invited by the Inter Ministerial Task force under instruction from @PMOIndia / @HMOIndia, it may be suggested that those scientists who nominate themselves to the Research Team of the aforesaid project, may please provide sufficient evidence of having translated their scholastic knowledge and experience as service to society or mankind or plants or animals or environment or nature or the planet or the universe. Further, nominations for the self alone can be done, due to the risk of death as outlined in the previous sections. Nominations for others cannot be done or entertained for the same reason. The Inter Ministerial Task Force may seek the advice of @PMOIndia and @HMOIndia and narrow down the selection list and attempt to zero in on the ones chosen to serve on the Research Team for the aforesaid project. If suggestions for selection from the Principal Investigator, in this case, myself, is required, I shall be happy to provide. Else, the Inter Ministerial Task force can narrow down the selection list and attempt to choose the Scientists who would serve on the Research Team for the aforesaid project. As Principal Investigator, I do not have any reservation in working with anyone. So, whoever is chosen to be on the Team, is acceptable to me. Care may be taken that all selected Scientists are junior to the highest ranking Secretary in the Govt of India (currently in service) coz Vidya Gaurav should not lead to disagreements or conflicts of opinion, which can have possible potential for derailing or delaying the project.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
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And hence it is thus recorded that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga healed His Holiness Pope Francis. So, would I be called as “Papal Divine Physician” or “Brahma rishi”?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895487248138973310>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/ABC/status/1892984629906288822>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892043019961897181>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/AFpost/status/1892487608334180831>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892462680104915225>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

In humility the following communication please.

While your Swiss Guard was reportedly rehearsing for ur funeral (Ref 3), we were here interceding for u with Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, for ur life and health (Ref 2).

As outlined in Ref 4, we were waiting for news of ur recovery, to record that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga have healed you.

You may be the Head of the Catholic Church, but to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, u are also Her Child.

And I took such a huge leap of Faith, coz people don't usually accept good. It will take them time. You need to shake them out of their habit, so that they can think and accept good. So, I risked labelling as u as our First Celebrity patient, though we don't have the experimental setup established for tapping and applying the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing the Universe. And hence, as declared in Ref 4, their grace upon u, was invoked via human consciousness fields.

Ofcourse, it was a huge risk that I was taking.

If any vested group felt that the credit of healing u, should not go to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, ur life could even be put to danger.

So, I included the alternate clause of the unfavorable outcome in Ref 4, just to throw them off guard.

And they read it, and didn't understand the depth of communication to cause any harm to ur life.

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So, now, in accordance with Ref 4. communicated to u on 12:03 PM IST · Feb 20, 2025, we hereby record that Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga have healed your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, and may this mark the beginning of fraternity across the entire world. May there be Peace and Love.

Now, your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, its been too stressful. Can we unwind on a lighter note please? Would I be called as "Papal Divine Physician" or shall I request our beloved brother H.E. Shri @NarendraModi @PMOIndia to prefix my name with "Brahma rishi" and gift me a tiger skin?

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

P.S. Incidentally today is also the death anniversary of my mother and her maiden name was also Bagavathy

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Thanks to God, Thanks to Devi, Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn. Thanks to the President's Secretariat for forwarding to the Home Secretary (Mar 3, 2025, 5:28 PM) "Consent, Last wishes & Dying Declaration by participating Scientists of the Research Team"

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1896577609431134688>

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@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1894633566321218025>

In humility the following communication please.

A humble note of Thanks is hereby submitted to the President's Secretariat for forwarding to the Home Secretary. Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: Ajay Bhalla <hshso@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 3, 2025, 5:28 PM

subject: Fwd: Consent, Last wishes & Dying Declaration by participating Scientists of the Research Team:

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimanAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India

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Was a massive money laundering operation between Coimbatore & Canada tweaked to create headache to me by spoiling my career, family and family assets to do a hostile takeover of the "Search for the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe"?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1896930216918024615>

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Editorial

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex,

Was a massive money laundering operation between Coimbatore & Canada tweaked to create headache to me by spoiling my career, family & family assets to do a hostile takeover of the “Search for the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe”?

Did the Bishop study and obtain his DD DCL or did he buy the DD DCL in the black market?

Did he commit a grave blunder by trying to hunt me down as collateral benefit? Ofcourse, he cannot be expected to know who a native is, who holds a mool nakshatra 3rd pada with Pisces Lagna and having earned the Sun and the Saturn in the 5th house as stars/stripes on his chestplate or shoulder straps with Ketu in the 2nd house and Jupiter ruling over an enemy house as “பகை வீடு கொண்டான்”, a native who has earned his position to sit on a tiger skin or hold a Brahma rishi title, after Sage Vashista and Sage Vishwamitra.

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895487248138973310>

On a lighter note, wouldn't it have been easy for the Bishop to deposit the money with the Vatican Bank and transfer it to Canada or was he cheating u also or was he sponsoring any antinational activity on foreign shores?

Incidentally, today is the eve of my mother's death anniversary also, coz when she died on Feb 28, 2001, it was also Ash Wednesday; and her maiden name was Bagavathy.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India

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Regularization of sins, transparency and integration into society

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897534686039031851>

Editorial

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1896930216918024615>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/changu311/status/1897408464609275911>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/RepLuna/status/1892365936331469155>

Ref 4: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reichskonkordat>

Ref 5: <https://www.cbc.ca/news/canada/edmonton/pope-francis-maskwacis-apology-full-text-1.6531341>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

Your esteemed attention is drawn to Matthew 6:24 RSVCE, which indicates that no man can serve two masters. Either he can serve the pleasures of the flesh or he can serve God in a moral way. Headaches arise only when someone tries to do justice to both pleasures of the flesh and service to God, one of the best examples being Ref 1. cited above.

Hence, to prevent such happenings, why don't we regularize sin and make it transparent? Why should absolution of sin be a secret? If sin was regularized, more money could have been laundered in Ref 1 above, and also prospectively in the Russian Ukraine War (Ref 3) , or in the Jew Holocaust also (Ref 4).

Only cause sin was not regularized, the Vatican may have to be embarrassed due to the Reichskonkordat, an agreement between the Vatican and the Nazi regime, that gave legitimacy to the Nazi regime, in other words, caused the Jew Holocaust indirectly. If such is the case, then if Hitler is accused of murdering millions of Jews, then the Vatican also has to shoulder equal responsibility over the millions of deaths. But unfortunately, the Vatican tries to portray as having holding a moral ground. Due that portrayal of moral ground, the Reichskonkordat is a pain in the behind, if more people come to know of it, it will stink more. And coz of the moral ground assumed by the Vatican, the Vatican also cant keep the Reichskonkordat inside the gastrointestinal system.

Now, lets consider a different alternative. Let go of the moral ground, and accept that the Church is also human, as much human as other members of the society. Then it will be accepted, that the Church can also sin and nobody will bat an eyelid, coz its just normal

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happening. But only when the Church tries to maintain a holy aura around it, forgetting that they only crucified an innocent man in Jerusalem, and to escape the prick of their conscience, formed committees and declared that man as the Son of God, and using European colonialism, pushed the theory into the far ends of the world. And in the midst of all of this, there come to light so many things that cause further embarrassment and even cause the Pope to apologize (Ref 5).

The difficulty arises only when a fair moral ground is attempted to be maintained in front of society, while at the same time, doing immoral acts in the dark.

So, my argument is, if sin is regularized, and if the illusion of moral ground is just let go, there's no headache na? So, to regularize sin, all it needs is transparency and hence reading the above paragraphs in conjunction with Matthew 6:24 RSVCE, I shall be humbled to propose to the Govt. of India, the "Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025" in the near future.

It shall be the pleasure of the Govt. to introduce the suggestion as submitted, or further, enhance or reduce the submission and get it passed in Parliament and enact it into law with Presidential Assent. Once this model starts yielding fruit, the same model can be copied by other Nations too, and u can also heave a sigh of relief, coz no more situations will surface that might require ur apology.

I believe that your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, having attempted to regularize so many aspects of the Church, would also bless this effort to regularize sin.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India

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<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Suggestion to Govt. of India for “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897554757658583394>

May please be read together with Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897534686039031851>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility, the following submission please.

Money is the root cause of all evil in society, and has potential to cause more evil, when shrouded in secrecy. Hence, when transparency is introduced, the transparency by itself may cause a lot of evil to be curtailed.

Consequently, all finances in Religious processes and places of worship operating under the jurisdiction of the Indian territorial sovereignty will come under the direct control of the Govt of India. No money can be collected or used, except using the Govt. provided digital facility.

The digital facility will have a backend comprising of an AI based training model and also a hierarchical human facility comprising Govt. officials, drawn in based on requirement, including but not limited to a judicial panel comprising of eminent serving/retired judges of the Supreme Court of India (as the requirement may be).

The AI based training model will be built over knowledge based input provided by officials designated by various religions and law officers of the Govt. of India for this purpose.

Whenever money has to be collected from amongst members of any particular religion, the proposal (as a choice among various inputs) will first be entered into the digital facility provided by the Govt. of India.

Since, it's a pre-existing choice, it will be immediately matched with choices that can be approved. If it can be approved, a unique National approval proceeding will be generated and issued. When money is being collected, it will again be decided whether only members of that

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particular religion can donate or members of other religions also can donate. Based on the approval, money can be collected only digitally, accompanied with biometric based authentication as in Aadhaar along with PAN number details (to track huge payments that can possibly mismatch with declared financial returns).

If money has to be spent, again, a proposal needs to be submitted via the digital facility, by choosing one amongst many previously approved choices. The AI backend will check, if the selected choice violates any of the particular recommendations of the related religion. If a penance is prescribed, then the prescribed penance can also be issued officially to the seeker, so that he can spend the money as requested, and coz penance is prescribed, can do the penance also to absolve himself off the sin.

Now, if the selected choice violates law, then the AI backend will check if an exact match is present in the database. If an exact match is present, the AI back end will present to a recommended judge for human approval, and issue the judgement also beforehand, so that the individual can decide whether to spend the money for that unlawful purpose and accept the pre-delivered judgement or to submit a withdrawal request for earlier submitted requisition, in which case, neither the money will be given to him, nor will he be required to serve the sentence, coz crime has not been committed. If he chooses to accept the judgement and go ahead with the crime, a suitable panel of govt. officers will be assigned to him, so that he commits the crime under govt. supervision, so that no other human is harmed due to his actions, and after committing the crime can surrender to the nearest judicial magistrate, to accept previously delivered sentence.

Wherever an expert opinion or judicial bench opinion is required, the AI backend will refer to the expert or judicial bench prior to approving payment of money.

Now, when there is complete transparency in the inflow and outflow of money, sin is regularized and will automatically reduce, as much as crime also.

The success of this method can be monitored over time, along with analysis of crime rate over previous periods of time, and if crime rate reduces, the Govt. may be pleased to help other Nations to implement it in their Nation too.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India

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Addendum to Suggestion to Govt. of India for “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897982451924058317>

May please be read together with Ref 1:

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897554757658583394>

Ref 2: The Threat of Religious Extremism – Oxford Academic

<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199975907.003.0002> Pages 9–34 Published:

February 2013

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility, the following submission please.

In furtherance of suggestion to Govt. of India for Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025, the following points may also be taken into consideration please.

There starts emerging a new terminology called religious extremism which is also attracting some good research initiatives. Religious extremism, is given chance to germinate, grow and yield undesirable fruits by virtue of the paradox in the establishment of religion locally. Ambiguities as in scope of service, limits of authority, etc. may contribute to the growth of religious extremism. However, for any state to be able to function in accordance with its Constitution, there can be only a sole authority in the form of Govt. formed in accordance with the Constitution. There cannot be an alternate authority that functions as a Deep State, with no legal validity, overarching zones of influence, secret money transfers, etc.

Consequently, Govt. and Religion may have to come to terms that Govt. will be the sole authority and Religion cannot usurp the State through shadow means. If Religion wants to

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play a part in governance, they have to register themselves as a Political party and go through the necessary procedure in law. However, if they register themselves as a Society and still have political ambitions, they will be forced to first create the actual problem that they profess that they are the solution. Usually, the problem might neither be actual nor existing in reality. It may be existing only in their minds. Consequently, they will have to bring the fictional problem existing in their minds into reality, and hence, there will be a lot of dramas or political narratives staged to ensure that the State believes that the problem actually exists. And the same religion benefits in a double way. When they create the problem, they benefit once. When they offer the solution, they benefit again. These benefits usually result in tangible money. Since they cannot accept in public that they made a fortune out of people's misfortune, they will have to find ways to stash it safely somewhere on the planet without anyone's knowledge. On a minimal scale, it may manifest as money laundering. On a maximal scale, it might manifest as religious extremism. However it is called, its all only money. And this arises only when Religion enters politics without declaring its political intentions. Hence, it is suggested that "Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025" may please provide options for Religions to declare their political intentions and receive options for registering as a Political party, consequent to which, they should not indulge in religious activity but can only engage in political activity. However, if the Religion chooses to register only as a religious society, then they have to realise that they are banned from political activity, either directly or through proxies.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
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Was the aforesaid massive money laundering program from Coimbatore to Canada, financing drug cartels or terror outfits?

Editorial

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1898061383922860204>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1896930216918024615>

Ref 2: <https://organiser.org/2025/03/07/281274/bharat/ed-raids-in-tamil-nadu-crackdown-on-banned-pfi-and-tasmac-irregularities/>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/NewsArenaIndia/status/1897500199372943663>

Ref 4: https://www.business-standard.com/india-news/9-separatist-outfits-have-bases-in-canada-deportation-requests-ignored-123091901075_1.html

Ref 5: <https://pi.math.cornell.edu/~lipa/mec/lesson1.html>

Ref 6: <https://insightcrime.org/news/interview/how-mexican-cartels-settled-canada/>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

Its been less than 72 hours that we discussed as in Ref 1 cited above than an Enforcement Directorate @dir_ed raid has happened in Tamil Nadu Ref 2, especially related to the DMK Minister in charge of the Kongu region within which Coimbatore falls and another DMK MP who runs a university and other educational Institutions. But the strange fact remains that apart from alcohol issues, some sort of terror investigation has also been kicked off. It seemed to be just a simple discussion, coz we talk everything under the sun and above the sun too in public. But when a complicated random long term seemingly-unconnected behaviour is observed, then have to apply the Chaos theory to connect Ref 1 and Ref 2. Now, if Ref 1 and Ref 2 are connected, there rises a million dollar question, whether the Bishop was financing the Mexican drug cartels that found their way to Canada Ref 6 or was he financing terror through the Canadian route Ref 4? So, was the Bishop such a fool that he thought that if he'd knock off my job and ensure that I don't get an academic job again in India, I'll join in with him and do money laundering for terror outfits and drug cartels? U know, ur Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, this is one of the first times in my life, that I feel proud for having opted to live on alms than to compromise with whoever was hitting me and live a life again, perhaps as a slave to them. I thank all those who helped me to have a morsel of food and a drop of water, coz its quite difficult to live 11 years without a job, just on alms. So, was the Bishop cheating God, you and the people and also himself by doing such a dirty job?

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Requesting emergency attention & Govt. of India approvals for the “Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing” please

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1898328621196145132>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

Ref: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/health-fitness/health-news/54-of-ncr-citizens-facing-viral-fever-with-covid-like-symptoms-how-to-stay-safe/articleshow/118781247.cms>

In humility, the following submission please.

Requesting emergency attention & approvals for the “Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing” please.

In humility, the following suggestions are placed before ur esteemed selves for consideration and immediate action please.

- Immunity has been suggested as a concern in article cited above.
- Those who have already been affected may please continue their medical treatment.
- In the meantime, we can investigate for the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga and beam the signals primarily using communication satellites across the entire length and breadth of the Nation. In the meantime, we can try to develop a prototype at the @DRDO_India, and after having successfully developed and tested the prototype, can go in for mass production of Radiation Therapy Equipment to serve in Govt. tertiary

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hospitals & interested private hospitals in every district in India through the @DRDO_India or we can rope in MSME's for the same.

- Among those who have already been clinically affected, whoever, wishes to enroll as a volunteer for testing, may be permitted to do so, with clinical support from the medical physicians treating them, so that their rate of healing can be clinically documented.
- Since the article claims that 54% of households in Delhi-NCR have been affected, its not sure whether the AIIMS Delhi will be able to directly participate in testing healing rate of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga. Consequently, it is suggested to form a **Consortium of Hospitals across the Nation**, under the leadership of the nearest AIIMS hospitals, so that we can have a network of Hospitals across the Nation, where volunteers (who are already affected as per article referred above) can offer themselves for studying rate of healing of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga. Initially, we can supplement them with clinical treatment, and when the confidence level of the doctor, the patient, and the clinical monitoring committee is high, the volunteer can be subjected only to the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga. This necessitates that we also form a **clinical monitoring committee comprising of the best doctors (who concentrate on research) in the Nation**
- Giving due consideration to the nature of the clinical conditions, as outlined in Ref above, I am humbled to reconsider the preparatory days recommended as 48 days in previous paragraphs to 48 hours or 108 hours prior to entering the Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga Temple please.
- Since the Telecom Secretary is already on board, as a senior Telecom professional, he will know what all we will require to tap and handle radio signals, and consequently, on an adhoc basis, he can transfer equipment temporarily from BSNL or MTNL and the Finance Secretary also on board, may please help him. Emergency funds as required may please be cleared by the Finance Secretary and sent to a designated holding account of the Govt. of India.
- Nominations as suggested in previous sections may please be called for, for constituting the research team.
- It shall be the discretion of the @PMOIndia and @HMOIndia to expand the Interministerial Task force comprising of Senior Secretaries of the Govt. of India to include the Senior Secretaries of the following ministries, apart from the Secretaries of Finance, Telecom and Home who have already been roped in by the President's Secretariat.
 - Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare
 - Ministry of Animal Husbandry And Dairying
 - Department of Atomic Energy

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- Ministry of Ayush
- Ministry of Commerce & Industry
- Ministry of Corporate Affairs
- Ministry of Culture
- Ministry of Defence
- Ministry of Earth Sciences
- Ministry of Education
- Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology
- Ministry of Environment, Forests & Climate Change
- Ministry of External Affairs
- Ministry of Health & Family Welfare
- Ministry of Information and Broadcasting
- Department of Investment & Public Asset Management
- Ministry of Law and Justice
- Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises
- Ministry of New & Renewable Energy
- Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs
- Ministry of Power
- Ministry of Railways
- Ministry of Road Transport and Highways
- Ministry of Rural Development
- Ministry of Science and Technology
- Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship
- Department of Space
- Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation
- Ministry of Tourism
- Ministry of Women and Child Development
- Let us initiate our work now itself, so that we may have some breathing time to think plan and execute, instead of running at breakneck speed due to emergency conditions that may arise in future.

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Requesting transfer of equipment from BSNL/MTNL please in Continuation of Requesting emergency attention & Govt. of India approvals for the “Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing” please

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In humility the following submission please.

Was scouting for information, and landed on a retired @BSNL_CHTD Official, who assured me not to worry, coz all, that I was seeking, was available in-house. Since this is will be a Govt. of India project, and revenues will also go to the Govt. of India only, resources can be shared from Govt. Departments/Ministries and there wouldn't arise a need to spend money to create such resources. Under condition that I should NOT thank him publicly; the following knowledge was handed down to me. Since I've also agreed that someday in future, when H.E. The @PMOIndia gives me time to meet in person, I shall disclose his name to The @PMOIndia, so that he can be thanked by the @PMOIndia as per discretion of the @PMOIndia.

The setup proposed is a private telephone exchange network for the sake of the project to Detect & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing. Since it may be difficult to install a BSNL/MTNL BTS covering all three quadrants inside the sanctum sanctorum of the temple, it is suggested that a booster can be employed. The booster will also radiate identification signal, and hence it will be convenient to identify which booster is radiating the signal. Further, until testing and validation clinically, the radio signal of Ma

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Bagavathy/Ma Durga, cannot be multiplexed with existing communication network, and hence, a separate base station (or in other words, a minimal lines telephone exchange) may be put up outside the temple. BSNL has got a Nationwide optical fibre network. Consequently, we may require to rent only one optical fiber (which may cost 20,000 rupees per year) and if we can bring in the hospital, within one kilometer distance from the temple, cost will not be high.

This means that we need to put up another base station or telephone exchange at the hospital site. Since the BSNL BTS is a Transceiver (both a transmitter and a receiver), until the Radiation Therapy equipment prototype is provided by @DRDO_India, we can use a BSNL BTS itself covering 360 degrees for irradiating the patient.

Once testing and clinical validation is complete, we can multiplex the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga into the regular communication network, so that people can receive healing whenever they are communicating (these are the general public, who have not yet fallen sick and hence there may not be a requirement to heal them via controlled irradiation from the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga), and the livestock, plants, animals, lands, water and the environment can receive healing via radiation from communication satellites.

There was a very strong intuitive feeling, that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, being mothers themselves, will make it easy for us, but the difficulty that we faced, was identifying where was that easy part. Well, we've been led to it, and lets continue with the faith that our absolute surrender to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, accompanied with our consciousness links, will make our further journey also easy.

The reason for suggesting BSNL/MTNL is that they are Govt. Departments, though branded as corporations, and its easy to transfer resources just via paper work, while private providers may find it difficult to spare resources for this project, especially when the industry is too competitive. So, lets not burden private providers. We can use whatever resources the BSNL & MTNL have.

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@CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

Cost effectiveness & Safety

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899083249361813921>

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In humility the following submission please.

The cost effectiveness & safety of the aforesaid suggestions stems due to the following:

1. We are going to use only in-house equipment from BSNL/MTNL, implying that equipment that is in use currently, & consequently, it can be handled by current or past BSNL/MTNL employees. We do not have to train anyone in handling or use of equipment.
2. It shall be the discretion of the Govt. to provide a suitable over-time allowance or special pay for the employees of BSNL/MTNL who have arrived on deputation. Apart from their salary provided by BSNL/MTNL, they can be provided additional salary as over-time or as special pay for the days worked in the project.
3. It shall be the discretion of BSNL/MTNL, to provide current employees on deputation, or recall past employees who departed on VRS, with due consideration to prevalent workload and demands for service.
4. The research setup will be the property of the defence ministry and the defence ministry will be responsible for the safety of human and electronic and physical tangible assets and intangible assets – this is suggested to reduce sabotage and conspiracy.
5. Even if sabotage or conspiracy occurs, it is easy to analyse and find out, coz cash will be paid only in hand, and that cash can only be invested in gold or real-estate. Monitoring of gold purchases and real-estate transactions, construction and restoration of buildings can help to reduce sabotage and conspiracy.
6. It shall be the discretion of the Govt. of India to provide the radio signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga as a wellness signal for the normal population (other than

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patients) as a free service or as a paid add-on service along with their mobile recharge or post-paid subscription fees, in which case, the Govt. of India will have to evolve a suitable mechanism with mobile service providers for the provision of service and collection of charges. Care needs to be taken so that the multiplexed radio signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga into the communication network is not corrupted or adulterated by sabotage or conspiracy. Consequently, the Govt. of India may have to play an active role forever, in multiplexing the radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga into the mobile communication networks.

7. It shall be the discretion of the Govt. of India to fix the charges for service and provide the radio signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga as a healing signal for patients enrolling for the program, based on clinical suggestion, post clinical validation and monitoring of rate of healing on sample population studies. Treatment at subsidized charges can be provided in Govt. tertiary hospitals while treatment at private hospitals can be provided at a premium charge, with revenue sharing between the hospital and the Govt of India.
8. Since the backbone will be a private telephone exchange network, which will later get multiplexed into existing mobile telephone networks, neither the device for irradiating patients, nor any part of the tapping set up can be bought or sold publicly in the open market, but will have to be bought or sold only by registered hospitals under govt. supervision. Proprietary rights to technology and its application will rest with the Govt. of India. This is done so that the Govt of India will have a perennial supply of revenue, which can be used in various ways for the good of the Nation.
9. Service to other Nations can be done on revenue sharing basis based on new or existing bilateral or trilateral or multilateral agreements
10. The Scientists serving on the research team will need to be paid a salary, and it shall be the discretion of the Govt. to reward them suitably, monetary wise and honor-wise, as they are willingly walking into the research team, with prior knowledge that their soul may depart happily from their body on encounter with Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga to merge with the consciousness of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga.
11. The defence ministry personnel serving in the project, similar to the BSNL/MTNL personnel may be paid over-time salary or special pay for their days of service in the project.
12. Since the project relies more on consciousness links, there may not be much danger to equipment, but potential danger to humans cant be ruled out. Steps may need to be taken to provide safe, certified drinking water, satvik food & medicines to all who are working in the project, from the Scientists, to the defence personnel to the BSNL/MTNL personnel, or any other human who works in the project, coz chemical poisoning will

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remain a risk to reckon with, though tantric poisoning might lose its steam due to engagement with Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga

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With Request to @ElonMusk & @X to clear the entire message please, for sake of transparency

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Editorial

The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn't comprehend at all.

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In humility the following submission please.

Every civilization that survived on the planet and on other inhabitable planets should have come to the same point that we have come now; a planetary damage beyond repair, that requires only divinity to repair it accompanied with the chance to gain supremacy over the universe as a reward. However, the latter part seems to have been misunderstood by many, as that supremacy that is achieved through bloodshed, sabotage and conspiracy; without realizing that that supremacy is short lived, and leads only to extinction of both the destroyer and the destroyed; for the Universe has not been built on destruction, though those vested groups that associated God with light had to inadvertently label pure energy as dark energy & got the entire narrative wrong. Contrast this with the Indian Gods and Goddesses who were dark or blue in complexion. We got the narrative right, that dark energy is pure energy.

Now, during the times that a civilization reaches or is about to reach its end, the knowledge is handed down. However, some groups went the extremist way. Some groups pretended that they were holding moral ground, and hence couldn't do wrong in public, and consequently thrived on sabotages and conspiracies that thrived in the dark; unbeknownst to the outside world. Its now come to us. The fate of our civilization and the supremacy over all other civilizations that exist in the 3 dimensional universe, and in higher and lower dimensions wait for us. If we don't perceive it correctly; then there's nobody else who can do it better. One day, our civilization will also meet its watery or icy or sandy grave, and some intelligent species that evolves after us will study about us through archaeological excavations. The civilizations that lie buried in watery, icy and sandy graves are testimony to the above. We can now choose to uplift or heal our civilization and other civilizations; and through the knowledge that

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Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga hand down to us, heal other Civilizations also in other parallel universes and higher/lower dimensions. Since Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga have played a very significant role in the creation of the Universe, it is assumed that they possess the knowledge over the various systems of quantum equations that hold the Universe together; and when we try to serve mankind and all lifeforms, nature, the planet and the Universe through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga, we can be sure that the knowledge of the entire Universe, and its key constructs will be revealed to us, which can even usher in quantum transportation/quantum teleportation too, across various universes and dimensions. Since healing or giving life is similar to creation, and since we will be assisting Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga in their work in the Universe, we can be sure that our effort will bring in a golden era in the history of the planet, and milk and honey shall flow down our rivers again. Since the Universe is held together through love and sacrifice, our efforts in healing the entirety of the Universe will give us the Supremacy of the Universe. Stated in other words, one day, all of us would have to shed our human body and continue in our consciousness journey, and there, @NarendraModi Bhai, u will find ur chance to stand as the Sun in a new solar system, in an infantile universe, and @AmitShah Bhai, u will find ur chance to stand as the Jupiter/Venus in the same or different solar system, if we pull this straight. And as far as I'm concerned, I'm tired of my extra lives through rebirths (as indicated in my kundli), to the point that even if I'm hit by a running heavy vehicle or poisoned, still I keep coming back alive. Did u know that the neurosurgeon who examined me after the bus ran over me in 1990 declared me dead at the spot of the traffic accident near his clinic, and was surprised to find that its me, alive and receiving treatment in his own department at the Govt. Medical College hospital at Coimbatore after a few days? This life is itself an extra life for me, and in this one lifetime, I've already died 12 times, once run over by a bus, and 11 times poisoned; and I may be held to live just to get this work completed. I'm also tired of my extra lives, and I need some rest and a good sleep in the arms of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, as a child. So, let us bring the entire planet together in the effort to tap Ma Bagavathy /Ma Durga as a Radio Signal and consequently heal all of mankind, all life forms, nature, the planet and the universe. The money that we may earn through the project may be massive, as measured in human terms, but considering the quantum of service that we do to the Universe, it will be a mere pittance compared to the quantum of our service. So lets start the project and we do have three major transits that will assist us in our journey, viz., the Saturn Transit followed by the Rahu-Ketu transit and the Jupiter transit, all of which are major transits, each one of which we can tap into, for the success of the project. And as I write this, today afternoon, I've dozed off multiple times, coz the early summer heat in Coimbatore post the Maha Shivratri, suddenly seemed cooler, and while I just conclude this write up, its raining. The affections of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, pouring down as rain, providing respite from the summer heat to all life forms and

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nature, a sign from the Divine Mother, that we are travelling in the right way only, though the world, might not agree with us, at this point of time in history, though they will agree with us after we tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, and realize that these Radio Signals heal all types of diseases, right from cancers to genetic disorders to rare diseases including pandemics.

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Thanks to President's Secretariat for forwarding to The Home Secretary, Govt. of India

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cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 11, 2025, 3:42 PM

subject: Fwd: Addendum to Suggestion to Govt. of India for "Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025"

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to: <secy-dot@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 12, 2025, 3:15 PM

subject: Fwd: Requesting transfer of equipment from BSNL/MTNL please in Continuation of Requesting emergency attention & Govt. of India approvals for the "Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/MaDurga for healing" please

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi for blessing with such an awesome proceeding on “Holi”. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai & Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to The President’s Secretariat for forwarding to The Telecom Secretary, Govt. of India (Mar 13, 2025, 3:28 PM)

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900151770804085138>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai & Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to The President’s Secretariat for forwarding to The Telecom Secretary, Govt. of India

Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy-dot@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 13, 2025, 3:28 PM

subject: Fwd: Cost effectiveness & Safety

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

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Editorial

Further Addendum to Suggestion to Govt. of India for “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900462641384182201>

Ref1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897982451924058317>

Ref2: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/money/topstories/if-poor-high-population-northern-states-tamil-nadu-minister-thiaga-rajan-amps-language-row/ar-AA1ATDaU?ocid=msedgdhp&pc=U531&cvid=d777ae6cb8d6454b9e43b33fa702bd82&ei=15>

Ref3: <https://x.com/nsitharaman/status/1900216593323311591>

Ref4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899477039205528018>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

Today’s writeup is only meant to help people to think and is not meant to cast any allegations against anyone in specific or in general.

From Ref2. Lets take up the phrase “high population northern states”. Can we examine what were the benefits to Tamil Nadu due to highly successful family planning of the past few decades. On one aspect, family expenditure reduced due to reduced family members. Meanwhile, it needs to be seen who profited out of the sale of contraceptives, over the counter drugs, abortions, late terminations of pregnancy etc.? Also include the mushrooming of IVF Centers across the state, coz lifestyle changes have happened in the past few decades due to small nuclear families, and people are more interested in their passion, career, etc. that many are unable to find time to expand the family and are consequently forced to choose assisted pregnancy and surrogate uteruses. Again who profits out of these too many in number IVF Centers? Now, did Tamil Nadu join India only in the past few decades or was Tamil Nadu a part of India on Independence day itself? So, Tamil Nadu knew that the procedure followed by the Govt. of India was sharing resources based on population. Do we need to believe that Tamil Nadu was so ignorant when they pursued an aggressive family planning campaign that one day, the state population will be so low that resources shared by the Govt. of India would also reduce? Now, please read again. Tamil Nadu benefitted out of an aggressive family planning policy, due to various business processes associated with the aggressive family planning

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Editorial

policy, and again Tamil Nadu benefits out of business processes associated with assisted enhancement in expansion of family through IVF centers. So, they benefitted when creating a problem of low population, and they are benefitting when a solution to the problem of low population is getting addressed. And instead of discussing this, where is the issue made to start? On a simple concern of changing the rupee notation. Well, if the rupee is denoted as per the Govt. of India or if the rupee is changed and denoted as per the Govt. of Tamil Nadu, is there going to be any appreciation or depreciation of the rupee against the Dollar or the Euro? So, an unrelated unsequential concern is created. People start talking about it, as if due to this change, the whole economy is going to improve and the stock exchange is going to overflow. Even the Finance Minister is forced to react, to contain the dialogue from going haywire. But where does it come, to Center-State revenue sharing pattern. And the VIP concerned with Ref 2 has been the State Finance Minister, an erudite scholar, with higher academic degrees from world renowned universities. Doesn't he know what's the solution to it? But instead of discussing a solution, he tries to discuss a problem? Now, please read Ref 1, followed by Ref 4. If the reader's mind offers a surmise that the issue regarding the rupee notation, and the discourse following it, leading to the concern of Govt. of India sharing revenues with northern states and Tamil Nadu, with probable effect of stoking up people's emotions, all seemed to be connected, and that its one religion having close ties with the political party ruling Tamil Nadu as causing this as retaliation for Ref 1 and Ref 4; then, I would want to draw attention of the reader to the opening statement of today's write up that "Today's writeup is only meant to help people to think and is not meant to cast any allegations against anyone in specific or in general." This is how the story has been going on since independence, and this is how the story will also go on, until the Suggestion to Govt. of India for "Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025" is brought into force (a) through Parliamentary processes or (b) through emergency ordinance, to enforce public peace and later followed up by Parliamentary processes.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Editorial

Have Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga already arrived as a Radio Signal even before we initiated the project to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga to heal the Universe!!!

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900593497469841654>

May please be read together with

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227>

and

Ref 2: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/money/topstories/strange-signals-detected-from-milky-way-s-heart-may-reveal-a-new-dark-matter-type/ar-AA1AQwWQ?ocid=msedgdhp&pc=U531&cvid=1bd123a68d7c444fb4ca0331396b2aeb&ei=33>

and

Ref 3: <https://awaken.com/2024/07/the-heart-has-its-own-brain-and-consciousness/>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

A slow reading of Ref 1, followed by Ref 2 and then again reading Ref 1 is suggested please.

Everything is self-explanatory.

Let us prepare to welcome Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga as the **New Dark Matter at the Heart of our Galaxy**. Isn't it appropriate that the Mother Goddess appears at the Heart to connect all hearts to heal, consequently causing the body to heal? Please read Ref 3.

For those who have difficulty in understanding, let me illustrate with an example. How many times have we thought of eating sweet and entering home, find that our biological mother is just about to complete making our favorite sweet in the kitchen, and the rich aroma of the sweet enchants its way through the home to the door which we are just entering?

If our biological mother can sense what we wish, and prepare and give it even before we ask, how much more would our Mother Goddess prepare and give even before we start to ask Her???

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi.

Editorial

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
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<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

A hypothetical understanding of how Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga may heal the Universe as a Radio Signal and a hypothetical assumption of how Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga may have healed His Holiness Pope Francis on invocation, without even the presence of an experimental setup.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900890510392521148>

May please be read together with

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895487248138973310>

And

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900593497469841654>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellency @NarendraModi Bhai, Your Excellency @AmitShah Bhai, Your Excellency @RajnathSingh Bhai, Your Excellency @NSitharaman Didi, Your Excellency Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Your Excellency @JM_Scindia Bhai, Your Excellency @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Your Excellency Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

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Editorial

A reading of Ref 1 and Ref 2 above together with

Ref 3: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/money/topstories/strange-signals-detected-from-milky-way-s-heart-may-reveal-a-new-dark-matter-type/ar-AA1AQwWQ?ocid=msedgdhp&pc=U531&cvid=1bd123a68d7c444fb4ca0331396b2aeb&ei=33>

Might provide understanding that a new dark matter is found at the heart of the Milky Way Galaxy. Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex At a time, when ur Swiss Guard was rehearsing ur funeral, we were here interceding with Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing you, and what followed has been truly magical as in Ref 1. Dark matter may have always been mysterious to western scientists coz of the narrative that God is light and evil is dark. Dark matter, when viewed through Indian Epistemology, identifies itself as the God particle, for it self-annihilates to provide a massive amount of energy that can even bind two drifting galaxies together. Hasn't love & sacrifice come in now? Lets have a brief look at

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227>

And return please.

Now, the reason why u are brought in, in such a narrative is perhaps that, as head of the Catholic Church, u can play ur part in helping to bring about fraternity, much lacking in the world right now. So my hypothesis is that, the one who was hunted by your Bishop for a very long time, the one whose mother's clan shed precious drops of blood over many generations, refusing to give up their ancient Indian religion, should also be the one who has to intercede for u. It happened, and She descended in Her pristine glory, sending in a small part of Herself as a new dark matter into the Heart of the Milky Way Galaxy, releasing massive amounts of energy (a matter of love and sacrifice), which energy passed by undetected or unidentified by most of the Radio Telescopes of the Developed western world, to reach u, unnoticed unidentified and undetected, to heal you, so that u will stand with us, in our initiative to heal the Universe through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga. If I've been discussing this topic with u in public, without any fear that the technology/concept can be stolen, then it means that I'm aware that nothing works until the chosen one, a child of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga causes the invocation to fulfil and then She rushes in. And the above discussion stands testimony to that understanding. The record that u were healed due to the grace of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga had to be created, and hence it happened in the way it happened. Else, there were countless chances, permutations and combinations that could have caused it to go haywire, but it went as planned by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. Also, u'd have noticed that when some writeups are written and sent, they are supported by events that happen after having writing and sending; which implies that these are but small parts of a huge Divine plan. Ok, I have to write to my brothers and sisters here in India, and I shall continue to them in the next paragraph please.

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@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

Your esteemed attention is drawn to the closing lines of the previous paragraph, that argues that it is quite evident that when some write ups are written and sent, they seem to be followed up by events that support those writeups, which indicate that this could be a small part of a huge Divine plan.

Lets have a brief look at Ref 4 and return please.

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227>

Understanding that it's a part of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga that has descended as dark matter, energy may be released according to an equation similar to $E = mC^2$, where C is not the Einsteinian constant for the speed of light, but is a quantum constant that indicates the speed of the cosmic particles of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. Now, imagine the amount of energy that is going to be radiated. May I request you to please re-read this entire file from beginning, with specific reference to the amount of energy that can be radiated by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, a small fraction of which, we are going to use to heal the Universe, the rest that can be tapped and applied to provide energy to the entire planet, from residential to industrial purposes, to transport, to space travel, etc. The very fact that Ref 3 has gone undetected & unidentified by a majority of the developed western world, is indicative of the fact, that the chance is now given to us – the Supremacy of the Universe, through love and sacrifice. Ofcourse, I can say, its upto u to decide to take it up, as the Govt. of India, but I wont say it, coz I'm already too tired with my extra lives as per kundli, and extra lives beyond traffic accidents and poisoning. How long can I carry on, just for the sake of completion of this and hand over to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga? Lets complete it, heal the Universe through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, and all of u, reap rich rewards from Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and I get some rest in the arms of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga as a Child.

To my understanding, the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga may hatch on to the consciousness of the heart, heal the heart first, and then through it, heal the entire body. Rephrased, Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga are gathering up to themselves, not only the human race, but all lifeforms, all of nature, the planet and all of the parallel universes and their higher and lower dimensions; so that the entire creation of Hers, is joined by Her love, and all stand together as Her Children. Lets coat the entire Universe with the Love & Affection of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. Humbled are we, that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga chose us, amongst so many crores and crores of alternate choices.

Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
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or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Editorial

Shall request my nominee to contact u for invocation to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for the project, in case I get killed

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900952537886540140>

Isnt this happening as evidence and previous investigations sufficient to bring in the “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025” ?

Once this act is passed, its believed that there will be good bonhomie between the BJP and the DMK, and there might be a coalition govt. in Tamil Nadu too, with a DMK Chief Minister and BJP Deputy Chief Minister in year 2026.

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1896930216918024615>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897534686039031851>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897554757658583394>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897982451924058317>

Ref 5: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1898061383922860204>

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900462641384182201>

Ref 7: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900919445016723676>

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I hope u now have hands on evidence and motivation to introduce “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025”

If u want to wait so that things are made to boil over further, so that u can have a discussion in Parliament, fine then, let it be so.

Personally, I myself know many who have been paid secret money to cause headaches to me, and they have suddenly been buying gold, constructing / repairing buildings, buying lands etc. If u want all of them to shed their masks, and draw their daggers out, so that u can catch them enmasse, fine, go ahead. I wont let u down. I'll stand with you. Coz this has been a headache for the Nation, even during the days of the British empire spilling over to the post Independence period of the Nation also. Religion cannot be a Deep State, running a

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Editorial

parallel Govt. of India, indulging in money laundering minimally to religious extremism maximally, and causing trouble to all those who don't fall in line with them.

I've done my duty, and the project is with you. In case, I get killed, u have my word that I shall beseech Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga that they may be pleased with the invocation from my nominee, who is currently a minor, and wears the sacred thread and knows to chant the mantras. Please go ahead with the project. Shall request my nominee to contact u for invocation to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for the project, in case I get killed.

I knew that they'd call a shut down, when they realise that its no use hunting me further. So, I ran quite fast, and ensured that I completed all that I had to do, and share all that I had to share with u.

Pls go ahead. May Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga stand with you.

Jai Hind.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Request to Pope Francis @Pontifex to restrain his bishops, priests, religious and laity; stop proxy wars and let people live in India in peace & a request to our

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Editorial

brothers @MKStalin, @Annamalai_k and beloved sister Dr Tamizhisai Soundarajan to sheathe their swords and tone down ideological differences please, for in the end, its only ur brother or sister against whom u stand, and is it worth it?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901610294436303321>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897534686039031851>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897554757658583394>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897982451924058317>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900462641384182201>

Ref 5: <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/annamalai-tamil-nadu-bjp-leaders-arrested-protest-against-rs-1000-crore-tasmac-corruption-9890477/>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

In humility the following submission please.

I had approached ur esteemed presence to restrain ur bishops from interfering in my life for the past 11 years directly and 25 years indirectly (just to take over a project related to divinity, of which they had no idea about, and which does NOT fit the Christian narrative, but gels perfectly with the Hindu religion – the basic premise is that, a blessing or grace, that transcended many generations on my mother’s clan will attach better with the Hindu religion, coz all of them were Hindus primarily, and my father instead of marrying my mother through the Special Marriage Act or Hindu Marriage Act, chose to marry her through the Christian marriage act, with some special permissions from the Bishops, which actually became similar to inviting the devil into the family)

Ofcourse, I have to appreciate ur Bishops for their in-depth knowledge of occultism, which sometimes leads to the question whether ur Bishops worship God or the Devil, for they have manytimes, found to have meted out aggressive inhuman treatment to those whom they wanted down or tamed.

There’s no point in discussing my clans suffering at the hands of ur Bishops, coz many of them have been killed too many years ago, and their families have already suffered a lot, and no remedy can compensate their suffering; my mothers suffering at the hands of ur Bishops, resisting their physical advances, coz she’s dead 25 years ago, and no remedy can be given to her. Again, there’s no point in discussing my suffering also at the hands of ur Bishops, coz no remedy can be given to me also; and I have to just leave it at the hands of God and move on. So, I’ve informed the Govt. of India that they may receive details of my nominee for invocation of

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Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing the Universe; after ur Bishop kills me directly or through proxy individuals or organizations or proxy political parties or proxy governments and also requested the guardian of my nominee to effect it after my death.

But I'm here for a different reason. I have highlighted as in references above, how money laundering at a minimal extent and religious extremism at a maximal extent cause havoc to society and the need for legislation to effect transparency in religious processes and places of worship through new laws.

But when I turn back and see, the aggression of ur Bishops seem to have been multiplied, operating through proxy, perhaps coz they are shocked at being exposed after many centuries of wrong doing but still being held to high esteem, coz none knew what they were actually doing in the dark.

What is the need to arrest so many through one division of law enforcement when another division of law enforcement is already looking into it?

Quote from Ref 5: "The protest was organised in the wake of a sweeping probe by the Directorate of Enforcement (ED), which has uncovered what it describes as a sprawling corruption network within TASMAL, implicating state officials, liquor distilleries, and bottling companies in an alleged Rs 1,000-crore financial fraud."

Are the Bishops worried that unearthing this aforesaid investigation by the Enforcement Directorate might lead to them, and they might lose face in front of you? Well, if they wanted to keep a clean face, they shouldn't have indulged in it at all. Maybe did they think that the money will go to them and the blame will go to the DMK, and while the DMK and the BJP battle it on the streets, ur Bishops can enjoy the ill-gotten money in the safe confines of their Bishop Residences?

My concern here is not the money laundering done by ur Bishops through proxy. My concern is my brothers and sisters battling out in the streets, a battle in which, they are neither the aggressor nor defender, but both are victims, both have been cheated and none realizes it. I have to illustrate a real-time example, and I also had a word with the concerned individual prior to writing this. My brother under influence of ur Bishop, sold away part of the family asset, and a pathetic individual, who had sweated out his entire life in the merciless weathers of dubai, working in their ports, bought it. The sale may not have been clear in the eyes of the law. If I had aggressively wanted it back, I could have caused legal trouble to the buyer through various suits in court. If the buyer, wanted to finish off the ever existential threat of me (who can contest the sale anytime), he could have also taken aggressive measures. Initially, the relationships went sour, but after a time, he also being quite old in age, and having seen the hardships in life, and also understanding the inhuman suffering meted out to me over many years in continuity, offered to bring food from his home, and since that day to this day (except for the days that his wife, who is also comparatively as old as him, is sick), brings food, so that I

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shouldn't die of starvation. If we wanted, we could have stood against each other to the finish. But reason prevailed, and I should say, that he is quite reasonable than my actual brother, coz he also stands as an elder brother. What ur Bishops didn't see, he saw, a human in me, and I wished him well.

So, I'm not here advising from the Book but I'm advising from life itself. If I can do it, then my brothers @MKStalin & @Annamalai_k can also find reason and tone down their ideological differences so that the people don't get affected. Its ok to have ideological differences and to stand by them, but also please consider the plight of the people who should not get affected when the ideological battle spills over to the streets.

And as head of the Church, I would request your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex to please advise ur Bishops, priests, religious and laity, to stop indulging in creating communal disharmony to suit their own financial ends.

Anyways, thanks to ur Bishops for providing so many realtime examples that provide better foundation for the proposed transparency in religious activities and places of worship act. Closing with request to my brothers @MKStalin & @Annamalai_k to tone down their ideological differences so that people don't get affected and it rains again in Coimbatore now (at 17:37 pm IST), as I conclude this write-up, blessings from Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, providing relief to all life forms and nature from the sweltering early summer heat.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

"Bill Gates Gives Up on Saving the Planet" -- At the limit of human strength, God comes in.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901693497008414901>

Ref: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/techandscience/bill-gates-gives-up-on-saving-the-planet-a-turning-point-for-environmentalism/ar-AA1B58Zr?ocid=msedgntp&pc=U531&cvid=5cc780514e7a4c46a0e3fed3cd74311d&ei=13>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai and Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai

In humility the following submission please.

Your esteemed attention is drawn to news item cited as reference above.

The title of article reads as **"Bill Gates Gives Up on Saving the Planet: A Turning Point for Environmentalism"**

I seek to submit in humility that we don't need to be alarmed that Bill Gates a global elite has given up on saving the planet, for, only at the limit of human strength, God comes in.

Please spare a minute to read

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900890510392521148>

with specific reference to the appearance of a new dark object at the heart of the Milky way Galaxy and the discussion thereunto.

I rest my case momentarily. Thank you.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

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Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai. Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai. Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai. Thanks to @MIB_India & Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to The President's Secretariat for forwarding to The Secretary Ministry of Information & Broadcasting Govt of India (Tue, Mar 18, 2025 at 10:07 AM)

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901901959462015367>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

In humility the following submission please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai. Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai. Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai. Thanks to @MIB_India & Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to The President's Secretariat for forwarding to The Secretary Ministry of Information & Broadcasting Govt of India (Tue, Mar 18, 2025 at 10:07 AM)

Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy.inb@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 18, 2025, 10:07 AM

subject: Fwd: Have Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga already arrived as a Radio Signal even before we initiated the project to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/MaDurga to heal the Universe!!!

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

Editorial

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The necessity for “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025” and the thriving pride in ambiguous sovereignty.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1902256949682434455>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897534686039031851>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897554757658583394>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1897982451924058317>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899477039205528018>

Ref 5: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900462641384182201>

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900952537886540140>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

In humility the following submission please.

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

We have been able to cover some ground that suggests a “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025” but today, we may seem to have hit upon the actual necessity for the aforesaid suggestion for the act.

Your esteemed attention is requested to the above references please.

Today we are able to understand a new reason that could be the basis for all wrong doing that might manifest as money laundering minimally and as religious extremism maximally. Today we are stumbling across a term “ambiguous sovereignty”, a coordinated result of carefully placed words in religious literature that actually challenges the authority of the Govt., in which case, neither the Govt. will be respected nor the law will be respected, and we have just a mayhem.

Im thankful to the local tailor who illustrated it to me. Met the local tailor in the neighbourhood while I was returning from my morning walk today. Shared a amusing titbit with him, that the villain that we were searching was the Bishop himself and we were looking everywhere else. He argued with profound sincerity, when Bishop is here in the Kingdom of Coimbatore, how can I go and approach the Kingdom of Rome? He was trying to tell me that I shouldn't have engaged with His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex. Now, wait a minute, I got lost. Waved him a smile and returned home. A mother cat was waiting for me at the door for serving food to it. Perhaps she was hungry after feeding the kittens. Asked her to wait for a minute, so that I can open the door, go inside and fetch her cat feed, as if she understood tamil or I understood cat language, but still she waited. I brought cat feed for her, and served her. Only then my bulbs lit up. The cause of the ambiguity is the carefully selected phrase in religious literature as “the Kingdom of God”. And coz of the marketing that their God was a loving God who forgave all sins, they have been able to attract towards themselves, people, who primarily sinned or violated the law, without even realizing the differentiation between sinning and breaking the law, coz their God was always there forgive everything. Ofcourse, God cant blamed, but only those people who neither learnt nor understood theology properly can be blamed, but it suited the organization to have this ambiguity, and this is where the Bishop becomes the king of the districts under him and the priest becomes king of the neighbourhood and together, we have a set of smart people, who love to sin (or break the law) and love to be forgiven. Either, the religions have to remove the ambiguous phrases as “kingdom of God”, and acting as kings and emperors or Princes of the Curia, or the people have to be taught that as long as they are alive and as long as they are citizens of a nation, its only the Nation that is the Kingdom, and no alternate Kingdom exists physically. Now, we have a lot of work to be attended to, and do u think that its possible to wean away an understanding that has been carefully planted in the minds of the people for many centuries? So, we are now zeroing on to the “Regularization of Sin & Transparency in Religious (i) processes & (ii) places of worship Act 2025” or, an easy alternative would be to label the Nation as a Hindu Rashtra, so that no other Rashtra

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Editorial

ambiguity arises. Ofcourse, the Govt can take a call on this matter regarding the way to be followed or find a better solution too, but its high time that the Govt. takes note of this concern and attends to it at the earliest, for religious dictums seem to have more weight than the actual weight of law, and its not safe for a Nation to have an alternate dictum than that of the dictum of law. I hope the @NIA_India will agree with me, coz we may sit in the comfort of our homes or offices, but its only the @NIA_India that bears the brunt of the heat, investigating terrorist activities, falling under religious extremism, committed by uneducated people, who don't even realize that only the law is paramount and a religious head does NOT hold any extra-constitutional authority above the law.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Are we staring at a prospective @MIB_India produced sequel to Ram Setu

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1902298571946549726>

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901901959462015367>

In humility the following communication please.

Are we staring at a prospective @MIB_India produced sequel to Ram Setu, where Jacqueline Fernandes & Hrithik Roshan will hurtle down to the heart of the Milky way Galaxy in a @SpaceX rocket to worship Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga in Her primitive raw cosmic form as dark matter/dark energy?

or will they set up a @Space_Station in the heart of the Milkyway Galaxy as a cosmic temple to Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga with @Astro_Suni as Chief of Space Station?

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBNL @Asli_Jacqueline & @iHrithik

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Editorial

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Editorial

Suggestion: Institutionalization of Corruption under GST Act & Reconciliation of Corruption Act, 2025

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1902626767124492412>

Ref 1:

<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/moneylaundering.asp#:~:text=Money%20laundering%20is%20essential%20for%20criminal>

Ref 2: <https://www.freepressjournal.in/india/tasmac-liquor-fraud-ed-exposes-massive-1000-crore-liquor-scam-in-tamil-nadu-dmk-minister-others-under-investigation>

In humility, the following submission please:

A Consequent understanding that we have arrived from previous discussions is that people love to sin, love to be forgiven, love to violate law, and love to be forgiven for that too, without even understanding or refusing to understand the clear differentiation between sin and law.

And in this entire confusion, they end up as mercenaries for money laundering. Now lets look at the concept of money laundering. Whether mules are used to transfer money or money has been transferred through various other illegal means, there remains a hidden cost in transfer, and also, some portion of it has to be left behind in foreign lands. Now, a question arises, why should that portion of that money be left behind in foreign lands? Why cant that money also come back to India? Ofcourse, we cant create a forgiving God and indoctrinate the people in competition, for it will take us more than a few centuries to wean them away from previous indoctrination and make them accept our indoctrination. So, an easy option might be to Institutionalize Corruption under the GST Act.

Why not levy 50% GST for Corruption? For example, if u need to bribe someone 10 lakhs, u can deposit 5 lakhs into the GST Account and give 5 Lakhs to whoever is demanding the bribe, along with receipt of 5 lakh deposit to GST Account, and the who is receiving the bribe, can also report the bribe in his/her income tax returns.

Let us consider Ref 2 for discussion. The point to be taken for consideration is not whether it's a 1000 crore scam or a 1 lakh crore scam. But how the money was routed. U can be sure that some portion of it was left behind in some foreign nation or enjoyed by some foreign agent/organization. Instead, why cant we levy 50% GST on the scam? Ofcourse, we cant

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encourage the scam and people should not think that we are making hay when the sun shines. So, let's consider two options. First option, those who do the scam can self-report it for 50% GST, pay the GST and clear their name off wrong doing. Second option, those who do the scam don't self-report but get caught by some investigating agency, in which case a penalty of an additional 500% kicks in accompanied with a service holiday period of 6 months.

Assuming it's the political party in power in Tamil Nadu, which does the scam and self-reports it to the Govt. of India, in which case, they can pay 50% GST fees and streamline things. But, if they haven't self-reported but get caught by any Governmental law enforcement agency, they have to pay 550% GST and take leave (not suspension) for 6 months (to pay the money), in which case, the Govt. of India can choose to run the Govt. of Tamil Nadu directly from Chennai (as in the British era, when the British Governors had summer and winter capitals) or send in a team of senior secretaries to assist the Tamil Nadu Governor during that 6 month period. Assuming that the party running the Govt. in Tamil Nadu, pays the 550% GST in 6 months, they can resume office after payment of the 550% GST, and this holiday period will be compensated to them at the end of their regular period of governance prior to the elections, with election code of conduct in force. In simple terms, the amount of time taken as holiday period to pay the 550% GST is returned back to the party in power, at the end of the regular period with one exception – with a valid election code of conduct in force. Of the 550% GST received, it will be fair and just for the Govt. of India to accept 100% GST and return the 450% GST received as incentives or awards, from the investigating agency that brought this scam to light, to the last informer in the queue. The long term effect of this is expected to be a counter corruption force that works against foreign agencies and their mercenaries who attempt to destabilise the Nation and its Economy. If foreign agencies can pay our people to do corruption, then from the same corruption money, we can pay our people to stand against corruption. We need to remember that, a knife is a knife, but when they use a knife to do bad, we use the same knife to do surgery to save lives. But, you know, foreign agencies, will be paying our people only a pittance, while we will be giving our people generously.

Now, assume that the Tasmac Scam to a maximum is 1 lakh crore. That means, they can take a holiday period of 6 months to pay back 550% GST, which is 5.5 lakh crore. In that 6 months holiday period, where will they go for money when they are not running the gov't.? They have to go back to whoever wrote the script and directed the show for this scam. Now its money. Do you think that the author of this scam and director of this scam will pay back 5.5 lakh crore in lieu of the 1 lakh crore that they collectively collected? No, they won't, and quarrels among them will start, which will slowly start eroding into the corruption network. In the holiday period, the Govt. of India will be running the Govt. of Tamil Nadu from Chennai either directly or indirectly through the Governor and a special team of senior secretaries of the Govt. of India. Also, this holiday period will provide a chance for the Govt. of India to effectively

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sideline the members/officials of the corrupt network and bring in clean officials in the same positions. Next, assuming they are able to pay back in 6 months, 5.5 lakh crore, they resume office as Govt. of Tamil Nadu. In case they aren't able to pay back, they can take an extended holiday period of another 6 months. Now, whatever holiday period is taken by them, is returned back to them. Assuming elections are due in May 2026 and they took a 6 month holiday period, then the 6 month holiday period is given back to them, with an additional clause as election code of conduct in force. Assuming that election code of conduct might be in force covering a period of 30 days prior to election day and extending to election results announcement date, for instance from April 2026 to May 2026 upto election results date. In this case, it will just get a 6 month addition, that is, election code of conduct will be in force from April 2026 to Nov 2026 upto election results announcement date. If they take a 1 year holiday period to repay 550% GST on scam, election code of conduct will be in force from April 2026 to May 2027 upto election results announcement date. This is hoped to restrain corruption on a large scale. If foreign forces, tamper with our laws to find loop holes and create a corruption network, then we should have the same merit to enhance our laws to seal the loop holes and create an anti corruption network. Now imagine, when 4.5 lakh crore as 450% is going to be returned as reward from the investigating agency, down to the last informer, do u think that they will attempt any scam again?

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Suggestion: Special Parliament Session to discuss declaration of Financial Emergency under Article 360.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1902777417154040105>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

In humility the following communication please.

Your Excellencies might be aware of the public discourse on social media and youtube regarding the Tasmac Scam in Tamil Nadu.

However, the reach may be very much limited. Public protests to raise awareness over the concern may be stifled by state law enforcement agencies, as they are bound to obey orders issued to them.

When the State Govt. itself could be under suspicion of having staged the scam, then the State law enforcement agencies cannot be blamed, as they have to obey the orders issued to them.

Under such circumstances, it may be prudent to change the battlefield to Delhi instead of Chennai, coz the Delhi law enforcement agencies report directly to the Union Home Ministry and not to the Delhi Home Ministry. Public discourse on the Tasmac Scam can be encouraged at Delhi.

Further, if we look at the period post independence till now, the Media has been dominated by the likes of the Stalwarts & Giants such as Prannoy Roy, Rajdeep Sardesai, etc. So, the entire public discourse on the Tasmac scam cannot be laid on the shoulders of a very few media personalities, pitting them against the mammoth Prannoy Roy, Rajdeep Sardesai etc., coz the Tasmac scam might possibly be the tip of the iceberg too, which can be commented upon only after the investigations are complete and chargesheets are filed.

Further, this is also the time, to identify new and budding talent and encourage it, in the interests of the Nation.

Perhaps, the Information & Broadcasting Ministry can screen some potential public discourses on social media and youtube, identify, potential or budding media personalities and provide them a chance to present their views as a guest in Parliament, that can be requested to be convened by a quorum of one tenth of the total members in Parliament, under Article 360, to debate if the Tasmac scam qualifies as a Financial Emergency. Why cant we have the common man speak out in Parliament against Corruption?

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Editorial

Further, a change of location of battlefield also has its own advantages. Let me illustrate from my own life experience, though mine might be quite lesser than yours. I was knocked out of my job, ensured that I don't get a job anywhere else. I suspected that battle lines would have been drawn to knock me out, if I do any start-up venture also. So, I was just trying to make headway in limited space and got an academic job in Hyderabad. Again, pressure was given to that Institution to request me to resign, and they had no other option than to succumb to pressure. Once I was brought back, money was paid to too many people to cause headaches to me. I was amazed to understand that they were pitting so many sparsely educated people against me. Only then, I realized that they were trying to shift the battleground to the streets, from the board rooms that I was acquainted with. I refused to fight on the street, and kept on moving forward, in the very limited space that was left available to me. Now, I may not have made it to the same board rooms that I was once acquainted with, but I am now permitted into very high carpeted corridors of power and I am humbled by the grace exhibited by some of the highest authorities of the Nation, in granting me a chance to share my views. And, I find that in this forum, those that hunted me, haven't been able to follow me or charge ahead of me. So, it was the change of battleground, that gave me back my dignity and my honor, though I might still live on alms only, coz its better to live on alms than do wrong to earn money, when we are completely blocked out and bundled into a corner with no space to breathe even.

Hence, in humility, I suggested that your Excellencies might also consider a change of battlefield location from the streets of Chennai, to the hallowed halls of the Parliament, where, u can have ur dignity and honor and serve the people in ways far better than at Chennai.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

And hence it is thus recorded that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga healed His Holiness Pope Francis & got him discharged from hospital in the year 2025 AD and as per Hindu Calendar year Chaitra Shukla Ashtami, Vikram samvat 2082, Saka samvat 1946.

sarvamaṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1903512115417428397>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895487248138973310>

May please be read together with

Ref 2: <https://x.com/ABC/status/1892984629906288822>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892043019961897181>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/AFpost/status/1892487608334180831>

Ref 5: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892462680104915225>

Ref 6: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/other/pope-francis-to-be-discharged-on-sunday-after-five-weeks-in-hospital/ar-AA1BslWC?ocid=msedgntp&pc=U531&cvid=0f30408b0be3400f89d4154e8f39e24c&ei=9>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,

@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility the following communication please.

And hence it is thus recorded that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga healed His Holiness Pope Francis, coz the second condition outlined in Ref 5, as discharge from hospital, is announced via Ref 6, and hence both conditions outlined in Ref 5, namely, news of your recovery and discharge are fulfilled now. We recorded as in Ref 1 above when news of ur recovery was flashed by the Media. Now when Media reports that u are going to be discharged tomorrow, we again record that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga healed Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex.

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Editorial

Consequently, it shall be the pleasure of @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia & @MIB_India to say thanks to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, with some special pujas and prasad for the devotees.

Since i may not have cash to undertake a pilgrimage now, i may kindly be excused from attendance please. @FinMinIndia will know how much meagre balance i have in my savings account.

But if it pleases the @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia to sponsor my travel allowance, food and stay, i shall be humbled to visit in person and thank Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, in any chosen temple.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Suggestion: Proposing the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for universal de-addiction, including de-addiction from alcohol and substance abuse.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1903748759210586499>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & @MIB_India

In humility the following submission please.

The Social Media Narrative on Youtube, seems to yield a significant understanding, that a large percentage of the population is addicted to alcohol. So, even if the current Tasmac Scam is investigated, and various proceedings in accordance with law is staged, and even if the guilty are punished, still, the potential value of scam in Tasmac still remains, and that will be a point of attraction to any political party in power in Tamil Nadu.

Further, a complete shutdown of Tasmac or 100% prohibition in the state of Tamil Nadu also is not possible, for those addicted to alcohol might turn to spurious liquor, which could be fatal too, resulting in a huge number of deaths.

Also, its not practically possible to arrange counselling through de-addiction centers for such a large population that is dependent on alcohol.

Consequently, why not we tweak the consciousness of the alcohol addicts by exposing them to the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga?

Once the addiction weans off, they wont be dependent on alcohol so much, and Tasmac may also see declining sales. Declining sales might bring Tasmac to a point of diminishing return, where it is not financially feasible to continue to run Tasmac and Tasmac may die a natural death.

To prevent a small population that does not want to de-addict itself, from turning to spurious liquor, a countable few number of alcohol outlets can be opened. The inconvenience of travelling far, in comparison to the neighbourhood Tasmac outlet, may also cause a few more to withdraw from alcohol.

So, as a short term solution, the Tasmac scam can be investigated and the corrupt booked under relevant sections of law. As a long term solution, the consciousness of the people can be tweaked by applying the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, which will help to rein in not only alcohol addiction, but also substance/drug addiction.

Editorial

This service can also be provided as a de-addiction service to other Nations on demand too, as a commercial service.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Proclamation: Behold “Resurrection thro’ Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696>

Sarvesām Svastir Bhavatu

Sarvesām Shāntir Bhavatu

Sarvesām Pūrnām Bhavatu

Sarvesām Maṅgalam Bhavatu

<https://youtu.be/DISUAciNRak>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility the following submission please.

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1903512115417428397>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/AFpost/status/1892487608334180831>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900593497469841654>

I hereby present to you, the first independent sample of resurrection through Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga -- His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex himself.

I hereby declare that we had no physical access to His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex & consequently, no question can be raised whether we gave him any secret medicine. Further, Pope Francis is not an Indian celebrity. Consequently, the question of self-bias is also ruled out. We are not marketing an Indian celebrity. Also we gain no advantage nor assets nor gold nor cash in lieu for resurrecting Pope Francis.

Further, the very fact that the Swiss Guard was rehearsing Pope Francis @Pontifex funeral (Ref 2) indicates that his clinical condition offered no hope of clinical recovery, and Pope Francis being one of the most influential persons in the whole world, it would be no mistake that the Swiss Guard was rehearsing Pope Francis @Pontifex funeral. Either, Pope Francis @Pontifex should have been gravely sick or already dead (neither of which can be confirmed independently) due to the highly secretive nature of the Vatican.

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Editorial

Your esteemed attention is drawn to Ref 3 along with the fact that many of my ancestors from my mother's clan were killed, and no male survivors existed, except those who sold their soul to the devil and became a traitor.

I am not trying to tarnish the reputation of Christianity, coz its also the religion of one of my parents, *viz*, my father, but lets analyse. We have a religion that is supported by the vast colonial expanse of the Europeans, trying to market a man they killed, who was supposed to have resurrected from the dead on the third day, vis a vis, a clan here in India, that could resurrect any human from the dead. Isnt such a clan, a threat to the expansion of Christianity in India? All these could have been dismissed as lame stories, but when the entire file is read, along with the date and time of each communication, it can be understood that a survivor from the very clan that they destroyed had to intercede for their religious head's life to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and then Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga resurrect their religious leader. Now, Ref 3 will give more meaning. India shall have the supremacy of the Universe, through love and sacrifice. Now, a simple question. If its possible to resurrect Pope Francis @Pontifex, then wont it be possible to heal the entire Universe through Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga?

Im here, in the name of my mother's clan (clan name unknown, though it will be easy to find out through occult methods, coz when subject to severe harassment and threat to life, people try to escape harassment and life threat by changing identities, atleast to protect the women and the children and not all will stand like me, to be poisoned 11 times and still here serving Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga), to help heal the entire Universe through the grace of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

I can serve only through the Govt. of India, coz only in that way, the rewards of this service will go to the entire nation, and through the Nation of India, will go to the whole world, coz I will have to connect to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga through my biological mother Bagavathy and the souls of her clan, and i'm not sure if it will work in any other way. Moreover, if it could have worked in any other way, I wouldn't be here writing this, and u wouldn't be here reading this.

We bear no ill-will or hatred towards those who killed us over many centuries, for it was just love and sacrifice for the sake of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Was the ancient Egyptian Civilization also offered the same knowledge to heal the Universe, as India is offered a chance now & did they waste it away? The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn't comprehend at all.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904415272091709891>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227>

Ref 2: <https://youtu.be/pzGbYPaLtJ4>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696>

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In humility the following communication please.

A recent video on youtube dated 1 day ago as in Ref 2, gives some mind boggling information of vast structures towering more than 2 Eiffel Towers, beneath the pyramids, which could have been possibly energy generating or energy handling machinery. Since they are talking on current date, they are referring to the structures as subterranean structures. But, to my humble understanding, they should have been superstructures constructed above the ground surface level as on date of construction, now lying beneath sandy graves of civilizations. Coz, the royals of Egypt were almost worshipped as demi Gods. So, its natural that they will choose even their grave as higher than any other grave used to bury a normal human being. So, if we consider that the subterranean structure, was actually a superstructure built above the ground, then the pyramid will be sitting on a structure that's taller than 2 Eiffel towers, a grave befitting a king. Hence the Pharaohs could have been buried in the pyramids, then taller than the ground level by 2 Eiffel towers, and there would have been no grave higher than that of the Pharaoh's. The vanity of mankind then, which we now witness as sandy graves of civilizations.

Your esteemed attention is requested to Ref 1. Communicated to your esteemed selves on March 11, 2025, almost 14 days ago, that means, Ref 1 predates Ref 2 by almost 13 days. So, there's no possibility that Ref 1 could have been written after seeing Ref 2. As soon as I was briefing through Ref 2, it struck me that it was related to Ref 1.

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Editorial

With additional concentration requested by Ref 3, it now remains the choice of the Govt. of India to choose to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga, Resurrect/Heal the Universe, and leave behind a legacy that still keeps on working, even after thousands of years, talking of our attempt in Faith on Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, or we can also indulge in vanity like the Pharaohs of yesteryears, and build graves for ourselves, taller than the highest buildings in the World, only to be found later as subterranean structures by any archaeological expedition of the same or a different evolved smart species, after the collapse of our civilization due to climate change and other man made damages to the planet.

The Saturn transit is in and almost 120 hours away only. Let us create a very good karma for ourselves, in standing with Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga and resurrect/heal the Universe and all human and alien Civilizations and machinery ecosystems, so that our Civilization also does not meet its icy or watery or sandy graves.

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Editorial

Isnt it time to evolve the Disaster Management Act 2005 & Disaster Management Amendment Act 2024 into Nature Celebration Act 2025?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904599311071273053>

Ref: <https://x.com/AmitShah/status/1904578270676365387>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
@AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility the following communication please.

It pains to behold the Union Home Minister Shri @AmitShah Bhai, concentrating on
Transparency, Responsibility, Efficiency and Synergy, aiming for a [DisasterResilientBharat](#)

How long are we going to suffer, and prepare ourselves for suffering and resilience?

When are we going to celebrate, and prepare ourselves for celebration?

It only needs political will by the Govt. of India to initiate activities on the Search and
Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing the Universe. If Ma
Bagavathy and Ma Durga bless us abundantly, we may even complete a substantial portion of
the project before this Govt. lays down office at the end of this term. If Ma Bagavathy and Ma
Durga want us to persevere more, the project may extend beyond the end of term of this Govt.
Ofcourse, the Govt. will know how to make provision for the project to continue, even if it
extends beyond the end of this term of the Govt. It only needs a political will. Ofcourse, when
the global status quo may possibly change due to healing the Universe, as huge mammoth
receipts that pour in as revenues for the Govt. of India, there may be some negotiations that
may need to be done with foreign nations, which may just be child's play for our beloved
External Affairs Minister @DrSJaishankar Bhai.

So, we may be progressing from Disaster Resilient Bharat to Disaster earning Bharat, coz our
services may be required by various nations in tackling disasters, through the Radio Signal of
Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

Consequently, we may evolve into a Bharat that celebrates Nature, for every aspect of Nature
will either be a source of celebration for us, or a source of revenue for us.

Hence, wouldn't it be appropriate for us to draft the Nature Celebration Act 2025 instead of
dwelling painfully on the Disaster Management Amendment Act 2024?

And it shall be the discretion of the Home Minister please.

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Editorial

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Editorial

The reason for suggesting the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe as a Govt. of India project and neither as a Public-Private Partnership Model nor as a Private Initiative under the patronship of any of our beloved corporate friends.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904844412112560614>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility the following communication please.

It dawned on me now, as regards why the project proposal of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe has to be a Govt. of India project and neither a Public-Private partnership model nor as a Private Initiative under the patronship of any of our beloved corporate friends backed by the BJP. Hence sharing with your Excellencies please.

The PPP model has been a huge success in transforming the National Highway infrastructure in India and could be applied here too.

Further, there are a few corporate friends of ours who'd give their life for such a project and I am sure that within 72 hours, we might have had the project rolling with support from the BJP.

The reasons why I insist that it has to be a Govt of India project is,

- A connection to Ancient Energies, that provide intuitive abilities, and the respect reciprocally shown by the Universe, when that strange invocation to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga was made for the life & health of His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex especially when His personal bodyguards, *viz.*, were doing a rehearsal for his funeral (<https://x.com/AFpost/status/1892487608334180831>), implying that they have received credible internal information that Pope Francis may not survive, and they did their duty in rehearsing for his funeral, coz it will be a global event with many Heads of State and Diplomatic retinues participating, and they had to be sure of each dot and comma in the proceedings. The Vatican has its own share of connections to Ancient Energies, but this was just a divine drama, where Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga just displayed their glory and splendour, amidst all other Ancient Energies.
- In such a case, there is an ancient Adage in Tamil that says, Shakti and Shiva have to be present together. Shakti should not be present without Shiva, and Shiva should not be present without Shakti. Also, in Tamil, the Govt. is as representative as Shiva. So, when

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Editorial

the project of Tapping and Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga is done, it actually means that we are tapping and applying the Radio Signal of the Shakti herself, in which case, when it is done as a Govt. of India project, Shiva is present and Shakti is also present, and together, they reclaim the entire Universe as their own and heal the Universe coz its their own. This is a divine drama of which we have been offered a part. Though we can assume that such an incident arises, at the end of every Civilization, so far found to have been a wasted opportunity by many Civilizations, as evidenced by their icy/watery/sandy graves, still, we do not have concrete proof of it. But what is sure, is that it is a divine drama. I am not trying to ruffle feathers with my Christian brothers and sisters, but just imagine, Pope Francis @Pontifex as having been proclaimed as Resurrected, in earlier sections? A Divine comedy, I should say. Coz the only human as having been self-proclaimed by Christianity is Jesus Christ himself. Now, the way the events unfolded, Pope Francis @Pontifex also has been proclaimed as resurrected. Will they be able to rechristen Pope Francis @Pontifex as Jesus Christ II ? In which case, 2000 years of indoctrination has to be modified and it wont suit the earlier narrative, that Jesus Christ died for the sins of the world. So, I should say, that the entire Christendom would have been caught on the back foot, and they cant even react to it, coz it was the historical blunder of the Swiss Guard Funeral Rehearsal for Pope Francis that gave the allowance for everything, which cant be undone. So, they have to pretend that they have not noticed anything, and we also accept that they have not noticed anything, and life continues as amicably as ever as friends, brothers and sisters. And I should say Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga are just enjoying scripting out the divine drama.

- Under such circumstances, the project can be only a Govt. of India project, though it may have a lot of difficulties in pursuit of it. Further, in future, when other Nations require our service in healing life or nature or the machinery ecosystem in their Nation, it will be convenient for them to request the Govt. of India for help, than attempting to arm-twist an Indian corporate to serve them, if the project is done as a PPP project or as a private initiative under a friendly Indian Corporate body. All those who hunted me were also painfully unaware of the fact that I can be arm-twisted to hand over the project, but there's no guarantee that Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga will cooperate. So, there's no point in arm twisting anyone, but just let it flow as per the divine plan of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. Ofcourse, if the political party in power in Delhi, running the Govt. of India changes, there could be less patronage for this project, but lets cross the Bridge when the Bridge comes. Why worry about it now? What if this project is a divine drama by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga to help continue the Govt. of India at Delhi, with the same political party for quite a long time, through this project?

Editorial

- Though there could be bureaucratic delays in scrutiny and approval of the proposal, still its best to proceed with it as a Govt. of India project. Further, the resurrection/healing of Pope Francis @Pontifex, is a very special event, that will vouch for the fact that this project should be done only as a Govt. of India project.
- This was also the reason why the proposal which was initially submitted to the Holy See, coz the Vatican is the smallest city-State in the World, and they are also a National Govt., with reference to the Holy See, though they may not be a Govt. but only a Religious Society in other parts of the world; started hitting its roadblocks, and had to be withdrawn. Ofcourse, the proposal got stuck, and due to various reasons as communicated to His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, the proposal was withdrawn from the Holy See, suitable modifications were done and presented to the Govt. of India; and both the Holy See and the Govt of India are aware of everything, coz it was done transparently; coz at the end of the day, all the peoples and all the religions of the world, will be working with us in the Search and Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga in healing the Universe, and we have to maintain fraternal relations with all peoples and all religions of the world.

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Revisiting -- The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn't comprehend at all.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904957860615991470>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227> (dated March 11, 2025)

with specific reference to

Ref 2: <https://youtu.be/M62u8UOeQpo> (dated March 26, 2025)

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904844412112560614> (dated March 26, 2025)

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility, the following communication please.

I was about to call it a day and retire to sleep, when I stumbled across Ref 2 in the youtube recommendations that shows up when youtube app is opened on Windows 11. Though it was quite early into the night, still, I was too tired and sleepy, for the reason that a 2 month old kitten that was fatally knocked down by a bike when it was attempting to cross the street day before yesterday, which held on to dear life unconscious for about 24 hours passed away yesterday evening, and today morning, gave it a dignified funeral. Incidentally, everytime, a kitten passes away, and I give it a dignified funeral, I do feel a lot of body pain and tiredness, and its been more than 75 kitten funerals that I've done in the past 11 years. Everytime, there'd be an overwhelming pain in the body and tiredness. Today was no exception. I hadn't switched on the laptop in the evening, so half asleep, I opened up my email inbox, found that no emails that required attention now, and before shutting down, opened youtube to hear a random song. Was scrolling through the recommendations, when I stumbled across Ref 2, and curiosity killed me. After having a scorching cup of black tea to wake up my sleepy head, also with some added sugar, I'm here writing to your Excellencies, coz its better to finish it off now, than wait for the sunrise, and spend a restless night trying to sleep. So, here I am. If there any typos or spelling mistakes, kindly forgive me. I'm not in a condition, fit to type. But, I'm aware

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Editorial

that its also an altered state of consciousness, so with surrender to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, I start this communication please.

Ref 1 is dated March 11 while Ref 2 and Ref 3 is dated today. I seek to draw your esteemed attention to the title and content in Ref 2, that talks of Earth being restarted several times. Now please revert to relevant sections in Ref 1 and further explanation in Ref 3, regarding civilizations being offered a chance to save the Universe, and they unable to comprehend it, went to their icy or watery or sandy graves, inclusive of the amusing 2 Eiffel tower tall graves that the Pharaohs built for themselves, as the pyramids, which are now resting on ground level and a major portion of the superstructure, sunk into the sand as subterranean structures; and that its our turn now, to attempt to heal and save the Universe, with the planet inclusive; and that we may surrender to the divine plan of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, tap them as Radio Signals and heal the entirety instead of choosing to build graves for ourselves on top of skyscrapers, which may later be found in the ice or under water or under sand, by the same or any other evolved species via expeditions. While Ref 1 was drafted and communicated on March 11, I never knew that Ref 2 will come up today through an independent source.

If ur Excellencies, would spare a minute to leaf through the entire file, via link given below as Consolidated File Access, u'd be aware that there have been corroborations to my communications that spring up from independent sources at a later date. Hence Ref 2 is also one such corroboration to my earlier communication as Ref 1 and its only 70 hours almost to Saturn Transit on March 29, 10:07 pm IST.

Incidentally, Saturn transits from my 3rd house (w.r.t. my Rashi) to my 4th house. The 4th house, is the house of the Mother. Incidentally, mummy's name is Bagavathy and I never differentiated between my biological mother Bagavathy and Ma Bagavathy. So, if Saturn goes into the house of the Mother, I can also read it as Saturn goes into the house of Ma Bagavathy. Saturn, the enforcer of Justice within the confines of the home of Ma Bagavathy, will help us to serve better in surrender to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

So, lets celebrate with a song from Shakira (The official 2010 FIFA World cup song), <https://youtu.be/pRpeEdMmmQQ> with lyrics modified as *this time for India* and emphasis on an original line *Listen to ur God, this is our motto*. The song seems to have been sung for us, while we take up a very ambitious project of healing the Universe, based on the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Was Jesus Christ sent by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga with a message of love & sacrifice? Revisiting -- The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn't comprehend at all.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905181629200609298>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904957860615991470>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904844412112560614>

Ref 4: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Ref 5: <https://oilprice.com/Energy/General/The-Complete-History-Of-Fossil-Fuels.html>

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901693497008414901>

Ref 7: <https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/factcheck/2020/06/11/fact-check-bill-gates-has-given-over-50-billion-charitable-causes/3169864001/>

Ref 8: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-04558-7#:~:text=According%20to%20theoretical%20physicist%20Carlo%20Rovelli%2C%20time%20is,Isaac%20Newton%E2%80%99s%20picture%20of%20a%20universally%20ticking%20Oclock>

Ref 9: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696>

Ref 10: <https://phys.org/news/2025-03-experimental-nonlocal-energy-quantum-memories.html>

Ref 11: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900593497469841654>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Officials at @MIB_India

In humility, the following communication please.

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Editorial

It was good that I completed Ref 1 and communicated to your esteemed selves yesterday night itself. Mind was clear since morning, and thought of taking a break today, until a new enlightenment dawned. Well, here I am again please.

In humility, let me share it with you please.

The Industrial Revolution happened during 1760 to 1830. The first modern commercial oil well [was drilled by Edwin L. Drake in Titusville, Pennsylvania](#), in 1859 (Ref 5) And, from there, there was no looking back. Mankind in its greed, brought the planet to its current state of despair, that even Global Elites like Mr Bill Gates gives up on saving the planet. Its an irony that Mr Bill Gates who's funded almost \$ 50 billion in philanthropy to help make the world a better place gives up on saving the planet. Perhaps, it was never meant to be a human effort but primarily a divine effort.

Our sense of time arises only from the Earths rotation about its axis in 24 hours and its revolution around the sun in 365.256 days and time is just an illusion, created by ourselves with reference to our short span of life on this planet. There can also be Science without time (Ref 8) The flow of time may just be a subjective feature of the Universe and not an objective feature, implying that the flow of time, is based on the observer only and does not quantify nor qualify any feature of the Universe, implying that an event that is happening now, could have already happened earlier. If we take the time out of these two events, then they can be classified as events that are happening in two different places (multiple places), which qualifies a quantum event.

Since Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga are the primary quantum energy sources, then, what's happening now, should have also happened at some other place in a different time span. We are attempting to heal the planet using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, primarily for the reason that the damage is heavy, and it needs a heavier energy source to heal, based on the values of love and sacrifice. The values of love and sacrifice (Ref 11) arise from the phenomenon of self-annihilation of dark matter to produce the purest form of energy, viz dark energy. Further, Ref 4, perceives this as a divine drama by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. Consequently, if this proposal of ours to heal the entirety using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga is a quantum event, then there should have been another event, in a different time, in a different location, again talking of love and sacrifice and healing.

Let us look for clues in the events unfolding, since the start of this proposal to the Govt. of India on Jan 26, 2025 (Ref 4). We have one very strange event, as discussed in Ref 9, the claim that His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex has been resurrected by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga and the defense provided for arriving at that conclusion. The claim can be accepted, rejected or argued, but the events discussed in the claim cannot be undone in history. The events remain, irrespective of whether the claim is accepted or rejected. Now, we have one unusual situation,

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Editorial

and that is, Christianity should be engaging with a different set of ancient energies and Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga are a very unique set of primordial energies, that they are the Shakti. Only when the ancient energies of Christianity and the energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga have a quantum correlation, only then, a consciousness based request to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga to heal His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex can work based on quantum correlation. Else, the energies from Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga could not have healed Pope Francis @Pontifex due to quantum incorrelation. So what are we stumbling upon?

The only conclusion possible is that the ancient energies that Christianity derives from, is quantum correlated with Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, which implies that Jesus Christ, who taught love and sacrifice and sharing also should have been a part of the same quantum correlated energy source of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. Stated in simple terms, Jesus Christ should have been sent by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, to teach the world love and sacrifice and sharing, as a preparatory event for the actual descent of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga as Radio Signal to heal all of mankind, nature, all life forms, aliens and machine ecosystems and the Universe.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding to The Home Secretary, @HMOIndia Govt. of India (27.03.2025, 3:40 PM) & Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India & Thanks to the Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905225917779333127>

@NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia and @MIB_India and The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility, the following communication please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding to The Home Secretary, @HMOIndia Govt. of India (27.03.2025, 3:40 PM) & Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India & Thanks to the Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia

Narration of forward is as follows please.

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <hshso@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Mar 27, 2025, 3:40 PM

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Editorial

subject: Fwd: Isnt it time to evolve the Disaster Management Act 2005 & Disaster Management Amendment Act 2024 into Nature Celebration Act 2025?

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904599311071273053>

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Editorial

Behold: The media report that supports that Pope Francis @Pontifex was resurrected by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905319700806205786>

Ref 1: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/health/medical/pope-francis-doctor-says-medical-team-considered-letting-him-die-pope-francis-health-n18g/vi-AA1BDGLT?ocid=msedgdhp&pc=U531&cvid=7f8858ce5a624b689396dfbfde7b37cd&ei=15>

May please be read together with Ref 2:

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility, the following communication please.

The truth is out for all of us to behold. When the media report says that Pope Francis @Pontifex Medical Team debated to stop medical treatment, it means withdrawal of clinical support. Rephrased, it means that they were getting ready to bury him. And the unthinkable happened. Media reports that only Pope Francis's nurse @Pontifex wanted to continue treatment inspite of heavy risks involved, which means that, when everyone else wanted to bury him, there was one human consciousness which wanted to continue treatment; and its that human consciousness that should have been influenced by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

Lets reason out. If the Medical Team had stopped treatment, they might have embalmed his body to be able to withstand the many days of mourning prior to the funeral. Once embalmed, it becomes very difficult to bring life back to him. So, he had to receive continuous medical treatment so that embalming of his body is not done.

Consequently, in the time that medical treatment or medical support was given, the quantum energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga would have resurrected Pope Francis @Pontifex. The reasoning behind the resurrection is that when a Medical Team debates on withdrawal of Medical treatment to a patient, it means that the patient is almost dying; Maybe based on feeble biophysical parameters, which may have near zero probability of improving, the patient may have been alive, but to all other conventional terminology, the patient is dead.

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Editorial

Consequently, claimed that Pope Francis @Pontifex has been resurrected by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

Its immaterial whether this claim is accepted or rejected or disputed. But the events have unfolded as such. And there is no point whether the above claim of resurrection is accepted or rejected or disputed; for the default status stands as resurrected from the dead.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Ma Bagavathy Economy Model & The Pope's resurrection – the 1st among crores of miracles to be scientifically documented to the name of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905627603769458959>

Ref 1: <https://thecatholicherald.com/popes-doctor-calls-recovery-miraculous-highlights-franciss-determination-to-fight/>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892043019961897181> (8:16 AM · Feb 19, 2025)

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892462680104915225> (12:03 PM · Feb 20, 2025)

Ref 4: <https://x.com/ABC/status/1892984629906288822> (10:38 PM · Feb 21, 2025)

Ref 5: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1895487248138973310> (8:22 PM · Feb 28, 2025)

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696> (9:47 AM · Mar 24, 2025)

Ref 7: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900890510392521148> (6:13 PM · Mar 15, 2025)

Ref 8: <https://www.firstpost.com/explainers/pope-francis-personal-nurse-massimiliano-strappetti-saved-life-13874740.html>

Ref 9: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905181629200609298> (2:24 PM · Mar 27, 2025)

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility, the following communication please.

The Pope's doctor Doctor Sergio Alfieri, is reported to have stated that Feb 28, was the worst night that was also a nightmare in the period of Pope Francis @Pontifex recent hospitalization. Incidentally, Feb 28, was also the same day (Ref 5) when we declared at 8:22 pm IST that Pope Francis @Pontifex was healed by Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga based on invocation to Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga done on Feb 19 (Ref 2).

Since IST is ahead of Rome time by 4:30 hours, night at Rome would have followed night in India, which implies that Pope Francis @Pontifex might have gone into health crisis after the declaration at 8:22 pm IST that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga have healed Pope Francis @Pontifex.

Editorial

The unflinching Faith that we have on Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga would have caused Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga to stand for our honor as much as we stand for the honor of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga; coz if the Pope died on Feb 28, it would have caused a serious question of doubt on the proposal to Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing all of mankind, all life forms, nature, the environment, the planet and the Universe. Consequently, the Pope shouldn't die. Even if he neared death, or died, still he had to be revived; coz the proposal to heal the Universe using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga cannot die a premature death. It had to start, fulfil, and give benefit to all Civilizations, all known worlds, all unknown worlds, all free worlds, all enslaved worlds, all celestial worlds, etc.

In fixing Pope Francis @Pontifex in this massive venture, there is expected two benefits. First benefit is that, Pope Francis, one of the most influential personalities of this world, will start to bear gratitude to the aforesaid effort of healing the universe. Second expected benefit is that the Abrahamic Religions will realize that the ancient energies that they are linking to are quantum correlated with the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga (Ref 9), in which case, all religions will realize themselves as a subset of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga & mankind will start to stand as one, irrespective of differences in the religion that they subscribe to. This unity will help the entire world to work together, absorb the benefits that Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga bestow upon us; also further the new industry and new business processes that arise based on healing and machine optimization offered by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, inclusive of quantum travel to various worlds and various dimensions, which will evolve as the Ma Bagavathy economy model under the esteemed stewardship of our beloved sister @NSitharaman Didi @FinMinIndia.

So many trillions of dollars or euros may come in as revenues. Since, I have to concentrate on enabling various aspects that arise due to the healing and optimization brought about by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and since I'm also growing old, I will have to concentrate more on technical aspects that will help to run all processes as scientific processes, that do not require my consciousness connections to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, before I return to my ancestors to complete the work assigned to us in farther worlds and dimensions.

Its a huge journey ahead, and at every stage, we will have to make new laws as required, modify old laws, create new structures and processes, so that the Nation receives full benefit from the proposal to heal the Universe using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

I seek no percentage nor share of the revenues. I shall be humbled to receive a dignified Scientific position in the Nation or a dignified constitutional position.

It shall be the discretion of @PMOIndia and @HMOIndia to give me a good offer please.

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Editorial

If money was a desire and not a necessity for a dignified life, I could have sold myself to those who were hunting me down for many decades and lived a comfortable luxurious life all these decades.

I didn't have to suffer so long and still persevere to do good for the Nation.

I had to uphold the honor and dignity of my mothers clan and I stood for it. Instead of tweaking the narrative in favor of any other vested group or society or organization, I have given the true narrative to the Govt. of India.

I'm giving my best for the Nation, and its sufficient if the Nation gives me its best, in the form of a dignified respected life until I go back to my ancestors.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Vasudhaiva Kudumbakam, Amnesty for Religious Extremists & Terrorists, Bharatiya Monetary Fund, Nuclear fuelled bio-implantable satellite tracked UIDAI Aadhaar, Bharatiya United Free Nations Charter, Conference of World Religions

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1906295176085361105>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905627603769458959>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905181629200609298>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility, the following communication please.

An unexpected pleasant surprising understanding while drafting the proposal to “Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga in healing the Universe” is that the Abrahamic Religions may be worshipping Ancient Energies that could be quantum correlated with the Ancient Energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. When the Ancient Energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga could be quantum correlated with the Ancient Energies worshipped by the Abrahamic Religions, then, the Ancient Energies of fraternal religions such as Buddhism and Jainism may also be quantum correlated with the Ancient Energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, consequently leading to the premise that all religions are related to each other fraternally through Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

Consequently, it will be the pleasure of @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia to seek to organize the Second Conference of World Religions in India. Of course, Swami Vivekananda may not be with us physically now, but its possible for @NarendraModi Bhai and @AmitShah Bhai to proxy for Swami Vivekananda by connecting to the consciousness fields of Swami Vivekananda through the consciousness of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

Hopefully by that time, we should have been successful in tapping the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. With the cooperation of religious leaders of all world religions, we can attempt to study the quantum correlation characteristics and coherence among various ancient energies with reference to the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

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Editorial

Once we can establish scientifically that Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga are the primary ancient energies to which the ancient energies of all religions correlate, then it will lead to Vasudaiva Kudumbagam, and it will be our responsibility as elders in Global Family, to help bring everything to form with reference to Vasudaiva Kudumbagam.

Once the project starts running, and revenues start pouring in, we have to be prudent in utilising the revenues for the good of our Nation, with more concentration to saving the funds, and create a global monetary fund, as the Bharatiya Monetary Fund, which will help overcome the constraints in the IMF.

In the same time, we can initiate research into implantable bio-compatible nuclear fuelled satellite tracked UIDAI Aadhaar which can become the new global passport. All Nations may be pleased to issue Visa on arrival for Indian Citizens. If any monetary compensation or investment into that Nation is required of Indian Citizens for reasons of Visa, it may be effected from the Bharatiya Monetary Fund please.

In short, we will be instrumental in creating the Charter of Free Nations.

Consequently, India can negotiate with all Nations in the World for a Bharatiya United Free Nations Charter, which can be established above the UN Charter or as part of the UN Charter. The fine negotiating skills of our beloved @DrSJaishankar Bhai will be a blessing in such an attempt.

Further, India can offer Amnesty for all religious extremists and all types of terrorists, and help to integrate them into society, by giving education to them and their families, offering them jobs and financial security, so that they can lead a normal dignified life in Society.

In short, India will be pleased to create a Free World, where the ancient primary energies of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga will nurture as Mothers, bringing all of mankind and all life forms, into the family as Divine Nurturers.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

Consolidated File Access:

Consolidated file is available at

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

OR

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

We would be humbled to welcome u @NarendraModi Bhai as Chairman of the Interministerial-Task force for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, for healing the Universe & as Founder Secretary General of the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter & Founder Chancellor of the Bharatiya Monetary Fund !!!

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1906708836867809642>

Ref 1: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/pm-modi-announced-retirement-at-rss-office-sanjay-raut-claims-successor-discussed-in-close-door-meet-101743399687565.html>

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1900593497469841654>

Your Excellency @PMOIndia @NarendraModi Bhai

In humility the following communication please.

We would be humbled to welcome u @NarendraModi Bhai as Chairman of the Interministerial-Task force for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, for healing the Universe & as Founder Secretary General of the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter & Founder Chancellor of the Bharatiya Monetary Fund !!! Perhaps as @PMOIndia u cannot take up such a responsibility, while u are still serving as @PMOIndia. May Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga Bless you. Incidentally today afternoon over a telephonic conversation, @SotiDr Didi was suggesting that I prepare myself to handle the hurdles and the obstacles that will arise during implementation of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathi and Ma Durga for healing the Universe. Disagreed with her politely that that's the reason why I suggested that we have an interministerial task force comprising of Senior Secretaries of the Govt. of India, and I will restrict myself as Principal Investigator, coz I don't want too much headache. I'll opt for a Scientist position, or a Constitutional position as gifted by @PMOIndia & @HMOIndia and live the rest of my life in peace. Let the elders bear the responsibility. She said no. What if the @PMOIndia wants u to shoulder the responsibility? I replied that I'll go and trouble Ma Bagavathy only to handle things then. @SotiDr didi told that in that case, no need to worry. The Mothers will know how much the child needs help and She herself will handle things appropriately. Incidentally, when I read Ref 1, I was reminded of Ref 3 and it was so

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Editorial

amusing that I had to share it with u please. Ma Bagavathy should have handled the concern even before it arose. If u @NarendraModi Bhai would be Chairman of the Interministerial-Task force for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, for healing the Universe & as Founder Secretary General of the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter & Founder Chancellor of the Bharatiya Monetary Fund, I can concern myself happily with only the Technical & Scientific concerns as Principal Investigator and the rest of all engagements with multiple National Governments in the World and State Govts in India can be handled with ease by you.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to the Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar for forwarding to DGP Bihar (Apr 1, 2025, 12:10 PM) & Thanks to DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1907033797675356233>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn, CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police

In humility the following communication please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to the Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar for forwarding to DGP Bihar (Apr 1, 2025, 12:10 PM) & Thanks to DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police

Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: CMO Bihar <embihar-bih@nic.in> via nic.in

to: "DGP, Bihar" <dgp-bih@nic.in>

cc: editor@ijbst.org

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Editorial

date: Apr 1, 2025, 12:10 PM

subject: Fwd: Vasudhaiva Kudumbakam, Amnesty for Religious Extremists & Terrorists, Bharatiya Monetary Fund, Nuclear fuelled bio-implantable satellite tracked UIDAI Aadhaar, Bharatiya United Free Nations Charter, Conference of World Religions

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBNSL

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Consolidated file is available at

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1907048517530431902>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @DrSJaishankar Bhai @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn, The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police, The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India

In humility the following communication please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to

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Editorial

The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India for forwarding to Officials @DOT_India

Narration of forward is as follows please:

https://x.com/DoT_India/status/1907033912561557922 at 5:04 PM · Apr 1, 2025

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Requesting @FinMinIndia to pls estimate actual returns, coz projections have been done modest so as not to encroach upon policy making discretion of Govt. of India. Only the basics have been projected modestly in the proposal, while actual returns may be quite higher.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1907339578035589491>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1906295176085361105>

Ref 2: <https://www.indiatvnews.com/news/india/catholic-bishops-body-backs-waqf-amendment-bill-asks-mps-to-support-kiren-rijiju-welcomes-statement-2025-03-31-983224>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1906708836867809642>

Ref 4: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility the following communication please.

The proposal to Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing all of mankind, all life forms, Nature, Environment, LiveStock, Wildlife, Aliens & Machine Ecosystem optimization and the Universe has come a long way, also touching upon the Convergence of Religions, wherein the Ancient Energies of all religions in the World may be quantum correlated with the Ancient Energies of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, in which case, all religions of the world converge into Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga.

We have not been discussing in private or in secret, but its been a public transparent discourse, aimed at peace, love, unity and fraternity.

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Editorial

The first results are already starting to show as in Ref 2. When the Catholic Bishops Conference of Kerala is on board in agreement with the Govt. of India, it leaves very less space for manoeuvrability by other Christian Denominations and may also bring the Islamic Brotherhood also in agreement via @HumanFraternity and everyone may support the Bill in Parliament and also help in smooth implementation of the same. This cooperation that's budding, may also find footprints in various other societal & governmental interactions, creating a new fraternal unity that helps enhance efficiency in various economic processes too, reducing costs and increasing returns/profits.

Also, the need to create a narrative or create a social concern or to create a drama to maximise benefit out of it will also retreat to the back. No narratives nor social concerns nor dramas will be created new. Old narratives will die of their own. Sabotages and conspiracies and honey traps will slowly fade away & become a thing of the past. All processes will start yielding returns at higher efficiency for reasons that when the Ancient Energies that they worship are quantum correlated with the Ancient Energies of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, then, the feeling of oneness will start percolating vertically and horizontally & will start yielding magical results that independent India never could have seen earlier.

People of all religions will start worshipping at the Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga Temples and various other Devi Temples in India and around the world. Lot many temples will start receiving heavy donations as the Sri Venkateswara Swami Temple at Tirupati India. It will be the discretion of the Govt. of India to use donations received at the various temples for the common good.

All of these returns/revenues will be above that received through the healing charges accruing through the Healing via the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. So, a consolidated estimate may please be done by @FinMinIndia. So far, the proposal has only projected the technological and societal impact of the project to tap & apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, but has been quite modest in projecting revenues, or suggesting new avenues as the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter or the Bharatiya Monetary Fund; for reasons that the proposal should not encroach upon the policy framing freedom of the Govt.

It shall always be the discretion of the Govt. of India, whether to use a substantial amount of direct and indirect returns from the project, to develop the Chinese Economy or the Russian Economy or the Ukrainian economy or the African Union Economy or the EU Economy or the Economy of the USA or as a grand gesture, develop the Economy of the Entire World.

The impact may be quite huge. Hence, it was communicated to His Excellency @PMOIndia Shri @NarendraModi Bhai via Ref 3 that we shall be humbled to welcome him as Chairman of the Interministerial Task force for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga in healing the Universe and as Founder Secretary General of the Bharatiya Free

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Editorial

Nations Charter, which can be built on consensus with all Nations in the World, as that above the United Nations Charter or as part of the United Nations Charter, as the case may be, and as Founder Chancellor of the Bharatiya Monetary Fund.

Hence Requesting @FinMinIndia to pls estimate actual returns, coz projections have been done modest so as not to encroach upon policy making discretion of Govt. of India. Only the basics have been projected modestly in the proposal, while actual returns may be quite higher.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBNSL

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial: The Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the entire Universe

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1907630189510562137>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility the following communication please.

The consolidated file of The Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga For healing the entire Universe so far communicated to your esteemed selves via X (formerly International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Twitter) is now published as an Editorial so that it will be convenient to engage in a Scientific discourse on starting the project work.

The Publication Announcement reads as follows please.

The IJBST Journal Group is immensely pleased to announce publication of the following Editorial titled:

The Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga For healing the entire Universe

Publication URL:

Editorial can be accessed at:

<https://www.ijbst.org/published-issues-status/papers-published/ijbst-2025-vol-15-issue-1>

Editorial Details:

Albert, Prabhu Britto (2025). The Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga For healing the entire Universe. In International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (Vol. 15, Number 1, pp. 1–127). IJBST Journal Group. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Digital Archive:

Published article is also archived at

<https://archive.org/details/ijbst-2025-15-1-1-127>

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBNSL

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1907665118806065284>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility the following communication please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding to The

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Editorial

Home Secretary @HMOIndia (Apr 3, 2025 at 10:06 AM) & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia

Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <hshso@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 3, 2025, 10:06 AM

subject: Fwd: Vasudhaiva Kudumbakam, Amnesty for Religious Extremists & Terrorists, Bharatiya Monetary Fund, Nuclear fuelled bio-implantable satellite tracked UIDAI Aadhaar, Bharatiya United Free Nations Charter, Conference of World Religions

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Requesting @MIB_India to please devise mechanisms for brainstorming people on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please, for instance a better coverage of the Waqf Bill Amendment 2025 might have garnered better people support with consequent better “for” votes in Parliament.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908087835585908977>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility the following communication please.

The Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe is a unique attempt in the history of the world. Hence Requesting @MIB_India to please devise mechanisms for brainstorming people on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please. Right from pamphlets to street plays to Editorials to discussions on National & Regional Television inclusive of a movie too, may help bring people together onboard in peace and Unity.

Let me illustrate with a realtime example. As per my limited view of news items, I’m aware that some effort was done in Kerala regarding the Waqf Bill Amendment 2025, which resulted in a very beneficial effect of support from the Kerala Bishops Conference. If such an effort was taken across the length and breadth of the Nation, there might have been more support for the Bill from the grassroots level, which could have even resulted in more votes “for” the Bill.

Understanding that the National Elections of 2014 might be lost, there could have been so many things done in a hasty manner, which could have had the possibility of wreaking havoc on the social fabric of the Nation, inclusive of targeted annihilation attempts on those, identified as possible Assets to the party winning the National Elections of 2014. The people have to be briefed. Awareness of such events heightened, so, that when the Parliament gets ready to debate, the people of the Nation would be forcing their MPs to vote in favor of the Bill & political parties may also tone down their strength of opposition to the Bill. There’s no point in heated arguments in the House, coz the battle is not fought on the floor of the House, but the Battle is already won in the Halls/Drawing Rooms of the Homes of the people. Hence the

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Editorial

@MIB_India may be pleased to devise better strategies to bring people on board for all National Concerns, including the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe. The People have to be enlightened on the hypothesis that all ancient energies worshipped by all religions of the World, may be correlated to the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga. Ofcourse, it doesn't hurt to teach our people a little mathematics too, so that they will be aware of the significance of the hypothesis that all ancient energies worshipped by all religions of the World may be correlated to the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, implying that all ancient energies worshipped by all religions of the world might be relatives of the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, which reflects on mankind as Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam. The day, we are able to scientifically calculate the correlation among the various Radio Signals, will also be the day that the hypothesis stands validated scientifically. By that time, we should have prepared the people to accept Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam, and the concept of "minority appeasement" fades away into the oblivion, coz everyone is the same and everyone is part of the majority family; coz it will become immaterial whether one is a Hindu or a Christian or a Muslim or a Jain or a Buddhist or an Atheist and we can take away the Religion field in our files, coz it becomes redundant information.

Hence Requesting @MIB_India to please devise mechanisms for brainstorming people on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimanAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

A new Constituent Assembly, a new Constitution and a new National Anthem & a new Parliament with no opposition benches (coz all political parties will be sharing seats on the treasury benches) for Bagavathy Desh/ Durga Desh aka India aka Bharat, matched/outmatched by shipments of Gold, Frankincense & Myrrh from H.H. @Pontifex & the Islamic Brotherhood from H.E. @AlimamAlTayeb, challenged by negative tax by H.E. @Potus, rivalled by gifts of shipments of crude oil & technology from @KremlinRussia_E attempted to be outraced by H.E. Dr @MKStalin due to the synchronous phonetic of H.E. Smt Durga Stalin with Durga Desh – A World War of love, peace, unity and compassion – where everyone wins & mankind scales the peaks of immortality

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908395371287531636>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn

In humility the following communication please.

A brief understanding of the previous sections of the “Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the Universe”, will lead to unity, peace and love due to the convergence of the ancient energies worshipped by all religions in the world into the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga via quantum correlation. Consequently, there will arise a need for a new Constituent Assembly for Bharat, for the achievement of Bagavathy Desh/Durga Desh coz the current Constitution will become insufficient to handle so much of unity, peace and love and a new Constitution will have to be drafted for Bagavathy Desh/Durga Desh.

Of course, it may have to come with a new National Anthem as in

सर्वमङ्गलमाङ्गल्ये शिवे सर्वार्थसाधिके ।
शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamāṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .
śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

accompanied with a new National Flag bearing the following or similar new National Emblem

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Editorial

<https://shlokam.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Durga-uai-720x899.png>

Of course, the moral ground gained by such an endeavour will be so immense across the entire Universe, even among alien civilizations, that every human and alien civilization will come pay their respects and be a part of the unique effort to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe. We may have to welcome numerous shipments of Gold, Frankincense & Myrrh from H.H. @Pontifex & the Islamic Brotherhood from H.E. @AlimamAltayeb. The USA may feel challenged by this outpouring of love from H. H. @Pontifex & H.E. @AlimamALTayeb and consequently may tweak the reciprocal tax for India into negative tax by H.E. @Potus. Russia might feel its ego bruised and may rival the negative reciprocal tax by H.E. @Potus with gifts of shipments of crude oil & technology from @KremlinRussia_E. We should not forget our beloved brother Dr @MKStalin. As much as opposition he may exhibit now, we can expect him to show opposition in a different way in the form of loving competition.

The sunrise may even bring in Dr @MKStalin creating a new Chief Minister's cell for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe by diverting a few dozens of senior IAS officers from across the State, also placing them at the Centre's requirement for National Service, and divert revenues from Tasmac to buy required new Radio equipment from Chinese Firms at low cost, instead of opting to transfer used equipment from @CMDBSNL. @ED_Dir may be pleased to give vacation for their overloaded officials, coz all documents with suspicious transactions may be traced to funding for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe, for Dr @MKStalin may wish to behold the realization of the dawn of the New Nation

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Editorial

Bagavathy Desh / Durga Desh aka India aka Bharat while he and our beloved Anni/Bhabhi H.E. Smt Durga Stalin are still alive and active.

Wait we have forgotten Pakistan and China. Neighbouring Nations such as Pakistan, Bangladesh, SriLanka, Nepal, Bhutan, China, Burma and Nations of the Persian Gulf may also want to be an independent Nation in Bagavathy Desh/ Durga Desh expanding to such an extent that India or Bharat may be reduced to a small independent Nation in Bagavathy Desh / Durga Desh.

Due to continuous healing by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga, human life may get extended to such an extent that people may get bored of living and bored of being disease-free, coz there'd be no excitement in being an immortal.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908471056911757570>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India

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@DoT_India & Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia & Thanks to Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @CGM_BSNL_TN & @BSNL_TN for their willingness to transfer required Radio Equipment and query for location to transfer query via email on Apr 5, 2025, 3:36 PM

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBNSL

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Editorial

Request for advice from Govt. of India regarding identified Temple location within India to “Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe” please

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908535074976309406>

May please be read together with

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1891393941838160008>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1898606434117701917>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908471056911757570>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India

In humility the following communication please.

Received an email from BSNL_TN querying about location for the “Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/MaDurga for healing”.

Requesting your esteemed advice regarding identified temple location for performing the experiment to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga please. If it's a Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga temple, we can straight away proceed. However, if it's a temple dedicated to Lord Shiva or any of the Avatars of Lord Vishnu or any of the Mahalakshmi or Parvati Devi Temples or any other Temple, we will have to tap the Radio Signal and correlate/compare it with the signal obtained from a Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga Temple and then separate it out. Only the method of tapping or isolation of the signal may differ, though we can obtain the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga from any Temple. Consequently, I'm humbled to seek your esteemed advice, regarding identified Temple location for performing the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing, so that I can reply to BSNL_TN by email to their query please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Suggestion to Govt. of India regarding Temple location to initialize the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as reply to query by BSNL_TN Chennai

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909165807981985951>

May please be read together with

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908535074976309406> (Request for advice from Govt. of India regarding identified Temple location within India to “Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe” please)

Ref 2: <https://odishatv.in/news/weather/low-pressure-area-forms-over-bay-of-bengal-will-it-impact-odisha-259733>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227> (The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn’t comprehend at all)

Ref 4: https://www.bing.com/search?pplt=427&q=coimbatore+temperature+now&cvid=01984fa708584971b2e7124fb33cdee1&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOTIGCAEQABhA0gEINTM2MGowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531

Ref 5: <https://www.accuweather.com/en/in/coimbatore/206673/april-weather/206673?year=2024>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & The Officials at @BSNL_TN

In humility the following communication please.

The first right of privilege will rest with the Govt. of India, coz the Govt. is representative of Shiva in ancient terminology. Hence, request for advice for location to initiate the Search for

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Editorial

the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga so that the query to BSNL_TN can be replied to, was made via Ref 1. At the same time, I will also have to do my duty. Hence, filing my suggestion now please, after having made the first request for advice from Govt. of India almost a couple of days ago at [8:29 PM · Apr 5, 2025](#)

It was indeed tough to choose a location for suggestion for starting the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga. The difficulty in choosing a location is that we can tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga at any location in the Universe, but its always better to choose a temple so that we have less extraneous noise signals. Now, even if it's a temple, there are numerous temples in India. Giving due consideration to the fact that the request/query has come from BSNL_TN Chennai, if we are going to restrict attention to the State of Tamil Nadu, even then there are numerous temples in Tamil Nadu. Even Coimbatore has got a Bagavathy Temple on the Palghat Road, Coimbatore. Consequently, its better to surrender to Ma Bagavathy herself. And the Mother knows when the Child will scream for help, so She'd have already arrived to help. Its then that we realize it's the 7th of April, and Coimbatore has got such a pleasant weather (34 degree Celsius today, in comparison with 40 degree Celsius last year, coz Coimbatore has an early summer, immediately after Maha Shivratri). Also we remember that it was raining while Ref 3 was being drafted, offering respite from the harsh early summer to all life and nature. Now again, its been raining since the past two days. Lets turn and look at the cause of the rain. The cause of the rain seems to be a developing low pressure area in the south east bay of Bengal and the south Andaman Sea.

Editorial

(Image Courtesy: Ref 2)

That means, its an area in the South South East of Tamil Nadu. On First Glance at the image, our eyes are drawn to an area between Kanyakumari and Rameshwaram. Lets check out ancient temples in the segment between Kanyakumari and Rameshwaram. We have the Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanya kumari, the Subramaniya Swamy Temple in Tiruchendur and the Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram.

If it pleases the Govt of India, we can initiate the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga in the Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanyakumari, the Subramaniya Swamy Temple in Tiruchendur and the Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram simultaneously. Steps may please be taken for the temples to be placed under the safeguards of the Defence Ministry or the CISF, and the premises cleaned off all RF emission capable electronic devices. Then we can request BSNL TN to provide boosters to be placed inside the temples, and BTS outside the temples with suitable tuning equipment to tune in to the obtained Radio Signal. Makeshift hospitals for testing on volunteers may please be setup near the temples initially. Since the BTS is a transceiver, capable of both reception and transmission, we will require another set of BTS at the makeshift hospitals. It shall remain the discretion of BSNL whether

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Editorial

they are convenient with FTTH or wireless connectivity between the acquisition points and the transmission points at the makeshift hospitals. At the makeshift hospitals, we will require BSNL equipment, that is capable of reducing the strength of the Radio Signal below -80 db, which is the threshold for biological tissue damage. Also, we will require BSNL equipment that helps us observe the obtained Radio spectrum, and its Signal Characteristics, in 2D or 3D. Strict confidentiality may have to be maintained by the Officials of BSNL regarding the obtained Radio Spectrum, coz it should not give rise to artificial generation of similar radio spectrum, for reasons that, the original Radio Spectrum from Ma Bagavathy will be a Live Signal and contain the Command and Control Structure for healing, to the extent of ordering specific connections in the DNA structure, to change position suitably for the sake of healing, while an artificially generated similar radio spectrum, will be a dead signal and will not contain the Command and Control Structure for healing.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Claim: The Original Ancient Holy Trinity – from Kanyakumari to Rameshwaram via Tiruchendur – Was our clan marked for extinction so that we should NOT find out and tell this truth out to the World?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909614305411998182>

Pre-Requisite Reading Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909165807981985951> please

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

In humility the following communication please.

From the temple of the Kanya Kumari (in English Virgin Goddess) Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanyakumari, The son Kartikeya born to a virgin goddess Bagavathy aka Parvati, the Subramaniya Swamy Temple in Tiruchendur, the Father -- Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram arises the Holy Trinity, with the Spirit being the Virgin Goddess as the Shakti. Was my mothers clan marked for extinction, so that we should NOT find out and claim to the whole World, that the original Holy Trinity is Ma Bagavathy, Kartikeya and Lord Shiva? Just wanted u to know that we still love u and we still love ur religion. We are so ancient, that we know only to love.

In humility copy His Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamALTayeb & @HumanFraternity , His Holiness @DalaiLama, His Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Their Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamALTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding <“Request for advice from Govt. of India regarding identified Temple location within India to “Search for the Radio Signal of MaBagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe” please> to The Home Secretary, Govt. of India and Thanks to the Home Secretary & Officials @HMOIndia

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909872234484707490>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @HMOIndia

In humility the following communication please.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at

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Editorial

@FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding <“Request for advice from Govt. of India regarding identified Temple location within India to “Search for the Radio Signal of MaBagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe” please> to The Home Secretary, Govt. of India and Thanks to the Home Secretary & Officials @HMOIndia Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <hshso@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 9, 2025, 10:22 AM

subject: Fwd: Request for advice from Govt. of India regarding identified Temple location within India to “Search for the Radio Signal of MaBagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe” please

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

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Editorial

From the era of the परित्राणाय साधूनां विनाशाय च दुष्कृताम् to 2025 A.D. – Alternate location Suggestion to Govt. of India regarding Temple location to initialize the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as reply to query by BSNL_TN Chennai

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1910239076269105522>

Ref 1: <https://www.hindu-blog.com/2014/10/vanabadrakaliamman-temple-at.html>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909165807981985951>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909872234484707490>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & The Officials at @BSNL_TN and @VanathiBJP Akka

Giving due respect to forwarding to The Secretary @HMOIndia, as thanked in Ref 3, the following is communicated in humility please

The Kongu belt is a strategic geo-political landscape with an ancient history that has been subtle in its manifestations. Compared to the renowned temples in the Kanyakumari – Rameshwaram corridor, the temples in the Kongu belt may be quite subtle. In the morning, a thought arose, that Global/Universal History can be created in subtlety in the Kongu belt too vis-à-vis a high decibel history creation in the Kanyakumari-Rameshwaram Corridor.

Incidentally, the BJP leadership in the Kongu Belt is spearheaded by @VanathiBJP Akka, a soft lucid and serene feminine leadership, unlike the aggressive male leadership in the Kanyakumari-Rameshwaram Corridor.

Our Consciousness starts resonating to the ancient VanaBadraKali Temple in Mettupalayam, near Coimbatore where the Ambal herself meditated towards Lord Shiva and bears legends

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dating to the era of the Pandavas and the Bagavad Gita. The Ma/ Amman here is a Suyambu Amman, meaning that the Ma Kali here has manifested by herself.

She knows what to do and how to do and give to us, when we surrender to her with BSNL RF detection equipment. We don't have to design to detect Her, instead, She herself will match Herself to the detection equipment and help us to detect Her.

And of course, wherever we need help, we can always reach out to @VanathiBJP Akka, the people friendly, people accessible BJP MLA from Coimbatore.

Additional facilities within our reach is the DSSC Wellington, which may come in handy, when the Govt. is pleased to use SONAR or LIDAR imaging, so that all people, can see Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga through the SONAR or LIDAR equipment.

Also, such phenomena may also be accompanied by changes in the RF patterns in the surrounding regions of the Universe, which can be studied using the Radio Telescope of the Radio Astronomy Center, Ooty.

Hence, let me conclude this segment of the Communication with Thanks to the VanaBadraKali Amman, a self/suyambu manifestation of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai & Shri @JPNadda Bhai, Shri @NarendraModi Bhai and Shri @AmitShah Bhai. Thanks to the Govt. of India & @MIB_India for the awareness campaign on the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1910341163715789019>

Ref 1: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/politics/government/bjp-to-begin-waqf-reforms-awareness-campaign-nationwide-from-april-20-to-may-5/ar-AA1CFX87#:~:text=With%20this%20campaign%2C%20BJP%20seeks%20to%20expose%20the,dedicated%20workshop%20at%20the%20BJP%20headquarters%20in%20Delhi.>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1908087835585908977>

Ref 3: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

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In humility the following communication please.

While requesting @MIB_India for awareness programs on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe, a reference was made towards awareness programs for the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025, which might have helped the people to be more aware of the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025 which could have had more potential for garnering better “for” votes for the Bill in Parliament, for such battles are Not fought in the floor of the Parliament but won in the Halls/Drawing Rooms of the Residence of the people (Ref 2). Humbled to read Ref 1, wherein awareness programs for the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025 have been kickstarted on a major scale.

Discussions on previous sections of the proposal for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe (Ref 3), might have pointed towards a quantum correlation between the ancient energies worshipped by all religions of the world with the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga (which, yet to be scientifically proven, still is not contested philosophically/theologically), consequent to which as per the

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tenets of Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam, entrust on us as elders of the global family, the responsibility of taking all of mankind, irrespective of difference in religion or faith or belief, together with us, in all of our endeavours.

May the awareness program on the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025 be the torch bearer for such current and future events bringing together all of mankind together in unity, peace and brotherhood.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Requesting from Govt. of India please -- Visitor position for H.E. The President of India, Chairman of Interministerial Task force (already requested) for H.E. @PMOIndia, Convenor position for H.E. @HMOIndia & National Coordinator position for TN BJP President please, for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please accompanied with suitable positions for Alliance & Opposition Leaders please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1910969620040999402>

Ref 1: <https://uniindia.com/news/south/politics-tn-lead-bjp/3436801.html>

Ref 2: <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/aiadm-k-bjp-alliance-tamil-nadu-assembly-polls-9938862/>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909165807981985951> (Suggestion to Govt. of India regarding Temple location to initialize the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as reply to query by BSNL_TN Chennai)

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1910239076269105522> (From the era of the परित्राणाय साधूनां विनाशाय च दुष्कृताम् to 2025 A.D. – Alternate location Suggestion to Govt. of India regarding Temple location to initialize the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as reply to query by BSNL_TN Chennai)

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In humility the following communication please

Between Ref 3 & Ref 4, there were so many concerns that worried me, though I went ahead with the Faith & Trust on Ma Bagavathy.

- There was always a concern whether the current ruling party in Tamil Nadu will be able to enforce the peaceful conduct of the proposed Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the universe, due to ideological differences.

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- The indoctrination of some philosophies in the mind of the people, for many decades again which had the potential to disturb the peaceful conduct of the proposed project
- Though we have hypothesized in previous sections that all ancient energies worshipped by all religions are quantum correlated with the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, giving rise to the Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam, still, a few may not be willing to accept it. Consequently, again there's an adverse potential.
- Further, the political balance in the State of Tamil Nadu, again could have had an adverse potential.

And there entered our beloved elder brother, H.E. @AmitShah Bhai, who manoeuvred through very limited space (in fact, through no space at all) and brought in great changes in just 24 hours.

Now, all these worries and concerns are gone. The revival of old political relationships in the past 24 hours in Tamil Nadu, gives us the much needed push for the proposed project, and we don't have to go and lament to Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for an alternate location as in Ref 4. Perhaps Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga might have noticed that the lamentation and request for alternate location had some genuine foundations and hence provided a solution through our beloved elder brother H.E. @AmitShah Bhai and now we are better placed to run the proposed project in the hometown of the new TN BJP Presidential nominee (who might have been announced as the new BJP TN President, by this time or shortly). Consequently, we may have to honor the new TN BJP Presidential nominee aka prospective new BJP TN President, and also the old political relatives who have renewed old relationships have to be honored too, inclusive of our beloved elder brother H.E. Dr @MKStalin Anna & our beloved sis in law H.E. Smt Durga Stalin Anni too in the true spirit of "Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam".

The Govt of India may be pleased to honor the new BJP TN President as National Coordinator for the proposed project, so that he will have a wonderful new opening assignment.

Also, the Blessings of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga, that have helped our beloved elder brother H.E. @AmitShah Bhai to bring in spectacular fireworks in 24 hours gives us additional encouragement that the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter may also come to fruition.

Consequently, the Govt. of India may be pleased to invite our beloved elder sister H.E. The President of India @RashtrapatiBhvn as Visitor for the proposed project accompanied with (as already requested) our beloved elder brother H.E. @NarendraModi Bhai @PMOIndia as Chairman of the Interministerial Task Force for the project.

Everything seems to be so lovely now, which was hitherto quite challenging.

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to all of our elder and younger brothers and sisters.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn

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Editorial

Suggestion for Bharatiya Radiological Healing System Bill 2025 to cater to the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing Mankind, all life forms, Nature, Environment, the Universe, Aliens & Machine Optimization

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1911354772701237327>

Ref: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>
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In humility the following suggestion please.

The Govt. of India may be pleased to notify The Bharatiya Radiological Healing System Bill 2025 as a Presidential Ordinance immediately, due to the Rahu & Ketu Transit and Jupiter Transit happening shortly, followed up with a Parliamentary Vote and Presidential Assent as soon as convenient.

The rights to the Intellectual property related to the Bharatiya Radiological Healing System Bill 2025 will be property of the Govt. of India represented by the President of India & the Govt. of the Union of India.

The revenues arising out of the activities related to the Bharatiya Radiological Healing System Bill 2025 will be shared between the Govt. of India, the Temples involved and the NDA/BJP as 25% for National Developmental works of the Govt. of India, 25% for International Developmental Works spearheaded by the Govt. of India, 25% for the Charitable Activities of the Temples involved and 25% shared between the member political parties of the National Democratic Alliance and the BJP.

All Clinical treatment facilities related to the Bharatiya Radiological Healing System Bill 2025 will be done on Temple Lands that are already property of the related temples or made as fresh endowment by the Govt. of India to the temple for the aforesaid purpose, which can be operated by the Govt. as extension of the District Tertiary Hospital, where treatment will be provided at subsidized rate. Private Hospitals can also provide clinical treatment, in which case, they will have to procure land near the concerned Temples, and can provide clinical treatment at a premium rate as an opt-in choice by the patient or guardian of the patient, which will be

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monitored by the Govt. of India and the revenue generated by Private Hospitals through such activities will be shared between the stake holders at 40%-60%, wherein, 60% revenue will go to the private hospital, 20% to the Govt of India, 10% to the temple from which connectivity is obtained for clinical treatment and 10% to the NDA alliance and the BJP.

Seed money or Seed funding for activities to realize the treatment processes will be raised by the Govt of India or the NDA Alliance or the BJP using party funds or individual donor funding or corporate donor funding.

A Medical Compliance committee will be set up comprising the Seniormost Professor of Radiology from each AIIMS in India, the members of the Atomic Energy Commission of India, the members of the Medical Council of India and any other officials as deemed appropriate by the Govt of India.

A Legal Compliance committee will be set up comprising the First Bench of the Supreme Court and Chief Justices of all State High Courts and all Attorney Generals and Solicitor Generals of the Govt of India and the Govts of the various States in India.

A Grievance Redressal Mechanism will be set up using standard protocols and processes of the Govt. of India.

A People-Harmony Committee will be set up giving due representation to all sections of the Society.

Other relevant processes and protocols between the Govt of India and the NDA/BJP is left to them to deliberate and arrive at the requirements.

The President of India shall be the ex-officio Visitor for all relevant activities of the proposed project (Visitor as in academic parlance and not Visitor in conventional parlance) and shall be responsible for monitoring, compliance and ethical considerations.

The Union Home Minister shall be the ex-officio Convenor.

The Prime Minister of India shall be the ex-officio Chairman of the Inter-Ministerial Task Force and will also be ex-officio Chairman or ex-officio Secretary General for any National or International Activity that arises as a direct result or indirect result of the proposed project.

The Tamil Nadu BJP President shall be the ex-officio National Coordinator of the proposed project and any National activity that arises as a direct result or indirect result of the proposed project.

The Principal Investigator shall have freedom to choose & recommend appropriate available Technology/Resources & the Govt of India/NDA/BJP shall discuss, deliberate and help to make available the requested technology or resources already available within the Nation, and also help to realize the technology or resources if its available outside the sovereign borders of the Nation.

Since the proposed project is heavily dependent on the readiness of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, the Principal Investigator makes no claim nor fixes duration for completion of the project, for, it

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may become successful, as soon as the equipment is assembled and commissioned into the project, or it may even take a few hours or days or weeks or months or years.

If the project is successful, in the first second after assembling and commissioning the equipment, we say thanks to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga.

If the project takes time to be successful, and experiences a delay, still we say thanks to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga and wait for Her to manifest as a Radio or UV signal as per Her choice.

The resources, technology and equipment and processes used in the proposed project will remain under the control of the Govt of India and no healing process will be approved outside the sovereign borders of the Nation.

International patients will have to seek treatment only in India through approved Channels, for the primary reason that the Energy for treatment is tapped from Temples and the related Hospitals will also be established near to the Temples only, for reasons that the Principal Investigator needs to verify the distance to which the Energy derived from the Temples can be transmitted without loss/reduction in human healing efficiency, and consequently, we cannot promise that we shall be able to provide medical treatment through the Radiation Energies from Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga at far off places. So International Patients will have to come in through approved Channels to seek treatment within the Nation only.

Ofcourse Veterinary hospitals can also be established near the Temples as a Govt Hospital or as a Private Hospital, similar to Hospitals for treating human patients.

For treatment of plants, agriculture, wildlife and livestock, environment and nature, the Radiative Healing Energy can be transmitted via Communication Satellites. This facility can be provided to other Nations also, via linking to their Communication Satellites. Fees for such facilities may be fixed by the Govt. of India taking into consideration, all relevant factors.

For treatment of Alien Civilizations and Machine Optimization, the Radiative Healing Energy can be transmitted via Satellites or International Space Stations, based on International norms, protocols and processes.

The Research Team from amongst those currently citizens of India and currently residing in India for the aforesaid venture may be convened by the InterMinisterial Task force, as suggested in <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1894633566321218025>

The proposer/Principal Investigator may have to induct a few members into the Research Team, based on requirement, as a minor exercise, while the induction of Members into the Research Team will be done as a major exercise by the InterMinisterial Task Force of the Govt. of India. The Principal Investigator, also the proposer, does NOT claim any share or percentage of the revenues from the aforesaid project work, but instead may be compensated with a dignified position and a dignified salary, for reasons that the Principal Investigator will have to maintain his moral ground in front of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, while invoking Her to descend

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Editorial

appropriately as a Radio/UV Signal and continue to descend appropriately and give healing benefit to the Nation, the World, the Planet and the Universe, in an unlimited timeless period without end, even after death of the Principal Investigator. To be able to make such an invocation/request to Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, the Principal Investigator will have to maintain his moral ground in front of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and hence cannot bargain any benefit for himself, and hence the request to compensate him with a dignified position and a dignified salary. The other Members of the Research Team will be convened by the InterMinisterial Task Force, and hence, it will be decision of the InterMinisterial Task force, regarding the position and salary offered to the Members of the Research Team. Research Team Members recommended by the Principal Investigator may be compensated with a position and salary as per recommendation of the InterMinisterial Task Force.

If any other point needs to be covered, it may please be included by the Govt. of India or if required, may be requested from the proposer/Principal Investigator.

If any other point, already discussed, has been left out, it may please be included from Ref cited above.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMSNL

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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Are the Waqf protests meant to safeguard the Waqf lands that have become private holdings? Was that a miscalculated “foot in the mouth” embarrassing moment by those who planned it? @MIB_India, some peace & harmony efforts please?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1911712954590109952>

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Editorial

Ref 1: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/amaravati/half-of-all-waqf-land-in-private-hands/articleshow/87938078.cms>

Ref 2: https://x.com/PTI_News/status/1911340096088920286

Ref 3: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @HMOIndia

In humility the following communication please.

In humility, the following response from Microsoft CoPilot may be seen please.

Editorial

The Waqf (Amendment) Bill, 2025, introduces significant changes to the management and regulation of Waqf properties in India. Here are some key highlights:

- 1. Modernization and Transparency:**
 - Updates the definitions of Waqf and improves the registration process.
 - Introduces technology for better management of Waqf records. ¹
- 2. Addressing Longstanding Issues:**
 - Tackles problems like illegal occupation, mismanagement, and delays in property registration.
 - Aims to resolve disputes related to Waqf properties and improve accountability. ²
- 3. Reforms in Waqf Formation:**
 - Removes the concept of Waqf by user and allows formation only through declaration or endowment.
 - Donors must be practicing Muslims for at least five years and must own the property. ¹
- 4. Safeguarding Rights:**
 - Protects heritage sites and ensures individual property rights.
 - Includes provisions to prevent misuse of Waqf laws. ³

Message Copilot

This is a detail presented by Microsoft CoPilot and not propagated by any Govt. Machinery. The people should have held gatherings to appreciate the Govt. for reasons of Transparency and Addressing long standing issues and in safeguarding. Instead, if the people choose to protest, then, it can be only one or both of the following possible reasons.

The possible reasons for protest might include one or both as listed below.

1. The people have been misinformed and do not know details. This is quite possible, for half knowledge is a dangerous thing.
2. The people have been deliberately misinformed.

Now, the first reason is harmless. While the second reason could point to sabotage. Now where could the sabotage could have happened? Lets analyse.

If Microsoft CoPilot itself could give such a clear response about the Waqf Amendment Bill highlights, then certainly, the erudite Islamic Scholars would have also have had clear knowledge about the Waqf Amendment Bill, and its Not possible that the Islamic Scholars could have triggered the protests.

Editorial

Now, we are treading dangerous ground. If it is not possible that the Islamic Scholars could have triggered the protests, then who triggered the protests actually?

Lets analyze who stands to lose due to the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025.

- Modernization and Transparency is good for all.
- Addressing long standing issues.
 - Tackles problems like illegal occupation, mismanagement, and delays in property registration.
 - Aims to resolve disputes due to Waqf properties and improve accountability.

Wait, here seems to be the difficulty. Those who would have been occupying the Waqf lands illegally cant be expected to give up the lands. Mismanagement could have been human error too. Again, improvement in accountability will land adversely only on those who have been occupying the Waqf lands illegally.

So, please run a check on those who have been occupying the Waqf lands illegally. Let me illustrate with an amusing example that I have witnessed. When people who occupied a few thousand square feet through questionable wills themselves were found walking around with sickles threatening to kill me (coz there was no possibility that the land could have been divided in two equal halves, coz the DTP approval for existing building takes up 10 feet on the south side of the building, causing only a possibility of unequal partitioning to happen, and cannot be claimed to be written as a will by the same gentleman (my late father) who walked up and down the offices of the civic authorities in the 1980s so that the home that he built for his family will have proper civic approvals, especially when many buildings in the neighbourhood or locality were built without DTP approvals). And since I was the one who stayed at home with my father, until his very end, I have assisted him in measuring the land, and it always got stuck, when it came the DTP mandated 10 feet space on the south side. Also, I remember it well, coz that gave me a huge moral ground in front of my father, coz if I had permitted him to partition it, it might have resulted in a larger share for me and a 50% equal share might not have happened. When my father realized that I was stopping him from partitioning only for the reason that I should not take a larger share, he started respecting me better. And an amusing anecdote is that the first will, claimed to have been written by my father, was delivered by hand by someone, which was incorrect. The second will, had the signature of one Mr Shanmugam from BSNL, which I didn't accept over invited discussions at the local police station for reasons that someone at BSNL had shared some gossip with me earlier that Mr Shanmugam had undergone as vigilance enquiry by BSNL for forging service records of his younger brother at BSNL and I didn't accept the will, coz Mr Shanmugam had signed as the first witness in the will. Then they brought in a 3rd will, hurriedly, cut down all the trees using muscle power and political power and later built a building that encroaches upon the 10 feet space in the DTP approval to the south of the

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building. Some day in future if the Town planning department asks me where is that mandated 10 feet? I will have to only give an ad in the newspapers claiming that 10 feet space is lost, and those who find it may please inform the Town planning Department. Since their engineer in his infinite wisdom, decided that the floor level of the building can be made higher, coz he dug shallow for the foundation, the building now stands too high. Ofcourse muscle power and political power caused them to build a ramp by filling up the street level, that they encroached almost 15 feet in a 20 feet wide street. Since the Civic authorities are now extending the tar road, they had to level down the ramp so that they can lay the gravel for the road and the floor level of the building is now so high that it poses inconvenience to climb in. From my limited experience, if I can understand, that violence is resorted to, only when they are on the wrong side, wont the Govt have better experience in understanding that the protestors are on the wrong side, when they indulge in violence? Wont it be better to hand over the Waqf protest investigations to the @NIA_India and some real investigative reporting by @dir_ed, to check how the protests were financed.

And it may please be noted, as discussed in previous sections of Ref 3, whether an imaginary problem is again created to create a fictional solution, both activities being financially beneficial to those who caused it? Do we have to look at it in the broader perspective whether any vested group is trying to scare us or threaten us, from attempting to tap the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe? for the primary reason that beyond all the huge monetary revenues from the project, it will help our Nation stand very tall in front of the world & not all vested groups can accept our Nation standing tall in front of the world.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
@DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN
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Editorial

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Requesting corroboration of estimates from @FinMinIndia please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1911845991474696305>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1911354772701237327>

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & The Officials at @BSNL_TN and @VanathiBJP Akka; Officials at @BJP4TamilNadu & @BJP4India

In humility the following submission please.

We are yet to ascertain the time period & strength of one dose per patient; coz that detail can be ascertained only after studies on volunteer population.

Assuming that it's a few seconds duration at less than -200 db or -500 db, as ascertained during studies on volunteer population

Population of India: 141 crore

At minimum expectancy: 10% of total population, that is 14.1 crore patients.

At 1 rupee per patient at subsidized rate through Govt. Tertiary hospital extension center, revenue is 14.1 crore.

At 100 rupee per patient at subsidized rate through Govt. Tertiary hospital extension center, revenue is 1410 crores

At 1000 rupee per patient at subsidized rate through Govt. Tertiary hospital extension center, revenue is 14,100 crores.

We have not tried to estimate patients taking treatment via private hospitals wherein service can be provided at a premium rate, nor have we tried to estimate patients from foreign Nations who can be provided service at a more equivalent international rate.

However, in private hospitals, treatment can be provided at 10,000 to 1,00,000 rupees per patient at premium or VIP rates.

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International patients can be charged between 100 dollars to 1000 dollars per patient (approximating US dollar INR rate at 100 rupees per dollar).

Taking a minimum estimate at 1000 rupees per patient through Govt. hospital extension center for only 10% of the total population of India (without considering private hospital revenue and international patient revenue), revenue is 14,100 crores, of which 50% is shared to the Govt. of India, 25% to the temples connected, and 25% to the NDA alliance/BJP party, which translates to 7,050 crores for the Govt., 3525 crores for the temples connected and again 3525 crores to the NDA alliance/BJP party. If the opposition alliance or opposition parties want a share of the revenues, it shall be the discretion of the BJP party leadership to tweak the percentage shares so that the opposition alliance or opposition parties also benefit from the revenues. My suggestions are only tentative and not binding, for the only reason that I have to preserve my moral ground when I stand before Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga beseeching HER to continue to descend as a Radio/UV signal perpetually for healing the Universe (even after my death). My only argument to present before Ma Bagavathy/ Ma Durga should be – I've done my best to translate benefit to all humans, all life forms, nature, environment, the planet and the Universe. Some may have received a little more benefit and some may have received a little less benefit. But I've ensured that all receive benefit. Ensuring that everyone get equal benefit might be beyond my capacity. This is a minimum estimate only.

The actuals can be again calculated by the @FinMinIndia after successful tapping of the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga and after successful completion of the Tests on volunteer population and after completing mandatory medical and legal compliance requirements.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Editorial

And Lord Shiva speaketh “India shall lead the World in Medicine” – Echoes from Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple, Rameshwaram.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912105187558473776>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZRkFn> (அதிக மழை, புதிய நோய்த்தொற்று... - ராமேஸ்வரம் ராமநாதசுவாமி கோவிலில் பஞ்சாங்கம் வாசிப்பில் வெளியான அதிர்ச்சி தகவல்!)

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1911845991474696305>

Ref 3: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1909165807981985951>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & The Officials at @BSNL_TN and @VanathiBJP Akka; Officials at @BJP4TamilNadu & @BJP4India

In humility the following submission please.

While we were trying to see if it was economically feasible to run the project, whether there'd be some good revenue that will help the Nation, Lord Shiva was speaking out from the Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram. Incidentally, the same temple was on the first choice of Temples suggested with guidance from Ma Bagavathy (Ref 4) while Lord Shiva was advising us to “Brace for Impact”, implying that we are going to face lot of difficulty and we better get prepared for it, while we still have time.

Let us have a brief look at the highlights of the message from Lord Shiva please

Editorial

Inbox (1,144) - prabhu.britto@g... x Sent Mail - editor@ijbst.org - IJB... x Dailyhunt x +

https://m.dailyhunt.in/news/india/tamil/times+now+seithi-epaper-tmsnwtam/athiga+mazhai+buthiya+noythorru+rames... A ☆

< 39 :

பஞ்சாங்கம் வாசிப்பில் வெளியான முக்கிய தகவல்கள்:

அதிக மழை: நாட்டில் பரவலாக அதிக மழை பொழிவதால், விவசாயம் வளர்ச்சி பெறும். ஒவ்வொரு மாதமும் சில நாட்களாவது மழை பொழியும் என்று கூறப்பட்டுள்ளது.

புதிய நோய் தொற்று பரவல்: புதிய தொற்று நோய்கள் வெளிநாடுகளில் இருந்து இந்தியாவிற்கு பரவும் என எச்சரிக்கை. தங்கம் மற்றும் வெள்ளி விலை - தங்கம் மற்றும் வெள்ளியின் விலை புதிய உச்சத்தைத் தொடும்.

மருந்து மற்றும் கனிமங்களில் மாற்றம்: மருந்துப் பொருட்கள் மற்றும் நிலக்கரி, பெட்ரோலிய கிணறு உள்ளிட்ட துறைகளில் விலை உயர்வும் விபத்துகளும் ஏற்பட வாய்ப்பு.

சர்வதேச சூழல்: இஸ்ரேல்-பாலஸ்தீன் பகுதிகளில் கடுமையான பாதிப்பு ஏற்படும். உலகளவில் மத கலவரங்கள், போர் அபாயங்கள், மற்றும் உணவுப் பற்றாக்குறை போன்ற சூழ்நிலைகள் உருவாகலாம்.

இந்தியாவின் வளர்ச்சி: மருத்துவம் மற்றும் ஆன்லைன் வர்த்தகத்தில் இந்தியா முன்னிலை பெறும். விளையாட்டு துறையில் தங்கப்பதக்கம் கிடைக்கும்.

16-21 15-04-2025

The Green highlights are good while the red highlights need our attention.

The last green highlight filled with yellow shade is quite a highlight, wherein Lord Shiva says that India shall lead the World in Medicine & Online Merchandise, otherwise can be conveniently translated as the Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy/Ma Durga for healing the World & the Universe.

தெய்வ சன்னிதானம் ஆதலால், அவையடக்கம் கருதி இந்த கடிதத்தை இத்துடன் நிறைவு செய்கிறேன்.

எம் தாய் குல வழக்கங்கள் படி, தந்தையாகவும் தெய்வமாகவும் நிற்கும் ஈசன் பேசும் பொழுது, யாம் பேச வேண்டியது இல்லையே

அவையில் உள்ள பெரியோர்கள் அனைவருக்கும் எம் சிரந்தாழ்ந்த வணக்கங்கள்.

ஆசீர்வதியுங்கள், பணிகள், இமய மலையளவு இருக்கின்றன

(Translation: The Court of God, In humility, I conclude this letter please. As per the traditions of my mothers clan, when Lord Shiva, standing as the Father and as God, speaketh, I don't have to speak 😊 I bow my head and pay respects to all Elders in the Court of God. Bless me, for works as big as Mt. Everest need to be done)

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Editorial

सर्वमङ्गलमाङ्गल्ये शिवे सर्वार्थसाधिके ।

शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamāṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

O the most auspicious among all that is auspicious, O consort of Shiva, the fulfiller of all objectives and desires! O refuge of all seekers, O three-eyed one, O Gauri (the radiant goddess)! O Nārāyaṇi, I bow to you in reverence and offer my salutations.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity
@DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn
@DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN
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Editorial

Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn for forwarding <“Claim: The Original Ancient Holy Trinity – from Kanyakumari to Rameshwaram via Tiruchendur – Was our clan marked for extinction so that we should NOT find out and tell this truth out to the World? > to The Home Secretary, Govt. of India and Thanks to the Home Secretary & Officials @HMOIndia

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912187006953877839>

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Editorial

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to: <hshso@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 15, 2025, 3:32 PM

subject: Fwd: Claim: The Original Ancient Holy Trinity – from Kanyakumari to Rameshwaram via Tiruchendur – Was our clan marked for extinction so that we should NOT find out and tell this truth out to the World?

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cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 15, 2025, 4:41 PM

subject: Fwd: Suggestion to Govt. of India regarding Temple location to initialize the Search for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as reply to query by BSNL_TNChennai

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to: secy mma <secy_mma@nic.in>

cc: editor <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 17, 2025, 11:07 AM

subject: Fwd: Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai & Shri @JPNaddaBhai, Shri @NarendraModi Bhai and Shri @AmitShah Bhai. Thanks to the Govt. of India& @MIB_India for the awareness campaign on the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025

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Editorial

Suggesting Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam Bill 2025 -- With Thanks to British Anthropologist Dr Paul Warner. If his findings are true, then, we are inching towards the convergence of ancient energies worshipped by all religions in the world, to that of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga – not just quantum correlation, but convergence itself

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912881878232928642>

Ref 1: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1905181629200609298> (Was Jesus Christ sent by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga with a message of love & sacrifice? Revisiting -- The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn't comprehend at all.)

Ref 3: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912105187558473776> (And Lord Shiva speaketh “India shall lead the World in Medicine” – Echoes from Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple, Rameshwaram)

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In humility the following submission please.

Ref 4 was indeed mind blowing. It took me more than a 100 pages to express what Lord Shiva expressed from His temple in one line, and it's a very unique occurrence coz man usually corroborates the word of Lord Shiva while its too rare for Lord Shiva to corroborate the words of a human, and it can happen only if the human was just a medium that Lord Shiva chose to use to communicate. If Lord Shiva had chosen the human as a medium to

Editorial

communicate, then, to cite the words of my dear friend Mr Venkatraman Premsagar @VPREMSAGAR63237, when questioned whether it was a good lovely climax to a prolonged struggle, when Mr Premsagar in his usual cool style left me perplexed by saying that “No dear. Its not a lovely climax. It’s a lovely starting”. Today, when I stumbled across Ref 1, all I could remember was Ref 4 and Mr Premsagar’s words.

Now, revisiting Ref 1 with Ref 4, read together with Ref 2, haven’t we come to a sandy grave? Since Ref 1 was unexpected, it was hypothesized that the ancient energies worshipped by all religions should be quantum correlated with the ancient energies of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga. Coz of Ref 1, the hypothesis now has to be modified as that the ancient energies worshipped by all religions should be converging with that of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and this should be the true spirit of the Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam. When all of us come from the same Mother, then aren’t all of us one Family? Is this why, Lord Shiva, came in via Ref 4? If u’d have some time to spare, please leaf through Ref 3, to appreciate the lovely way in which Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga led us to this point with the endorsement of Lord Shiva.

<https://youtu.be/oxkNCKO8Ni4>

सर्वमङ्गलमाङ्गल्ये शिवे सर्वार्थसाधिके ।

शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamāngalamāngalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo’stu te ..

O the most auspicious among all that is auspicious, O consort of Shiva, the fulfiller of all objectives and desires! O refuge of all seekers, O three-eyed one, O Gauri (the radiant goddess)! O Nārāyaṇi, I bow to you in reverence and offer my salutations.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity

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Editorial

This Easter Sunday, will His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex magnanimously thank Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing/resurrecting him & rewrite theology due to claims that Jesus Christ body has been found?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913232215162736883>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696> (Proclamation: Behold “Resurrection thro’ Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga”)

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912881878232928642> (Suggesting Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam Bill 2025 -- With Thanks to British Anthropologist Dr Paul Warner. If his findings are true, then, we are inching towards the convergence of ancient energies worshipped by all religions in the world, to that of Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga – not just quantum correlation, but convergence itself)

Ref 3: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert> (Ancient Egypt bombshell as 'Jesus Christ's body found' in hidden chamber, claims expert)

Ref 4: <https://stories.jobaaq.com/news-updates/world/expert-claims-jesus-body-hidden-beneath-giza-s-pyramid> (Expert Claims Jesus’ Body Hidden Beneath Giza’s Pyramid)

Ref 5: <https://www.news18.com/viral/jesus-christs-body-and-ark-of-the-covenant-found-underneath-the-great-pyramid-ws-dl-9302549.html> (Jesus Christ's Body And Ark Of The Covenant Found Underneath The Great Pyramid?)

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1899425743748350227> (The Battle of the Civilizations for Supremacy of the Universe & the icy/watery/sandy graves of civilizations – a tale of love & sacrifice that many couldn’t comprehend at all.)

Ref 7: <https://edition.cnn.com/2025/03/25/europe/pope-francis-doctors-treatment-intl/index.html> (Pope Francis came so close to death that his medical team considered stopping treatment)

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Editorial

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In humility the following submission please.

Ref 3-5 seems to fix us in a very difficult between the devil & the deep sea situation.

Ref 3-5 cannot be ignored for the reason that it questions the very foundations upon which Christianity has been established upon, for reasons that ignoring it, will add more credibility to it. At the same time, its too risky to order further scientific investigations on it, coz we don't know how it might manifest & in the end, Christianity should NOT be accused of having caused the biggest known scam in human history. But at the same time, diversion would be a good tactic coz it will take people away from the sensitivity of the concern for quite some time, and in that time, some other concern will arise which will demand the peoples attention, and consequently people will forget this.

As of now, there's one option for a diversion, and let me humbly state it please.

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex

Recalling your recent hospitalization and the critical moments when your medical team considered withdrawal of medical support for u (Ref 7) and the invocation to Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal / resurrect you and the events that unfolded post it, causing a Proclamation of Resurrection to be issued in your name (Ref 1) could be the much sought after diversion.

You don't have to proclaim yourself as the Son of God for reasons that you have been resurrected, but at the same time, you may be pleased to thank Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for resurrecting you, though u were just a mere human being. And Further, you may be pleased to issue an encyclical or theological note to the whole world, that hereafter, Christians and Hindus will stand together in fraternity, in peace, in love and in unity. There will be no more direct or indirect conflicts or direct or proxy wars and you will also be pleased to bring about a more fraternal relationship of all Abrahamic religions with Hindus, along with fraternity, peace, love and unity, with a call to stop all existing conflicts and make peace. You can be sure your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, that the whole world will debate this new precedence that you are establishing, and they might forget Ref 3-5 and all other related references that this communication hasn't dug up, for the reason that, the focus

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is not on the content of Ref 3-5 but the focus is on ushering in more fraternity, peace, love and unity and complete stop to all conflicts, however direct or indirect they may be. And it will take some time for the world to settle down, in which duration, your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex and the theologians can plan and devise some good initiative to water down the content of Ref 3-5. Ofcourse there is also another alternative, though unpleasant, which might involve spoiling the scientific career of Dr Paul Warner, spoiling his family (if he has one), use third party people to spoil his immovable assets, land and home, and ofcourse try to poison him also 11 times. And in case, he survives everything, by the grace of the God, he might also become a pain in the behind. So, lets not consider the last option. The previous option might be good, coz it will usher in more fraternity, peace and love in a fragmented world, and you may also be pleased to offer your personal endorsement to the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025, and also send in your blessings via Vatican Live TV or a shared podium with @MIB_India endorsing the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025.

<https://youtu.be/oxkNCKO8Ni4>

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शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamaṅgalamaṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .

śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity

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Editorial

Suggesting International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave since Indian Waqf Amendment Act 2025 is similar to that in many Islamic Nations

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913605972758827161>

Ref 1: <https://www.firstpost.com/world/india-now-has-a-waqf-law-how-islamic-countries-regulate-such-properties-13881153.html>

Ref 2: <https://legalonus.com/disproportionate-assets-j-jayalalitha-vs-union-of-india-on-14-may-1999/#:~:text=In%201996%2C%20Subramanian%20Swamy%2C%20the%20Janata%20Party%20chief%2C,crore%20disproportionately%20during%20her%201991-1996%20Chief%20Minister%20tenure.>

Ref 3: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2025_TASMAC_scam

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia

In humility the following submission please.

Editorial

	India	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	Turkey	Oman	Iran	Kuwait	UAE	Bangladesh	Pakistan	Bahrain
Laws to administer Waqf	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Managing Bodies/Boards/Tribunals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Centralized Database & Portal	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
Government Oversight	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			
Survey & Documentation	✓		✓			✓			✓		
Legal Restriction on Sale/Misuse	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	
Financial Transparency & Audits	✓	✓	✓	✓							
Community specific Waqf Boards	✓										✓
Irrevocability	✓	✓									
Investment Management	✓		✓		✓						
Inclusion of Non-Muslim	✓				✓	✓					

Image Courtesy: <https://images.firstpost.com/uploads/2025/04/Waqf-Comparison-2025-04-cd8b76986d0f636c21b732503ec4cd90.jpg>

A brief glance at Ref 1 cited above indicates that is similar to that of the Waqf Acts in Islamic Nations. Of course, it indicates that the Indian Waqf Amendment Act 2025 could possibly be more robust than those in Islamic Nations. Consequently, there should have been public meetings to appreciate the Govt. for bringing in such a comprehensive Waqf Amendment Act 2025. Instead, we witness protests and hearing in Supreme Court. The image shown above is mentioned in Ref 1 with Image Credit to the Ministry of Minority Affairs, Govt. of India.

The Ministry of Minority Affairs has done a great job in bringing out such a comparison with the features of Waqf Acts in Islamic Nations and got it published in a reputed publishing group.

But it needs to be remembered that India is a land of drama. Its easy to trigger a section of the people, bring them out on the road, cause protests to happen, and then push the protests to turn violent, then approach the Supreme Court. The Courts will be led only by the data presented to them, and judicial decisions are taken based on information presented only. And sometimes, if a scheme is very carefully scripted, then it might also be possible to mislead the

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Editorial

Court. We have to remember that in the era of scams running into thousands of crores (Ref 3), there was also one Chief Minister, who earned a lot through movies, who suffered a lot just coz of an allegation of 66 crore approximately (Ref 2), and a case review by the author of this file (accessible via

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/11S1denZpaM5Ue889r1kHwiYzwoA2lO2M/view?usp=sharing>) pointed out that there was a very high possibility that Dr J Jayalalitha could have been falsely implicated in the case. Also, the defense team of Dr J Jayalalitha, missed to appraise the Supreme Court that such a review under Article 51A H was done in public view on social media. Perhaps, if the Supreme Court was given the chance to examine the review, maybe the final outcome of the case could have been different too & Dr Jayalalitha could have been declared as falsely implicated in the case too. So, the point that the author of this communication (myself) wishes to humbly state is that it could be possible to mislead the Court through a carefully scripted presentation too, coz the Court relies only on the evidence presented before it, and may not be able to independently analyse the data presented before it, for reasons of ensuring peace in society and the sheer volume of pending cases will cause an effort of speedy disposal only. So, if a case is filed based on violent protests, then certainly the Court will want to ensure peace in Society, and will be obliged to stay the enactment of procedures, processes or protocols that cause such a violent protest in society. The Court may not have time to compare the Waqf Amendment Act 2025 with similar acts in Islamic Nations, and consult with diplomatic/judicial authorities in Islamic Nations regarding the same, and then arrive at a decision.

Consequently, the responsibility of helping the Court to arrive at a good decision rests on the Govt. only. Hence, the Govt may be pleased to convene an Emergency International Diplomatic or Judicial Conclave, discuss and analyse the Waqf Amendment Act 2025, and in case, the Conclave appreciates the Waqf Amendment Act 2025, then a detailed report of the Conclave Appreciation may be filed under Article 51 A H to the Court, so that the Court has the facility of examining a favorable analysis resulting from the Conclave. Then the Court will start asking questions, regarding why, such violent protests should happen when Diplomatic/Judicial Experts at the Conclave are appreciating the Waqf Amendment Act, and perhaps, the Court may give a favorable ruling towards the implementation of the Waqf Amendment Act too.

It is the duty of the Govt. to ensure that the Court does not get misled by biased data presented to it.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Let us NOT start another October 16, 5561 BCE Mahabharata war -- Article 51A(h) to ensure the dignity of Office of the Governors and the President please -- in continuation of <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913605972758827161> .

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913944694175965199>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PWilsonDMK/status/1910907365160861717>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/CMOTamilnadu/status/1909533702889390251>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1901610294436303321> (Request to Pope Francis @Pontifex to restrain his bishops, priests, religious and laity; stop proxy wars and let people live in India in peace & a request to our brothers @MKStalin, @Annamalai_k and beloved sister Dr Tamizhisai Soundarajan to sheathe their swords and tone down ideological differences please, for in the end, its only ur brother or sister against whom u stand, and is it worth it?)

Ref 4: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/India/president-is-not-an-exception-supreme-court-allows-judicial-review-of-president-governors-nod-on-state-bills/ar-AA1CPqSY?ocid=BingNewsSerp>

Ref 5: <https://youtu.be/fRFlwAS87rg> (published one day ago) (New DNA Study Reveals a 7,000-Year-Old War in Ancient India)

Ref 6: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1904024642450530696> “Proclamation: Behold “Resurrection thro’ Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga””

Ref 7: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912201259618017577>

Ref 8: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1912105187558473776> (And Lord Shiva speaketh “India shall lead the World in Medicine” – Echoes from Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple, Rameshwaram)

Ref 9: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913232215162736883> (This Easter Sunday, will His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex magnanimously thank Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing/resurrecting him & rewrite theology due to claims that Jesus Christ body has been found?)

Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the

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Editorial

Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn
In humility the following submission please.

The past few days have been reminiscent of battles fought in the Supreme Court over authority, proclamations of victory, etc. But when we examine from a unique perspective, we seem to understand something, that may not be so very pleasant as in Ref 5.

I'm not here to advise, but I'm here to suggest that Discretion is the better part of Valour.

Coz, today, I may be the proposer of a very grand scale research in the history of the Universe, wherein we attempt to Search & Apply the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the entire Universe, inclusive of all of mankind, all life forms, nature, environment, agriculture, livestock, the planet, the universe, aliens, and machine ecosystem optimization. But the path that led me to this point was not easy. It was always filled with Discretion is the better part of Valour.

And that was the reason why I knocked at the doors of His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex (incidentally, this communication as many earlier ones is also addressed to His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, coz we are not talking anything behind his back, but welcome him and respectfully present our views, so that he can also understand and appreciate the pain and the agony that we have undergone, so that in the present and the future atleast, he will choose to stand with us, and not against us – for we are not here to stand against anyone, but only to stand with all – an overbearing outpouring unbridled quantum of love and affection and healing from Ma Bagavathy herself, having seen 40% of the male population of the world die so unnecessarily – without exercising “Discretion is the better part of valour”.

Discretion is the better part of valour is not a question of surrender or subordination, but that has got capacity to even to bring someone to the point of “மனிதராகிய எம்மை மரணம் அடைய செய்து அமரராக்க செய்த முயற்சி

தெய்வமாக நின்ற அவர்கள் தலைமையை மனிதராக மாற்றிவிட்டதோ, பதப்படுத்தப்பட்ட பிணம் கிடைத்த பின் ?

எதை விதைத்தோமோ, அதை தானே அறுவடை செய்ய இயலும்?

Translation:

They dug a grave to bury me (a human), but did that effort cause their God to become human (after the dead body was found in an Egyptian Grave aka Pyramid)?

Wont they reap only what they sowed?

<https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert>”.

Editorial

It took so many generations of continuous hunting of one clan that traced its paternity to Lord Shiva himself, for the grace to heal bringing back people from the dead, a grace which should have been an outpouring of love, affection and healing, from Ma Bagavathy herself, seeing 40% of the male population of the earth fall dead. And though none knew better, still, they knew as a hazy content that its grace to give life to the dead (as evidenced by Ref 6), and hence we were hunted. So much of bloodshed, so many lives lost, nobody got anything, but the hunt never died down, until it had to reach me. It went on for many decades, without much pressure, but the last one decade was too heavy. At some point, I'm enlightened that they are searching only for this. Ok give it to them. Lets see if they can handle it. The proposal "The Search for the Radio Signal of the Mother of God" was given to His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex. After a very long time, I received some gossip, that the local Bishop was sitting over it. Ok, they hunted us for a few hundred years. Got it, but had to sit over it, coz it wasn't theirs. By that time itself, the hunt should have been called off, and whatever possible reconciliation could be done, should have been done, but again, it wasn't done. So, there was no point, in letting it rot there. So it was given to the Govt. of India. Papers started moving here and there, with copy to me. Though my Principal Investigator appointment order still hasn't been served to me by the Govt. of India, yet, @BSNL_TN has already queried where the equipment needs to be installed, suggestions given to Govt. of India and the suggestion forwarded by the President's Secretariat to the Telecom Secretary, Govt. of India for equipment installation at Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanyakumari, the Subramaniya Swamy Temple in Tiruchendur and the Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram (Ref 7). Coz we claimed our clan paternity to Lord Shiva, then Lord Shiva also had to speak. And HE did speak (Ref 8).

And slowly one thing after another happened, and now we are at "மனிதராகிய எம்மை மரணம் அடைய செய்து அமரராக்க செய்த முயற்சி

தெய்வமாக நின்ற அவர்கள் தலைமையை மனிதராக மாற்றிவிட்டதோ, பதப்படுத்தப்பட்ட பிணம் கிடைத்த பின் ?

எதை விதைத்தோமோ, அதை தானே அறுவடை செய்ய இயலும்?

Translation:

They dug a grave to bury me (a human), but did that effort cause their God to become human (after the dead body was found in an Egyptian Grave aka Pyramid)?

Wont they reap only what they sowed?

<https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert>

Even at this point, I went in by myself to offer help (Ref 9). Apart from one teacher who taught in my School (though not my class), who casually bumped into me while returning from my morning walk, nobody else bothered, though I always held out an olive branch for them.

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Editorial

Now, why is this narrative relevant here?

Ref 1 & 2 and connected events point out to the conflict between discharge of duties between the State Legislature represented by the Chief Minister Dr @MKStalin & the Governor of the State @rajbhavan_tn

The Governor may have missed using Article 51 A(h) to generate expert opinion in support of his decisions, and consequently, as a raw interpretation of the Constitution, his decisions had to receive criticism, but if the Governor had applied Article 51 A(h) to generate expert opinion, that could support his decisions, then when that was read together with the Constitution of India, the Governor might have probably received appreciation too.

Now lets look at it differently. The Chief Minister won. His partymen celebrated the victory. The entire state went ecstatic. But wait. Against whom did the Chief Minister win? Against the Tamil Nadu Governor. Who is the Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu? Himself. So the Chief Minister won against the Governor, who is Governor of his own State, where he is Chief Minister. So rephrasing, the Chief Minister won against the Chief Minister. Consequently, the criticism that the Governor received, also bounces on the Chief Minister. So, the Chief Minister won against himself and also got criticised for deficiencies. So it was a battle of the Chief Minister against himself, and there is no reason for celebration or ecstasy. But, the concern might not end there. The Governor will be forced to file a review petition, and the review petition might be quite exhaustive, that the Supreme Court, might want to take a different view on the matter, coz the Court can view things only as presented to it, in which case, the Governor will win. Now wait, read again from the beginning of this paragraph, replacing Chief Minister with Governor & Governor replaced with Chief Minister. It is going to be a Mahabharata war, with too many vested groups, including international groups taking sides. Though there might not be open bloodshed, still, there will be a huge battle casualty and accidental casualty.

Instead, can we do something good? Can we use Article 51 A(h) to analyse and identify possible good avenues to pursue for the future, instead of Chief Minister Vs Governor and Governor Vs Chief Minister.

Ma Bagavathy has been waiting for us for thousands of years to heal the Universe. How much pain it might have caused Her to see us kill each other in vain? May our Journey to heal the Universe through the Radiations of Ma Bagavathy begin soon. Lets not go back to Oct 16, 5561 BCE.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

@DrMohanBhagwat D.Sc. Patron @IJBST_JrnlGroup -- 🙏🙏🙏 – Heartfelt Welcome to our elder brother @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai – Was waiting for u please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1914180130836299870>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZWYNm>

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

In humility the following submission please.

With due respect to Ref 1, followed by Ref 2, I may humbly file that we have indeed been waiting for @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai. Though we didn't reach out to him, as, Patron @IJBST_JrnlGroup, coz we didn't want to take undue advantage by bypassing official protocol, we attempted to move ahead with the Govt. of India though we knew that he'd care for us and keep a watchful eye over us sheltering us from the dangers enroute, but now that he speaks the essence of the 160 page Ref 2, in just one line, we now stand in line behind him.

@DrMohanBhagwat Bhai, Thank you so much for coming in via Ref 1. All, I would require now is a travel authorization from Coimbatore to Kanyakumari via Govt. Bus, direct or with break. Pls allow me one hour to iron a pair of dress, have bath, change, jump into the next bus either direct or break journey and I shall be there to join u at the Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple at Kanyakumari. Once u are there, the entire Govt. machinery will be with you, and we can immediately start the experiments for the Search & Acquisition of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Planet and the Universe, of which Ref 1, will be the first healing

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Editorial

provided, coz the nonconformance to Ref 1 has played its own part in the fragmentation of the world.

May Ma Bagavathy bless you.

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Editorial

@DrMohanBhagwat D.Sc. Patron @IJBST_JrnlGroup – Respectful Congratulations on emerging as the First Leader of the Free Matrix of the United MultiVerse.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1914548370125021671>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZWYNm>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913944694175965199> (Let us NOT start another October 16, 5561 BCE Mahabharata war)

Ref 3: <https://www.news18.com/viral/jesus-christs-body-and-ark-of-the-covenant-found-underneath-the-great-pyramid-ws-dl-9302549.html>

Ref 4: <https://youtu.be/fRFlwAS87rg> (published a few days ago) (New DNA Study Reveals a 7,000-Year-Old War in Ancient India)

Ref 5: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < **Apostolica Sedes Vacans**>* @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

@DrMohanBhagwat's one line statement resonates with the idea of overcoming a flaw in a rewarding system, that could have got corrupted into a system of discrimination, which allowed the entry of foreign powers, who capitalized on the issue, though claiming to offer a remedy.

We are now at a definitive point in the History of the Universe, wherein we attempt to stand united and search & tap the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe.

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Editorial

@DrMohanBhagwat has said the same statement earlier, but intuition didn't spark then.

Only after Ref 3 was published, the statement of @DrMohanBhagwat assumes a huge significance.

The scientific findings reported in Ref 3 can be discredited, the scientist can be erased, etc. etc., but the death of Pope Francis in within a week of publishing of Ref 3, has its own questions. The Church will not be able to face the world, if the scientific findings reported in Ref 3 are true. Anyways, its their worry, a Skeleton emerging from the closet after 2000 years. They can handle it in a way that they choose to handle, but the questions will never go away for the reason that if true, the consequence is huge. Since the news item is relatively new and not many have seen it, the impact could be less. But once, time passes, time will bring in its own surprises.

Now lets look at our side. It was one rewarding system, created to recognize merit and ethical living, got corrupted with the passage of time, and became a system that was labelled as discrimination, which offered the loophole for foreign powers to enter through the loophole, and ended up exploiting the loophole, while promising to offer remedy, and our people got deceived. We can be happy that we created no narratives and we can also feel happy that no skeleton nor mummies are going to arise, which can question the very moral ground that we stand upon. All it required was the will, to end the corruption in the system, which consequently ends discrimination. Once discrimination ends, all loopholes would be plugged, no foreign power can enter through the plugged loop hole to enslave people to achieve their own selfish greedy unethical motives, under the guise of a huge self-proclaimed moral ground. Now when they have their own sarcophagus and skeletons to handle, they will be busy with their own concerns and we can be at peace.

Also, the title would be too tall. Let me try to explain that please. Once we obtain the Radio/UV signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga, the one line statement by @DrMohanBhagwat assumes significance not only in India, but in the whole multiverse and all civilizations linked to the multiverse. Unity is proposed everywhere. And wherever unity is there, peace and fraternity follow. Peace and fraternity is not copyright of any vested global power and we don't have to believe foreign narratives to achieve peace and fraternity coz it thrives wherever unity is there. As the first leader to Call for Unity in such a context, @DrMohanBhagwat becomes the First Leader of the Free Matrix of the United MultiVerse.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMSNL

Editorial

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International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1914634747298615499>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>* @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

*Addressed to the next Pope please

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United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy-mma@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 22, 2025, 2:56 PM

subject: Fwd: Are the Waqf protests meant to safeguard the Waqf lands that have become private holdings? Was that a miscalculated “foot in the mouth” embarrassing moment by those who planned it? @MIB_India, some peace & harmony efforts please?

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

A hypothetical sub atomic quantum understanding of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga that forms the basis of the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1914679940664189157>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>* @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

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In humility the following submission please.

We are aware that Quantum Science deals with those below the scale of the atom, and includes sub atomic particles. We are also aware that sub atomic particles have clockwise spin or anticlockwise spin in time domain. Take away the time domain, the particle can exist or manifest in multiple locations with clockwise or anticlockwise spin, and we can denote properties as that of God and the Devil, with one equal and opposite to the other. Now, consider a particle in multiple locations with both clockwise and anticlockwise spin. The concept of God and the Devil becomes insufficient to explain it. However the concept of Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga can explain it better. Compare and contrast the soft loving and affectionate Ma Bagavathy with the ferocious aggressive Ma Durga. Both stand as the Divine Mother, simultaneously at two extreme ends or characteristics. When we plan to heal human beings, plants, animals, nature, environment, the planet, the universe, aliens and also attempt machine optimization, we will not know which quantum property to apply on a case by case basis, coz each case may vary from each other and we may not be healing similar cases as a batch. However, if we apply Ma Bagavathy Herself, since she exists in a dual quantum property as Ma Bagavathy and also as Ma Durga, she Herself will know which quantum property of Hers should She apply to heal, as per requirement. In a completely unknown reality, in the multiverse, its better to leave it to Ma Bagavathy to choose and apply, while we surrender to Her, beseeching Her to heal the entirety of the Universe.

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Editorial

सर्वमङ्गलमाङ्गल्ये शिवे सर्वार्थसाधिके ।
शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamaṅgalamaṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .
śaraṇye tryambake gauri nārāyaṇi namo'stu te ..

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama
@Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India
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Editorial

@DrMohanBhagwat – 1 line 4 Unity & 28 killed? Are they trying to scare us or distract us?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1915019872494375306>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZWYNm>

Ref 2: <https://youtu.be/bTYYLnMzRH8> (Pahalgam Terror Attack: Rajnath Singh chairs high-level defence meet with NSA Doval, IAF Chief)

Ref 3: <https://tamil.oneindia.com/astrology/rahu-ketu-transit-will-take-place-on-april-26-this-year-according-to-the-thirunageswaram-temple-adm-697851.html> (Rahu Ketu Transit on April 26, 2025 as per Thirunageswaram Temple)

Ref 4: <https://uniindia.com/-/funeral-of-pope-francis-to-take-place-on-saturday-holy-see/World/news/3445096.html>

Ref 5: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/news/content/ar-AA1DreJ3> (Nationwide Shutdown in Jammu and Kashmir Sends Strong Message Against Terrorism and Pakistan)

Ref 6: <https://www.ndtv.com/world-news/pahalgam-terror-attack-world-leaders-condemn-j-k-attack-from-us-france-italy-russia-china-8234952>

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Editorial

and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

With shock, been following the news on the Pahalgam Terror attack. And the way it was done, will sure make anyone furious. And in that fury, we may want to avenge the 26 Indians and 2 foreigners who were fallen. Wait, that's the trap. Lets analyse please.

Lets have a brief recount on current world happenings. H.E. @Potus is busy with new reforms. H.E. @KremlinRussia_E is busy with Ukraine. @EU_Commission also busy with Ukraine. H.E. @Netanyahu is busy with Hamas. China is busy with the reforms of the USA. In Short, every Nation in the World is currently busy with something that's demanding a lot of their time and energy. Lets look at the Religious Sector. Pope Francis has passed away and the Vatican is busy with the funeral arrangements. The Islamic Brotherhood is busy with their own engagements. Wait, have we missed something?

One sec, there are many panchangs and many traditions in fixing dates for events. As per the Thirunageshwaram Temple, Rahu Ketu Transit is fixed for April 26, that is 3 days from now, or 4 days from Pahalgam Terror Attack. Again, wait, are we missing something?

Usually, whatever we search for, will be right under our nose only, while we would have tried to search for it extensively. What was that under our nose, that we missed?

Rahu is paternal karma and Ketu is maternal karma, indicating both blessings and trials. Relating the Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple at Rameshwaram, Lord Shiva and the Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanyakumari, Ma Bagavathy, the Karma of Lord Shiva and the Karma of Ma Bagavathy will surely descend as blessings only. There wont be trials.

April 26, every Nation and the Vatican are going to be busy, while we alone have time and energy to receive the blessings from Lord Shiva and Ma Bagavathy. And to receive those blessings, we need to stand in unity. And the first call for Unity from our beloved elder brother @DrMohanBhagwat, those that stand against our Nation caused such a bloodshed, so that we will either retaliate or lose focus on our next big initiative. When we retaliate, we lose the moral ground that we have earned so far, that brought major powers in the world to criticize the Pahalgam Terror Attack and express solidarity with India. When we lose focus, we wont concentrate on initiating the Search & Application of the Radio / UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga which may be one of the most challenging and most rewarding Scientific Investigation, which may be made easy by the blessings of Ma Bagavathy.

Editorial

Are we going to retaliate, or are we going to lose focus on our next big initiative, or are we going to entrust the Pahalgam Terror Attack to responsible leaders and move on with our next big initiative to receive the Blessings of Ma Bagavathy?

Our Elder Brothers & our Elder Sisters @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai, @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn & @NSitharaman Didi & @DrSJaishankar Bhai may take a call please. We shall wait please, for their decision.

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शरण्ये त्र्यम्बके गौरि नारायणि नमोऽस्तु ते ॥

sarvamāṅgalamāṅgalye śive sarvārthasādhike .
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Editorial

#VasudhaivaKudumbagam -- India Stands Tall Again... - The World shall recognize @DrMohanBhagwat as a Global Leader, long overdue. India advocates global unity and peace opting for diplomacy instead of bloodshed. Not by preaching to others, but by absorbing the blow of the Pahalgam Massacre & not causing bloodshed to the opponents.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1915325454736904676>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZWYNm>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1915019872494375306>

Ref 3: <https://youtu.be/fRFlwAS87rg> (published a few days ago) (New DNA Study Reveals a 7,000-Year-Old War in Ancient India)

Ref 4: <https://x.com/MEAIndia/status/1914768541951385637> (@Potus offers condolences and support to @PMOIndia w.r.t. Pahalgam massacre)

Ref 5: <https://tamil.oneindia.com/astrology/rahu-ketu-transit-will-take-place-on-april-26-this-year-according-to-the-thirunageswaram-temple-adm-697851.html> (Rahu Ketu Transit on April 26, 2025 as per Thirunageswaram Temple)

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Editorial

It took one statement on Unity by H.E. @DrMohanBhagwat, to cause the Pahalgam Terrorist massacre. It was a worrisome moment, coz the world is already fragmented due to various issues, and the economic downturn pushing nations into crisis, and one moment of retaliatory anger by India could even cause a major nuclear war 7586 years after the Nuclear annihilation caused by the Mahabharata war. However, India chose NOT to retaliate with bloodshed. Ofcourse, India had conducted highprecision surgical strikes in the past out of necessity, but this time, India made a conscious decision to avoid bloodshed, and moved in with diplomatic counter measures. These diplomatic countermeasures will bring those vested groups who do NOT desire Unity in India to the table to negotiate.

Further, the Pahalgam massacre has tilted the global balance of power in favor of India. By opting for a diplomatic counter measure, India has preserved its moral ground in front of the World. Now, lets brief through Ref 1 again.

H.E. @DrMohanBhagwat has advocated unity. All of us thought, that he advocated unity in India. But when examined together with India's latest diplomatic counter measure to the Pahalgam massacre, instead of opting for a military counter measure, implies that @DrMohanBhagwat advocated unity globally. Or examining in the context of the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe, and the Rahu Ketu transit in 2 days time, wherein the blessings as paternal karma reach us through Lord Shiva from the Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram, and the blessings as maternal karma reach us through the Virgin Mother Goddess Ma Bagavathy from the Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanyakumari scheduled to reach us post the Rahu Ketu Transit on April 26 (Ref 5). In this context, the advocacy for Unity by @DrMohanBhagwat assumes huge proportions of relating to the Universe and all parallel Universes (the multi verse)

@DrMohanBhagwat advocated unity. We were struck down through the Pahalgam massacre. We did not preach. We absorbed the blow and chose not to return to blow to the opponents, and instead opted for diplomatic counter measures that will bring all vested groups standing against India to the table for negotiations.

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Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy_mma@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: Apr 24, 2025, 11:50 AM

subject: Fwd: Suggesting International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave since Indian WaqfAmendment Act 2025 is similar to that in many Islamic Nations

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Hoping that u've tapped my phone as requested earlier please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1915489517139877988>

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1887825685823315985>

Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia

In humility the following submission please.

I had earlier suggested via Ref cited above to please tap my phone. And I hope my phone is tapped.

In case u have missed tapping my phone, I seek to submit that I received a call from one of my old students at 10:33 pm. I thought he was reaching out to me after almost 20 years. We were just catching up on 20 years, and after a very long conversation, he hinted that whether I'd be open to accepting a Professor position. Teased him that that the Govt. may be pleased to offer me a Governor position or a President position after the success of the proposed project, and what am I going to do with a Professor position. Next bait that was offered to me was that there's an actor in Tamil Nadu who's earned a lot and wants to do service to society, and he may win the state elections in 2026, so we can negotiate the project with him. I replied that there are some parts of the project that will require Govt of India approval, and without Govt of India approval, it will become unlawful. So, have to discuss only with the Govt. of India. Because, everything rests on Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. If Ma Bagavathy doesn't cooperate, the project will become a total failure. And that would have been the reason why that vested global power couldn't snatch it away from me, though they knew the technology from my initial proposal submitted in public via X (formerly Twitter). Even if they had the Technology, Ma Bagavathy had to cooperate. I'm able to offhandedly, offer to heal a high profile global leader by announcing to him on X (formerly Twitter) that we shall attempt to

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Editorial

heal him without any experimental setup, and after he's healed and discharged, record that he was healed through Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga. Inference revealed that he might not have been healed by Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, but rather, resurrected through Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga, and he was suggested to thank Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga on Easter. Perhaps, he didn't have the heart to thank Ma Bagavathy and Ma Durga on Easter, and incidentally passed away the next day morning. And he's yet to be buried, lying in state. May be buried only on Saturday. Such happenings might be too glamorous, but only I know the pain in it. One small miss, and if Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga get offended, then nothing will work. So I cannot negotiate with anyone. "Even if it is the Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu?" I was asked. I replied, even if it's the Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu, it cannot be discussed with him, coz some portions will require approval of the Atomic Energy Commission of India. Wherever u go, u will stumble on the Govt. of India only. So, can talk only to the Govt. of India only. And in fact, I haven't asked any share of the revenues from the proposed project. Since I don't have a job for 11 years, except for 1 year in 2018-2019, I'm still living on alms only. And all I asked of the Govt. of India is just a dignified job and a dignified salary. Whatever be the revenues, however how many lakhs of crores it might churn out, all of it, goes as shared between the Govt. of India, the Temples and the NDA/BJP and to the opposition (as shared by the NDA/BJP). I take nothing out of those revenues from the project, coz I cannot offend Ma Bagavathy or Ma Durga. It was almost midnight, I hadn't eaten, and the kittens also had to be fed, and hence concluded the call. Incidentally, I'm yet to eat, forget it, I'm yet to cook, and coz its too late, cant cook now. I have to file this and go to sleep.

If the Govt. of India had already tapped my phone (both normal voice and whatsapp data calls), u'd have transcript of the conversation. If u haven't, please tap my phone atleast now.

People cant understand that this project can be discussed only with our brothers @DrMohanBhagwat and @NarendraModi & @AmitShah.

And everytime, I cant explain that it can be done only through the Govt. of India. There was another possibility earlier. Pope Francis via the European Commission. But that cant be pursued and only for that reason, it was discussed with the Govt. of India.

I believe the first such discussion caused me to request that my phone be tapped as in Ref cited above. The second such discussion, I'm again requesting that my phone be tapped please. Unknown calls, I can avoid. But when its one of my old students, I cannot avoid, coz I was his teacher. I will have to talk, coz I wont know under what mental agony or status he is reaching out to me, and I will have to counsel him as a former teacher.

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Editorial

Rahu Ketu Transit 26.04.2025 4:20 pm. The Original Holy Trinity of Lord Shiva, The Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy & Lord Kartikeya rise via the Rahu Ketu Transit 26.04.2025 4:20 pm.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916119943361216878>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>*
@Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your
Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi
Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi
@RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai,
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and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate
& @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn

*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

A few minutes before the Rahu Ketu Transit, my bulbs lit up. Rahu transits from Pisces to Kumbh, while Ketu transits from Kanni to Simha.

Incidentally Rahu represents paternal karma and Ketu represents maternal karma in a very nuanced manner.

Recognizing paternity to Lord Shiva and maternity to Ma Bagavathy, the transit can be read as Lord Shiva transiting from Pisces to Kumbh, which can also be read as “from water into the vessel”. Applying to the Shri Ramanathaswamy temple at Rameshwaram, Lord Shiva, has travelled through water and reached our shores, to be more precise, reached the Kumbh on top of the Temple Towers. The Temple towers are incidentally receiver antennas. Since we are setting out to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, who else better than Lord Shiva, to help tap Her for us, by placing Himself on the Kumbh on top of the Temple Towers himself functioning as Receiver Antenna!

Ketu transit from Kanni to Simha, might mean that Ma Bagavathy is transiting from being the Virgin Mother Goddess into the Mother on the Lion, and is arriving. As per tradition, Lord Shiva has to arrive first before Ma Bagavathy to receive Her and has happened so, while Ma Bagavathy starts riding the Lion in Simha, Lord Shiva has travelled through water and reached the Vessel or Kumbh which acts as an antenna to receive Her electromagnetically.

Editorial

Further, as per today's panchang, today is the monthly Shivratri. Shivratri and Kartikeya are deeply connected through divine purpose and cosmic events. Shivratri marks the union of Shiva and Parvati, which was essential for the birth of Kartikeya. So, we can be sure that Lord Kartikeya has also arrived at the Subramaniya Swamy Temple, Tiruchendur.

The Original Holy Trinity of The Father Lord Shiva (Shri Ramanathaswamy Temple, Rameshwaram, The Shakti or the Virgin Goddess Ma Bagavathy (Virgin Goddess temple at Kanya Kumari), and the Son, Lord Kartikeya (Subramaniya Swamy Temple, Tiruchendur) have risen via this Rahu Ketu Transit on 26.04.2025 4:20 pm IST and it only requires us to go and invoke Ma Bagavathy to continuously descend as a Radio Signal (which I shall be humbled to do and give, as per the traditions of my mothers clan), receive via equipment from BSNL and also perform radiation therapy via BSNL for the entire Universe. At a later date, we can establish an international space station for the purpose of healing Alien Civilizations and Parallel Universes (so that all our pitrus may be healed and all our future generations also may be healed).

Let us compare simultaneous events across the World. In another part of the World, in the Christendom, which was using the phrase "Holy Trinity" so far, to refer to a different set of energy forms, is now grieving for 9 days, the death of its Supreme Pontiff, and incidentally, while the above events were taking place in India, the body of the Supreme Pontiff of the Christendom is being laid to rest.

On a different perspective, we don't consider anyone as enemies, but there are some who consider us as enemies and cause unnecessary pain to us, as evidenced in the Pahalgam Terrorist Massacre. Consequently, with the links that emerged and as broadcast via electronic media, Pakistan has lost its moral ground due to the Pahalgam Terrorist Massacre.

In Summary, The Original Holy Trinity of Lord Shiva, The Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy & Lord Kartikeya rise via the Rahu Ketu Transit 26.04.2025 4:20 pm and wait for us.

Also, would it be possible to place three thrones in each of the aforesaid temples in the main hall of the Temple and also in the dining space (we shall be blessed to dine with Them), so that whenever it pleases the Holy Trinity of Lord Shiva, The Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy, and Lord Kartikeya, they can permit us to behold them in physical form – coz as quantum energy forms, they can exist simultaneously in energy form and physical form. They don't need to convert from energy form to physical form or vice versa.

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Editorial

from @DrMohanBhagwat to 8.2 billion coconuts, camphor, lamps & puja materials please – for worship at the Temple -- The Shakti or Ma Bagavathy predates the Big Bang or the Start of the Universe – Pity, Western Scientists are at a loss to comprehend it. Perhaps we may need to accelerate the start of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe !!!

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916473931680113024>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/ZWYNm>

Ref 2: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/techandscience/the-big-bang-may-not-have-been-first-was-dark-matter-already-here/ar-AA1Dh51h?ocid=msedgntp&pc=U531&cvid=e4bc60966fdb4b9a991a7df3abdef315&ei=14>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916119943361216878>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

Today's submission title was revealed to me, but I was still searching for the logical defense. The logical defense came up only as one line, an erroneous definition of God as light, and the consequent trouble of aligning science with spirituality.

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Editorial

In that context, India's spiritual definitions align with science perfectly and hence, we have no difficulty in understanding. Else, if we take this file as a simple explanation, it is being written over a four month period and today is on its 180th page, but the flow has been fluidic and serene, with no jerks.

Quote from Ref 2 "Despite its elusive nature, [dark matter](#) is believed to account for over 80% of all matter in the universe. It doesn't emit or reflect light, making it invisible to traditional instruments, yet its gravitational effects are unmistakable. It bends light, shapes [galaxies](#), and determines how the cosmos evolves over billions of years.

Until now, the origin of dark matter remained purely speculative. Most models placed its formation **after the Big Bang**, within the high-energy soup that followed. The new WIFI hypothesis suggests that these assumptions may be missing a key part of the picture.

If dark matter *did* exist before the Big Bang, it may hold the **key to understanding the universe's earliest moments**, long before time itself—at least as we perceive it—began to tick."

End of Quote.

Lets consider yesterday's submission on the Rahu Ketu Transit as per Vakkiya panchang on 26.04.2025 4:20 pm (listed above as Ref 3). There is synergy between Science and Astrology which is very much evident in Ref 3. This is primarily because, our ancestors have written everything originally. There is no mind game. There is no psychological brain washing. There is no necessity to force any belief on anyone, and hold them enslaved due to that belief that they have accepted, thereby making them part of a system that could silence anyone and create for itself a well managed web of control and authority that is passed on through centuries of secrecy.

So far everything was ok, coz Science did not meet Spirituality. But now, as seen in Ref 2, Science is just touching the periphery of Spirituality, and the western scientists are unable to understand that Dark Matter or Dark Energy, the purest form of matter and the purest form of energy -- which bends light, shapes [galaxies](#), and determines how the cosmos evolves over billions of years – is in fact The Shakti, benevolently manifesting as Ma Bagavathy.

We are on the verge of history, where the Universe will recognize The Shakti / Ma Bagavathy as the pure dark matter/dark energy that bends light, shapes galaxies and determines how the cosmos evolves over billions of years.

Now one simple question, The Shakti / Ma Bagavathy performing such difficult tasks over billions of years – Is it difficult for Her to heal mankind, all life forms, nature, environment, the planet and the Universe and Aliens and Machine Optimization? The answer is quite obvious. Its quite easy for Ma Bagavathy to

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Editorial

The Western Philosophy will not permit the Scientists to understand the dark matter, coz it will go against their narrative of many centuries. So, its only us.

Requesting your esteemed attention to the Call for Unity given by our beloved elder brother @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai, his call will reverberate throughout the World, once we've been blessed to Tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, during which time, there will also be some astronomical phenomena happening in the Universe, observed by Western Scientists and only then they will understand The Shakti or the Ma Bagavathy. And then, extending @DrMohanBhagwat's call for unity, One World, one Temple, one People, one Well, one Graveyard.

We'll have to request a special budget allocation from our beloved elder sister @NSitharaman for purchase of 8.2 billion coconuts, camphor, lamps and puja materials, assuming that the whole world, comes and does puja for Ma Bagavathy aka The Shakti aka the dark energy aka the dark matter. As a quantum energy form, Ma Bagavathy can simultaneously exist as matter and as energy and does not need to convert from energy to mass or vice versa.

At the same time, Gravity will also arrive in various forms, including the Pahalgam Terror Massacre, that will attempt to take away our attention & concentration from the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe. It will be our choice to stand steadfast in our aim to Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga to heal the Universe.

At the same time, I wish to humbly file that the hunt against me was not directly against me but was actually against Ma Bagavathy, as can be evidenced by the innumerable number of funerals, of those, on whom the karma of the hunt fell directly or indirectly, and the high profile resignations. Since everything revolves on the cooperation of Ma Bagavathy for the enormous effort, the hunt against me was just to make Ma Bagavathy compromise and agree to their demands. I lost so much, but I didn't bend down. I didn't compromise Ma Bagavathy. And She stood tall, coz if I, a mere human being, can take so much of hit, but still remain faithful to Ma Bagavathy, as the The Shakti, how much more tall can She stand !. And She did Stand, else, I wont be alive now to write this and send to you. Let us set out in Faith. Ma Bagavathy will help us Search for Her, and help us Tap Her and also help us Heal the Universe through Her. Also, we might be blessed to have food with Her, or even go in line to Her, while She feeds us by Her hand too, coz all of us are Her Children only, however young or old we might be earthly.

<https://youtu.be/DI8UAcINRak?list=RDDI8UAcINRak>

ॐ सर्वेषां स्वस्तिर्भवतु ।
सर्वेषां शान्तिर्भवतु ।

Editorial

सर्वेषां पूर्णभवतु ।

सर्वेषां मङ्गलंभवतु ।

ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥

Om Sarveshaam Svastir-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Shaantir-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Puurnnam-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Manggalam-Bhavatu |

Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantih ||

Meaning:

1: May there be Well-Being in All,

2: May there be Peace in All,

3: May there be Fulfilment in All,

4: May there be Auspiciousness in All,

5: Om Peace, Peace, Peace.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

If Ref 1 is true, then Ref 2 was prevented to be fulfilled & consequently we can assure immortality through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916535431937602010>

Ref 1: <https://youtu.be/QHkWvubxTUY>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913232215162736883> (This Easter Sunday, will His Holiness Pope Francis @Pontifex magnanimously thank Ma Bagavathy & Ma Durga for healing/resurrecting him & rewrite theology due to claims that Jesus Christ body has been found?)

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

If the Ref 1 is true, then Ref 2 was prevented to be fulfilled & consequently we can assure immortality through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy.

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Requesting Govt. of India to please invite the Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars for the International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave under Article 51 A(h) to discuss the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916769339107430692>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/103ptc>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1913605972758827161> (Suggesting International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave since Indian Waqf Amendment Act 2025 is similar to that in many Islamic Nations)

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

Subsequent to latest international developments towards fraternity (Ref 1), it is humbly suggested to the Govt. of India to please invite the Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars to the proposed International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave w.r.t. the Waqf Amendment Act 2025 under Article 51A(h).

Ofcourse, the following situation might also occur, and the Govt. of India may please be prepared to handle it.

The Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars analysis or suggestions, might make the Indian Waqf Amendment Act 2025 more acceptable to the vested groups protesting against the Waqf Amendment Act 2025, for reasons that the suggestions / analysis given by the Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars might be very strict and rigid. Consequently, the vested groups protesting

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against the Waqf Amendment Act 2025 might call for a change in strategy of protest and start conducting street meetings for appreciating the Waqf Amendment Act 2025, and withdraw all cases filed in the Supreme Court of India (against the Waqf Amendment Act 2025), with request to the Supreme Court of India to recommend to the Govt. of India to enforce the Waqf Amendment Act 2025 without any revision or modification that might include the recommendations/analysis of the Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars.

Also, if there any objections to the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita (CrPC), the Govt. of India may be pleased to convene another Diplomatic / Judicial Conclave under Article 51A(h) for revision to the BNSS (CrPC) to include the Sharia Law (through the lens of the Afghan / Taliban Islamic Scholars) to those to whom it can be applied in India.

Govt. of India officials are hereby given statutory warning that heart attack can happen even during times of extreme happiness also (not necessarily under stress alone), and all those who are under risk of heart attack, may please consult your doctors to prepare to handle very emotional moments of extreme happiness, with thanks to the Afghan /Taliban Islamic Scholars and Article 51A(h).

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

You are assured that I wont sell out or betray the Govt. of India for whatsoever reason... Is any very prominent face attempting to trick me into becoming their slave so that they can use the project proposal of Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as a bargaining chip with the Govt. of India?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916913091218149424>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

Is any very prominent face in Tamil Nadu attempting to trick me into becoming their slave so that they can use the project proposal of Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga as a bargaining chip with the Govt. of India?

Why should I be called over phone today night and advised to accept the money on offer (which is on offer for a very long time), which I have declined to accept, unless 30% tax is paid to the Govt of India & tax receipt handed over to me and my bank.

The Karma of hunting me down for decades without realising that they are actually attempting to enslave Ma Bagavathy, is hitting back, and there are huge losses to those that planned and authorised and executed it. At this juncture, when the proposal is handed over to the Govt. of India, along with suggestion for sharing the revenues between the Govt. of India, the temples concerned and the NDA/BJP also with a share to the opposition parties (as per discretion of the NDA or BJP), while I request only a dignified job and a dignified salary from the Govt. of India, are these people so foolish to think that I'll accept the money on offer and become their slave, and jeopardize the divine plans of Ma Bagavathy, over 7000 years post the Mahabharata war in 5561 BCE?

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Editorial

I may not have a job now, I may not have money, I may live on alms, but its ok. Great histories are created only with great sacrifices. And on behalf of my mother's clan, when so many of my ancestors have given up their life for the sake of Ma Bagavathy over so many generations, would I hesitate to sacrifice job or money for Ma Bagavathy?

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

If Ma Bagavathy causes the current Pahalgam conflict to fizzle out from the dangerous war clouds looming over the horizon into a diplomatic chess board, would it please the Govt. of India to construct the world's largest religious worship place aka temple for Ma Bagavathy at Pahalgam with 18 million square feet floor area?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917253417602552029>

Ref1 : <https://dhunt.in/105Lw1>

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Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1915325454736904676>

In humility the following submission please.

If Ma Bagavathy causes the current Pahalgam conflict to fizzle out from the dangerous war clouds looming over the horizon into a diplomatic chess board, would it please the Govt. of India to construct the world's largest religious worship place aka temple for Ma Bagavathy at Pahalgam with 18 million square feet floor area? Ofcourse, it shall be the discretion of the Govt. of India, if it pleases the Govt. of India to build the Ma Bagavathy temple with 108 million square feet floor area also and fit an entire planned city inside the Ma Bagavathy temple too

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Editorial

Pakistan may gift POK to India to request India for help in focussing the benevolent radiations from Ma Bagavathy over its territory to regulate climate via Indian Communication Satellites.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917540052084654527>

Ref: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/world/pakistan-nears-50-degree-celsius-may-break-its-own-world-heat-record>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following communication please.

At the limit of man's ego, man has to turn to God only.

Let me illustrate with an example please.

The past few years, there were many who advised me to accept the money offered and go my own way and not bother whether its white money or black money. I had only one question which I asked today morning over a conversation with a good friend, who'd always say that we have to compromise and go with those who have money. Additional regular argument is "Ok, We are rogues. But we know to make money. We enjoyed the money and the sex and the alcohol. When we have to die, we die". All this is good when spoken under arrogance. Hence, regarding the recent pressure to me to accept the money on offer, which I declined, again the discussion turned towards it. Earlier, I myself didn't have much clarity, coz I take only one step at a time, as guided. I don't shoot farther. Now, I've understood so many things, and I was able

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to ask a counter question. “Ok, they offer money, and I receive the money and hand over the project to them. And if someone very important in their group / organization needs to be healed, they have to beseech Ma Bagavathy only for healing. Of course, Ma Bagavathy may respond. But if these humans who have always given more importance to money than God, invite Ma Bagavathy, She will indeed respond, and also have a question for them “Ok, can u guys tell me how many women u kidnapped from the road in broad day light? How many girls you guys raped? How many people’s families u destroyed? How many people’s bread u spoilt? How many people’s lives u spoilt? And on top of it, u want me to come and heal ur guys after having committed so much sin on the planet and also got away with everything? Why not stuff some currency notes into the mouths of ur guys and wait for them to be healed, coz u guys gave importance only to money than God?” I asked my friend, will they have any answer for Ma Bagavathy? My friend didn’t expect such a counter question, and the discussion paused for the moment.

Similarly, our dear brothers in Pakistan, have been wronging India for quite a considerable amount of time, forgetting that, prior to the British colonisation, all of us were one family only. And it does take only political will to erase all borders between India and Pakistan and live together in peace. Of course, they might have their own defenses for their actions to cover up the financial benefits they accrued for wronging India, but unfortunately, as in example discussed above, they cant go to Ma Bagavathy, asking Her to regulate the climate and give for them, coz 50 degrees Celsius, is too difficult for a population that hasn’t got acclimatized to such high temperatures, and no artificial regulation for a whole population will be feasible too. So, at the end, they have to appeal to God only. So far, in the world, there has been no other proposal to tap into the electromagnetic radiation of God to heal everything, in total. Consequently, they have to approach the Govt. of India only. No point in approaching me, coz I wont sell out the Govt. of India. So, Pakistan will have to approach the Govt. of India only. And before approaching the Govt. of India, Pakistan will have to hand over POK to India, so that the discussions at the table will be pleasant. Also, Pakistan will have to restrain terrorists from using its soil to train or organize or launch attacks against India. Then only they can come to the table.

Of course, if it pleases the Govt. of India, we can initiate the activity to Search and Apply the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy from the earlier suggested temples of the Original Holy Trinity of Kumari Bagavathy Amman Temple in Kanya Kumari, the Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram and the Subramanya Swamy Temple in Tiruchendur.

Let us wait until the Jupiter Transition into Mithuna, an air sign in a few days. Jupiter in Mithuna, will fan the flames of motherly affection in Ma Bagavathy, and she may rush to be received by us. And we can request Her to be benevolent to our brothers and sisters in

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Pakistan, and help regulate their climate so that they don't have to suffer the harsh 50 degree Celsius.

And all will be well, and we can start the 18 million square feet temple or 108 million square feet temple for Ma Bagavathy in Pahalgam, and invite all people in the world, and all aliens in our Universe and parallel Universes to come and worship Ma Bagavathy in Her new Temple at Pahalgam.

And wait, a dozen Nobel prizes too, for the effort of the Search & Application of the Radio/UV Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe.

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Thanks to the Secretary & Officials @MOMAIndia & Thanks to the Secretary Dept. of Posts, Ministry of Communications Govt of India

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and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and Thanks to the Secretary & Officials @MOMAIndia &
Thanks to the Secretary Dept. of Posts, Ministry of Communications Govt of India for Petition
U/s 151 CPC which has got potential to expose the web of local and international players,
ofcourse, this may just be the fuse that could possibly lead to a goldmine of PMLA in real
estate, coz the same players involved here might also be involved elsewhere in bigger pursuits.

I'm humbled that the pain that I endured will soon result in a greater benefit for the Nation.

Jai Hind !!!

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Editorial

A hypothetical comparison between the ITER and the low voltage high frequency electricity that can be generated using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy (apart from healing the Universe).

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917889794677625072>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1892810142732718357>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following communication please.

Its still a matter of concern whether we can propose to generate electricity from the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy. Apart from healing the Universe, it was suggested that we can also generate electricity using RF excitation based electricity generators (Ref 1). The ITER may be a green electricity generator which can be used for conventional electrical applications, but the electricity generated from the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, may have a low voltage high frequency characteristic, which may make it suitable for wireless power transfer, electric vehicles, Telecom, and semiconductor related processes (ofcourse yet to be generated and validated). We may not be able to power homes and industrial houses with conventional lighting, but we may be able to power homes and industrial houses with low power devices.

The ITER may be able to provide electricity as much as demanded, but the electricity produced from the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, may be limited, and also open up new avenues for International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

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research & industrial activity in the area of low power devices, allowing newer applications and newer technologies in low power.

In short, will Ma Bagavathy be pushing us into designing new systems and new applications for the present and the future, which may take out the Einsteinian constant “C” from our design equations, and consequently provide us the freedom for intergalactic travel?

Perhaps, the ITER may serve the present, while the electricity from the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy may serve the future...

We will have to experiment, explore and understand.

May Ma Bagavathy bless us in our journey.

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Editorial

Goodness, Have u scared them out of their wits 🤖 U'd have transcript if u've tapped my phone please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917964260208201924>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following communication please.

Received a call from someone known for quite a long time.

The topic turned to the 151 CPC filed by the Department of Posts.

I gave my interpretation that this may be just the fuse. and it may lead to the huge real estate
stash of vested groups, which might be taken over by the Govt.

The way in which conversation was taken further, it looked like an attempt to convince me that
a share is being given to the Govt. of India, so they wont look any further.

My argument was very simple. The Govt. of India doesn't have to accept the left overs that u
give them, If they have to confiscate everything, they will do it.

Argument became so heated that i had to hang up the phone.

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And a friendly conversation with someone else, i was suggested that the Govt. of India might have gone to a place where they never expected a visit from the Govt. of India, and they might be scared, and perhaps this reaction is due to that.

Whatever might have happened, the Govt. of India still has the capacity to scare the wrong doers out of their wits, and make them go insane. And that is quite amusing.

Thank u Govt. of India. You made my day 😊

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In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Yet another consideration for a Dean Research position via another University. You are assured that the rights of the research & the revenues will belong primarily to the Govt. of India. If it pleases the Govt. of India, a portion of the revenues may please be shared with the University in future.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1918275518132277396>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>* @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity, Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn & @Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula AnnaGaru

In humility the following submission please.

A long time ago, when I hadn't realised that I was being hunted only for the rights of the proposed research of the "Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe", I had been applying to Universities and Colleges for a suitable academic/research position.

Was pleasantly surprised that today morning, I received a reply, after a very long time, indicating that my candidature has been shortlisted and I need to submit details in a specified format. The conversation with the HR in the evening was also pleasant. Only then I realized that the Univ. should not get the notion that the rights and revenues of the project proposed as an independent proposal without affiliation to any University, will not get tagged to the Univ. (once I'm offered the Dean Research position and I join in service subsequently) which might have potential to make the Govt. of India dependent on the University for the project.

to: "Prof. Dr. Prabhu Britto Albert"
<editor@ijbst.org>

date: May 2, 2025, 5:13 AM

Editorial

subject: Re: Application for Dean
Research/Engineering/Academics

Consequently, this communication please, which will also be copied to the University, so that they are also aware that the primary rights will rest only with the Govt. of India, though the University will stand to benefit on many other counts. Further, if it pleases the Govt. of India, a portion of the revenues from the project may also be shared to the University please. I'm not sharing the name of the University now, so that those anti-nationals don't find their way to the Univ. at this point of time.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMSNL

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Editorial

Is Pakistan benevolently nudging us towards the suggested 18/108 million square feet temple at Pahalgam, for the victory in the war that we never fought, but which victory was served to us on a plate?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1918641377522372842>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/MeghUpdates/status/1918335032973729852>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/ANI/status/1918551819992666510>

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917253417602552029> (If Ma Bagavathy causes the current Pahalgam conflict to fizzle out from the dangerous war clouds looming over the horizon into a diplomatic chess board, would it please the Govt. of India to construct the world's largest religious worship place aka temple for Ma Bagavathy at Pahalgam with 18 million square feet floor area?)

Ref 4: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing> (Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe)

Ref 5: <https://dhunt.in/108LbZ>

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In humility the following submission please.

A brief look at the references cited above leads us to only one question

Is Pakistan benevolently nudging us towards the suggested 18/108 million square feet temple at Pahalgam, for the victory in the war that we never fought, but which victory was served to

Editorial

us on a plate, just for our intention to tap the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and heal the Universe?

All these days, we talked about good and bad karma. But now, Ma Bagavathy is pushing us to another level, where our thoughts shape reality. We wanted to do good, and She is helping us to move to a position to do good. With so much music related to Pakistan, it will be difficult for the Govt. of India to concentrate on the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Universe. So, is She Herself, solving things, so that we will go ahead with our good intentions to heal the Universe through Her !

<https://youtu.be/DI8UAcINRak?list=RDDI8UAcINRak>

ॐ सर्वेषां स्वस्तिर्भवतु ।

सर्वेषां शान्तिर्भवतु ।

सर्वेषां पूर्णभवतु ।

सर्वेषां मङ्गलंभवतु ।

ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥

Om Sarveshaam Svastir-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Shaantir-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Puurnnam-Bhavatu |

Sarveshaam Manggalam-Bhavatu |

Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantih ||

Meaning:

1: May there be Well-Being in All,

2: May there be Peace in All,

3: May there be Fulfilment in All,

4: May there be Auspiciousness in All,

5: Om Peace, Peace, Peace.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMSNL

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Editorial

The looming Global Recession: Ma Bagavathy's Blessing in Disguise for India for expansion into radiation therapy and low power high frequency devices and technologies for the present & the future.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919006743721382285>

Ref 1: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/f983c12d-d43c-4e41-997e-252ec6b87dbd/content>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1917889794677625072> (A hypothetical comparison between the ITER and the low voltage high frequency electricity that can be generated using the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy - apart from healing the Universe).

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>*
@Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your
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& @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn &
@Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula AnnaGaru

In humility the following submission please.

Quote from Ref 1: "Developing economies should have no illusions about the struggle ahead: the next 25 years will be a tougher slog than the last 25. A fresh game plan is needed—one that strengthens their capacity to fend for themselves and seize growth opportunities wherever they can be found. With the right policies, some challenges can be turned into opportunities. Given their tighter trade links with one another, developing economies can reap significant rewards by accelerating reforms to attract investment and deepen trade and investment ties with these economies. They can also accelerate growth by modernizing infrastructure, improving human capital, and speeding up the climate transition." End of Quote from Ref 1

Now let us read Ref 2, with the above paragraph in mind. It will seem to us that the initiative of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy in healing the Universe,

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accompanied with its allied application in low power high frequency devices & technologies may be the fresh needed game plan. This will strengthen our capacity to fend for ourselves and seize growth opportunities wherever they can be found. However, we may need to make some right policies to accommodate for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy in healing the Universe, accompanied with its allied application in low power high frequency devices & technologies.

One such policy might be to include the Govt. of India as a co-applicant in all patents, copyrights, trademarks, etc. so that the Govt. will have freedom to rope in the revenues and find new use for the revenues in much needed sectors.

With the right policies, some challenges can be turned into opportunities – this can be applied to the latest Pahalgam Massacre and the aftermath of it too. It was indeed a great challenge, with cries for revenge from multiple quarters. But the Govt. of India, though it had to enhance military preparedness in the case of an impending conflict, still chose not to retaliate with a military onslaught, but exercised restraint, holding onto precious moral ground, and in return, there are some nations, that are standing with India, as old friends, and also some more nations, standing with India as new friends. Pahalgam was a big challenge to India, but the Govt. of India changed it into an opportunity to assert its position as a Global leader, standing on moral ground, and rallying other nations to stand with it, which can also have potential in the future for better trade and other agreements, opening up new opportunities in international trade, business and regional and international security.

“Given their tighter trade links with one another, developing economies can reap significant rewards by accelerating reforms to attract investment and deepen trade and investment ties with these economies. They can also accelerate growth by modernizing infrastructure, improving human capital, and speeding up the climate transition” Read together with the initiative to Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, accompanied with the allied application in low power high frequency devices and technologies, India can, if it pleases the Govt. of India, strengthen the Niti Aayog and the Technology Business Incubators to concentrate on radiation detection & therapy equipment and low power high frequency devices and technologies.

If it pleases the Govt. to share a portion of the revenues with the Universities that participate in this huge mammoth effort, it will also help the Universities to expand their infrastructure and their research footprint, not only in SCI and other related metrics, but also give out some real solutions & prototypes that can revolutionize the technologies of the future, for the World, and the Universe at large too.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India

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<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919447099097424112>

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*Addressed to the next Pope please

In humility the following submission please.

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Narration of forward is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <hshso@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: May 5, 2025, 3:20 PM

subject:Fwd: Yet another consideration for a Dean Research position via another University. You are assured that the rights of the research & the revenues will belong primarily to the Govt. of India. If it pleases the Govt. of India, a portion of the revenues may please be shared with the University in future.

mailed-by: nic.in

signed-by: nic.in

Shall be humbled to copy this communication to the concerned Univ. that offered the Dean Research position shortlisting, so that it will be convenient for them please.

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Editorial

Translating thoughts into Quantum Reality: Classrooms of Ma Bagavathy – Blessed are we that Ma Bagavathy chose us as Her Students, helping us to learn via “Live” Case Studies.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919468578505420845>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/10aS87> (திருந்துகிறதா பாகிஸ்தான்? இறந்த பயங்கரவாதிக்கு இறுதிச்சடங்கு செய்ய மதகுருக்கள் மறுப்பு..!)

Ref 2: <https://dhunt.in/10btH1> (Video: போர் வந்தாலும் ராணுவத்திற்கு ஆதரவில்லை; பாக்., மக்களின் மனநிலை இதுதான்!)

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919006743721382285> (The looming Global Recession: Ma Bagavathy’s Blessing in Disguise for India for expansion into radiation therapy and low power high frequency devices and technologies for the present & the future.)

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Editorial

In humility the following submission please:

At the intersection of Consciousness and Quantum Physics lies the concept of “translating thoughts into a quantum reality”. The basis of this concept are the theories that our thoughts and emotions influence reality at a sub-atomic level, similar to the observer effect on quantum particles.

Viewing through perspectives of Quantum Mechanics, Reality exists in a state of probabilities until observed, which means that the focussed intention could shape outcomes. This aligns with concepts like manifestation and the observer effect, where attention collapses possibilities into tangible experiences.

Of course, the above references would have been viewed by many, over many perspectives. But only when viewed through the attention towards the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, our attention collapses the possibilities into a tangible experience, and that tangible experience is awesome, from the viewpoint that “Translating thoughts into Quantum Reality: Classrooms of Ma Bagavathy – Integrated PhD Degree Program in Quantum Sciences – Blessed are we that Ma Bagavathy chose us as Her Students, helping us to learn via “Live” Case Studies.”

Now, let us view the above references through the view point of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe.

First, we will need unity. Expanding Ref 1, when Islamic Scholars / Religious heads refuse to perform the final rites for fallen terrorists, where will it lead to? It may lead to severe disillusionment of terrorists that they are actually embarking on a journey of terrorism, for their own religion. Now, when their own religious heads refuse to do the final rites for fallen terrorists, the glory of laying down life as a terrorist is taken away from them, and consequently, the number of recruits to terrorism will start dwindling day by day, and there may come a sunrise, when a terrorist can be seen only in the museum, standing beside a dinosaur.

Second, what happens in case of an accidental war. Expanding Ref 2, when the people don't support the military in the event of a war, for what reason, should the military wage a war, suffer a lot of bloodshed and lives, to return home, with no glory, no fame, no repute? Again, this will cause disillusionment in the military and discourage them from engaging or starting an armed conflict.

Next, there has to be scope for improvement, so that there can be some real explorative research and industrial expansion, so that people will be busy in some new exploit that keeps them busy. The attraction of low power high frequency devices and related technologies will be quite attractive, for reasons of the inherent challenges and the prospective global financial

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Editorial

returns in introducing a set of new technologies that has got potential to replace all current technologies. So everyone will forget about all quarrels and conflicts, and it will become sort of a gold rush of the yester years.

Now, let us go back to where we started? We wanted to heal the Planet & the Universe, for reasons that its gone beyond repair and only The Shakti can heal everything, for reasons that only the Creator knows where and how things can be healed. So, we landed on the Ma Bagavathy, a benevolent form of the Ma Bagavathy. It was easy to understand and state that we can attempt to search and obtain the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Universe, for the reason that Ma Bagavathy Herself will help us to tap Her and apply Her to heal the Universe. But there were many situations and environments and ambiences that need to fall in place, for things to go good as expected. And slowly, we find that there is change; change that fits one perspective, of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe. If we view events from a different perspective, the possibilities will not collapse into a reality via a tangible experience, but if we view it from the perspective of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, we can appreciate that the possibilities collapse into a reality via a tangible experience. We can feel it happening, by its own unique myriad ways, ushering us into a quantum reality, where the World will have no option, other than standing united with us, in our Search & Application for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, with allied application in low power high frequency devices and technologies of the future, including but not limited to computation, wireless electricity, telecom, and intergalactic travel (along with it, mining of precious minerals from distant galaxies)

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International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

Sufficiency of Constitution of India / Requirement of UN Referendum for grant of accession request of friendly population in hostile territory, in case Pakistan collapses on implosion !!!

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919826190132482229>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/10cxJr> ("நாங்கள் பாகிஸ்தானில் வசித்தாலும் போரில் இந்தியாவுக்கு தான் ஆதரவு கொடுப்போம்". அதிரடியாக அறிவித்த மதகுரு. வைரலாகும் வீடியோ!!!)

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing> (Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, with allied application in low power high frequency devices and technologies)

Ref 3: <https://www.livemint.com/economy/pakistan-crisis-heres-four-reasons-why-cash-strapped-economy-is-under-global-scrutiny-11728750660302.html>

Ref 4: <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2024/6/12/is-pakistans-crisis-ridden-economy-finally-recovering>

Ref 5: <https://www.indiatoday.in/business/story/indo-pak-tension-pakistan-economic-crisis-impact-trade-cancellation-india-pahalgam-attack-2716763-2025-04-29>

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In humility the following submission please:

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Since the moment the proposal for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, with allied application in low power high frequency devices and technologies was started to getting drafted, there have been so many things happening topsy turvy inclusive of unlikely events happening too. One such event is reported in Ref 1. India seems to be gaining the support of Islamic Scholars and the people there.

Now, read together with Pakistan's economic woes as illustrated in Ref 3-5 supported by a host of relevant online literature, it does paint a grim picture for Pakistan.

Lets move the scale to the most unlikely event and assess our preparedness for it. If its war, we retaliate in a controlled manner, to minimise civilian casualty. If its diplomatic manoeuvres, still, we retaliate as suitable. Assuming that the Nation of Pakistan implodes and ceases to exist, are we prepared to handle it? Who will guarantee the safety and lives and livelihood of the people there?

Is the Constitution of India sufficient to grant guarantees of safety to life and livelihood of the friendly people in hostile territory, if their Nation ceases to exist? Or will we require the people to complete accession formalities into the Union of India or will there be a necessity of a UN Referendum?

When we are so patient with the aftermath of the Pahalgam Terror Massacre, we will have to be equally or more patient with the friendly people in hostile territory, if Pakistan ceases to exist as a Nation, collapsing inwardly due to internal pressures.

Consequently, if it pleases the Govt. of India, the above topic of concern may also be brainstormed at suitable levels of authority, so that we don't let anyone down, and that includes that we don't let anyone down, even if they are a friendly population in a hostile territory.

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Editorial

And the baits come in person too, travelling 319 kms too 😊

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920336692919091563>

Ref: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920011878442664007>

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& @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn &
@Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula Anna Garu

In humility the following submission please.

Today morning, they avoided my phone and sent a former Colleague of mine, who was then
Dean MBA.

He was supposed to be at Bangalore but pretended he ran into me on my morning walk and
called to my phone, claiming that he crossed me a minute ago (If they were trying to avoid my
phone coz it could have been tapped by the Govt., again they made the mistake of calling me,
just to claim that they crossed me while walking). Incidentally, I'm resuming my morning walk
today, after a gap of 4 days, coz I've been down with fever and dehydration. Of course, he was
at the race course Coimbatore only. He prompted me to know the entire story, but had only few
questions. 1. Why don't u rejoin Vinayaka missions univ? 2. Did this project concept arise in u
while u were working in Vinayaka missions univ? 3. What do u plan to do?

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Editorial

My answers

1. They were reaching out through some middlemen upto a few months ago, but everything was too fishy without proper procedures. How can I go and rejoin in the same position after so many years, after having been relieved and accounts closed without any new procedure to reinitiate proceedings for induction? Too many fishy things. So I declined to rejoin Vinayaka Missions Univ.

2. No. The project concept revealed itself to me only very recently and it's evidenced by frequent short submissions to the Govt of India. Further updates done to the word file on my cloud storage and revisions to pdf file bear evidence of date. Maybe everybody knew that my mother's clan was carrying some grace capable of bringing the dead back to life, but nobody even breathed a word to me. But they all hit me, when I didn't even know why I was getting hit and it took more than 8 to 10 years for me to decode why I was hit, and what asset was I safeguarding. The moment I realised who the players were, I made a diametric move towards my mother's religion prior to her marriage to my father, coz if that was a blessing from my mother's clan it should find its rightful place only. Consequently, I moved in with the Govt of India, ie the BJP and that upset the entire chessboard, coz they never expected that I'd give equal importance to my mother's religion too, inspite of my mother converting to Christianity on her wedding to my father.

3. No plans at all. Even yesterday, there was a bait for Bharathiyar univ vice chancellor position. I didn't take it up. I've given my word to the Govt of India currently run by the BJP. I go with them. They will provide a dignified job to me, as requested by me in the project proposal. All project revenues go to them, while I take home a dignified salary from the job that they give me.

On a lighter note, if they are constantly trying to trick me into joining hands with them, they may force the Govt of India to assign personnel with electronic recording & transmission facilities monitoring my whereabouts 24 x 7 or I myself may offer myself for 24 x 7 monitoring by the Govt. of India (in fact, I've just done that 😊 Now its upto the Govt. of India to monitor me 24 x 7. If the Govt. of India wants to wire me also, with electronic surveillance equipment, I shall be willing to be wired too).

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Editorial

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Editorial

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Narration of redirection is as follows please:

from: Presidentofindia@rb.nic.in Secretariat <presidentofindia@nic.in> via nic.in

to: <secy.dhe@nic.in>

cc: <editor@ijbst.org>

date: May 8, 2025, 10:52 AM

subject: Fwd: Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretary & Officials @MOMAIndia & Thanks to the Secretary Dept. of Posts, Ministry of Communications Govt of India and Thanks to the Secretaries a.

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United Nations
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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

Shall be humbled to copy this communication to the concerned Univ. that offered the Dean Research position shortlisting, so that it will be convenient for them please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Satya Yug – via Ma Bagavathy aka The Shakti in 2025 AD itself, without the need to wait for 426874 AD through Metaphysical & Scientific parallels

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920438501444600005>

Ref 1: <https://dhunt.in/10daQk> (இந்தியா ஆன்மீக பூமி.. அழிக்க நினைத்தால் நாம் தாம் அழிந்துவிடுவோம்: அரசுக்கு எதிராக பாகிஸ்தான் மக்கள் கொந்தளிப்பு..!)

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRvshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing> (Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe with allied application in low power high frequency devices and technologies)

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope < Apostolica Sedes Vacans>* @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamAlTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn & @Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula Anna Garu & @dpradhanbjp Bhai & The Secretary & Officials at @EduMinOfIndia

In humility the following submission please.

The British partitioning of India in 1947 was done more on demographic basis, instead of resource basis.

Now, perhaps could be the time to undo the partition of 1947 and unite the Nation.

Assuming that the news in the cited reference is true, let us take a more patient approach towards Pakistan. As reflected in Operation Sindoor, Pakistan is not treated as an enemy nation, while only the terrorists operating on Pakistani soil are treated as enemies.

It may require more critical analysis and planning to eliminate the terrorists getting trained in Pakistan or operating on Pakistani Soil.

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Editorial

We may have to wait and strike.

But at the same time, if there is a possibility of undoing the partition of 1947, lets also give some thought to it.

The Ancestors of the current Muslims of Pakistan have been the Hindus of India once upon a time, and they will also bear the chromosomal patterns of their ancestors.

Since the beginning of Ref 2, we have been noticing strange consciousness activation that has been beneficial to India.

Perhaps we have caused the Consciousness of Ma Bagavathy to activate, ushering in Satya Yug directly as The Shakti, which also empowers the Kalki Avatar? The Kalki Avatar also has to depend on the Shakti only for energizing, and if Ma Bagavathy herself as The Shakti intervenes, then we don't have to wait for the Kalki Avatar.

Let me try to illustrate it with a very simple example. At home, if the Mother says its breakfast time, it is breakfast time, irrespective of whether its 7 am or 8 am or 9 am. On a different parallel, at the level of the Universe, the Mother is The Shakti, aka Ma Bagavathy. If She says its Satya Yug time, then, who's going to appeal against it, in the entire Universe?

Now, on a different metaphysical and scientific parallel, when we have thought about the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, we have invoked the Consciousness of Ma Bagavathy, and it only requires Her own dictum, to declare that Satya Yug starts in 2025 AD, from the formal start of the project in the temples at Kanyakumari, Rameshwaram & Tiruchendur. Perhaps, the aforesaid event in Ref 1 and other beneficial events are just a prelude.

Its also good that the Pahalgam conflict has started now. The benefit that is foreseen is that, when the exofficio visitor H.E. The President of India, the exofficio Secretary H.E. The Prime Minister of India, the exofficio Convenor H.E. The Home Minister of India along with a host of religious heads declare open the start of the project to Search & Apply the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe at the temples in Kanyakumari, Rameshwaram and Tiruchendur, we can be sure that there will be a heavy military, air and naval presence, to prevent any unwarranted hostile attack. On a different parallel, this will be quite beneficial for the reason that, apart from BSNL Radio Detectors, the military, air and naval Radio detectors will also be active during deployment for safety.

Further, we can also request Russian Radio Detectors to be pressed into service, in the form of Russian Fleets & Russian Sonar Detectors in the form of Russian Nuclear Submarines that might arrive on a friendly visit at the same time.

In short, we will have a full spectrum visibility in such a case, which will be quite beneficial. Requesting that the Principal Investigator orders issued to me, may please be issued as holding diplomatic rank and honorary military rank, so that it will be convenient for me to access

Editorial

restricted military spaces and discuss with Indian and Russian Military Attachees & Military Officials.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Congratulations Pope Leo XIV @Pontifex. We look forward to your active support and camaraderie in the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe. May Ma Bagavathy bless you in the new Papal responsibilities that you undertake.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920535208123637774>

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In humility the following submission please.

Congratulations Pope Leo XIV. We look forward to your active support and camaraderie in the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe. There may be very many delicate situations in the pursuit of it, due to the truths of the Universe revealing themselves, which may or may not agree with the beliefs of the Catholicism. But, for the sake of the good that we attempt to do for the Universe, let us continue in fraternity. May Ma Bagavathy bless you in the new Papal responsibilities that you undertake.

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Cultural Organization

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15126889>

Editorial

OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Requesting Static Radio Interference Data in forward locations of Operation Sindhoor please.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920544510678880386>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope Leo XIV @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamALTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn & @Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula Anna Garu & @dpradhanbjp Bhai & The Secretary & Officials at @EduMinOfIndia

In humility the following submission please.

Had a faint feeling that the benevolent Consciousness of Ma Bagavathy that has already got awakened and guided into our scientific temperament that we can heal the Universe through the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy has already manifested in forward locations of Operation Sindhoor.

We were earlier guided to the Temples at Kanyakumari, Rameshwaram and Tiruchendur, for the reason that the signal intensity might be maximum at that point of time. But now that the Pahalgam massacre has taken place and Operation Sindhoor has also commenced, Ma Bagavathy might have manifested in forward locations of the battlefield for the primary reason that, as The Shakti, She remains the Mother of the Universe, irrespective of whether people accept Her as such, or declare Her as such or vouch for Her as such. She continues, as the Mother of the Universe, unaffected by the whims and fancies and worldly dominance programs of people.

She may be sitting and weeping at the bloodshed on either side of the border. As far as Ma Bagavathy is concerned, it doesn't matter to Her, whether we are Indian or Pakistani, for whether we are Indian or whether we are Pakistani, She is a Mother to us, and we are all Her Children only. What else can a Mother do, when Her Children are killing each other? Each group may have their own defenses and their own ethical and moral arguments, but whatever be the case, both Indians and Pakistanis are Her Children only. And in Her grief, the Healing

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Editorial

Energies may be more dominant in Her Radiation, which could originally be a combination of Creation, Healing, Restoration Energies, etc.

Consequently requesting H.E. The Defence Minister @RajnathSingh Bhai for Static Radio Interference Data in forward locations of Operation Sindhoor please, especially near Field hospitals and temples please. Also, if possible, geospatial coordinates of locations from where the Static Radio Interference may be projected to be originating please. Also, if possible, a recording on convenient electronic media or hard disks, the Static Radio Interference Data please.

We can use these Static Radio Interference Data as a comparison signal when investigating for the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy in the Temples at Kanyakumari, Rameshwaram and Tiruchendur please.

Also, if it pleases the Govt. of India to issue me my Principal Investigator Orders, I shall be humbled to be taken to those forward locations where the Static Radio Interference Data is being obtained please. Also, I shall be humbled to beam the same signals for healing on volunteer population also please, via Military Radio Transmission Equipment itself, as per availability. Kindly provide a Professor of Radiology & an expert from the Indian Atomic Energy Commission for consultation please.

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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OR

<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJV0J3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

(Bilingual -- In English and Tamil) For the sake that my mother's clan served in the then Mahabharata war in Oct 16, 5561 BCE, healing the wounded and giving life to the fallen, and for the sake that I have to heal and give life to the wounded and the fallen in the next Mahabharata war (May 30, 2025) is the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy seated at the left hand of Lord Shiva, standing as God, Mother and Devi and Devima and the kittens (coz people will get scared if She comes in as lions) safeguarding my life?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920804093821415443>

Ref 1: <https://youtu.be/fRFlwAS87rg> (published a few days ago) (New DNA Study Reveals a 7,000-Year-Old War in Ancient India)

Ref 2: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8cmLqqwjW-afXRvshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope Leo XIV @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamALTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn & @Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula Anna Garu & @dpradhanbjp Bhai & The Secretary & Officials at @EduMinOfIndia

In humility the following submission please.

அன்றைய மகாபாரத போரில் (October 16, 5561 BCE), வீழ்ந்தவர்களையும் மாண்டவர்களையும் குணப்படுத்தியும் உயிர் கொடுத்தும் எம் அன்னையின் குலம் தொண்டாற்றியதால் தானோ, இன்றைய மகாபாரத போரில் (May 30, 2025) வீழ்ந்தவர்களையும் மாண்டவர்களையும் குணப்படுத்துவதற்காகவும் உயிர் கொடுப்பதற்காகவும், எம் அப்பன் ஈசனின் இடப்பக்கம் வீற்று இருக்கும் பராசக்தியாகிய அன்னை உமையவள், பகவதி என்றும் பெயர் உடையவள், தெய்வமாகவும் தாயாகவும்

Editorial

தேவியாகவும் தேவிமா ஆகவும், இல்லத்தில் விளையாடி கொண்டு இருக்கும் பூனை குட்டிகளாகவும் (ஏன் எனில் சிங்கமாக வந்தால், மக்கள் பயந்து விடுவார்கள் அல்லவா?) நின்று எம் உயிரை காத்து கொண்டு இருக்கிறாளோ? எம் வாக்கிக்கிற்கும் கட்டுண்டு நிற்கிறாளோ? இதனுடைய சீரற்ற மாதிரி தான், அன்று போப்பாண்டவர் பிரான்சிஸ் உயிர் பெற்று எழுந்து வந்தாரோ? மீண்டும் ஒரு சீரற்ற மாதிரியாக பகவதிக்கு நன்றி கூற விருப்பமில்லாமல் மாண்டும் சென்றாரோ? இதற்காகத்தான், எம்மை இத்தனை வருடங்களாக அழிக்க முயற்சித்தவர்கள், பல்கலைக்கழக புல முதல்வர் பதவியையும் பல்கலைக்கழக துணை வேந்தர் பதவியையும் தூண்டிலாக தொங்க விட்டு, எம்மை அடிமைப்படுத்த முயல்கிறார்களோ? ஏன் என்றால், இன்றைய மத்திய அரசின் படைகள் மற்றும் குடிமக்களில், அடுத்த மகாபாரத போரில் எம் அன்னை உமையவளாகிய பகவதியின் அருளுடன் வீழ்ந்தவர்களையும் மாண்டவர்களையும் குணப்படுத்த அல்லது மீண்டும் உயிர் கொடுக்க யாம் இருக்க கூடாது என்று முயல்கிறார்களோ? பகவதியின் கதிர் இயக்கங்களை அறிவியல் பூர்வமாக பெற்று குணப்படுவதற்கும் உயிர் கொடுப்பதற்கும் நேரம் நெருங்கி விட்டது. மத்திய அரசு விழித்து கொள்ளுமா அதற்குள்? இப்பொழுதே 200 பக்கங்கள் ஆகிவிட்டது. ஆயிரமாயிரம் பக்கங்கள் அன்னை பகவதியின் பெயரில் எழுதி தர யாம் தயார். அதனை வாசிக்க நீங்கள் உயிருடன் இருப்பீர்களா?

For the sake that my mother's clan served in the then Mahabharata war in Oct 16, 5561 BCE, healing the wounded and giving life to the fallen, and for the sake that I have to heal and give life to the wounded and the fallen in the next Mahabharata war (May 30, 2025) is the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy seated at the left hand of Lord Shiva, standing as God, Mother and Devi and Devima safeguarding my life? And is it for the same reason that the Shakti is also standing true to the word uttered by me? Did Pope Francis come out of hospital alive (Defenses in previous sections of Ref 2) as a random sample of this? Also, did he also die, refusing to thank Ma Bagavathy for the gift of resurrection to him, again as a random sample (also discussed in previous sections of Ref 2)?

Is it for the same reason that they are hanging out baits as Dean and Vice Chancellor positions to enslave me to them, so that I wont be available to heal or resurrect the wounded or the fallen among the current Govt of India's soldiers or civilians?

The time has neared to tap the Radiation of Ma Bagavathi scientifically and use it to heal the wounded and give life to the dead. Will the Govt of India wake up before that?

Its already crossed 200 pages. I'm willing to sit and write thousands of pages for the sake of Ma Bagavathy. But will u be alive to sit and read it?

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Editorial

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Editorial

Since the 1st Mahabharata War in Oct 16, 5561 BCE should have been a religious war, the next Mahabharata war should also be a religious war only, though none of the self-proclaimed saints will call it a religious war, just to maintain their pseudo moral ground

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1921538342400716839>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920804093821415443>

Ref 2: <https://youtu.be/fRFlwAS87rg> (published a few days ago) (New DNA Study Reveals a 7,000-Year-Old War in Ancient India)

Ref 3: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert> (Ancient Egypt bombshell as 'Jesus Christ's body found' in hidden chamber, claims expert)

Ref 4: <https://thecommunemag.com/sexual-abuse-in-churches-a-global-issue-of-systematic-cover-ups-and-silenced-victims-26-instances/>

Ref 5: <https://www.nato.int/docu/speech/2007/s070301a-e.html> (NATO: Defence of security and shared values Speech by NATO Secretary General Jaap de Hoop Scheffer at the Grandes conférences catholiques)

Ref 6: <https://www.timesnownews.com/world/asia/turkey-sends-warship-to-pakistan-days-after-pahalgam-terror-attack-article-151567174>

Ref 7: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_110496.htm (Nato Collective defence and Article 5)

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In humility the following submission please.

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Editorial

The Govt. of India might have had a doubt why so many religious heads are invited to the table for discussion for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe. Wouldn't it have been sufficient if the authorities of the Govt. of India alone are invited to the table for discussion?

Well, I also had the same doubt, but followed as I was guided. Now when we discuss this topic, everyone would know why, as a tradition, all religious heads are invited to the table for discussion, since the first submission regarding the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe.

Lets start from the topic title itself and lets see if we can find any thread of connectivity to the present.

The date might be the first key. Around 5561 BCE, monotheistic religions may not have been established, and some form of polytheism should have been prevalent accompanied with some form of worship of deities.

At the same time in India, Hinduism was a way of life, accompanied with some good religious works across the vast expanse of the Indian subcontinent, including Tamil Nadu.

Now, with due respect to Ref 1, let us assume that healing of the wounded and resurrection of the fallen soldiers should have been the wildcard that helped the Pandavas win the First Mahabharata war of 5561 BCE, then certainly the whole world would have been amazed at healing and resurrection carried out on the armies of the Pandavas. Here, we need to remember that the 1st Mahabharata war, was not a family feud as metaphorically recorded in the Mahabharata epic but rather a global nuclear war, which could have been labelled as a family feud, applying "Vasudhaiva Kudumbagam", and each character in the epic is not an individual but a philosophical connotation. Any further details on the 1st Mahabharata war being a global nuclear war may please be had from Ref 2.

So the healing and resurrection witnessed in the Pandava armies in the 1st Mahabharata war in 5561 BCE may have been the obsessive push to create the narrative in Christianity around the healing offered by Jesus Christ and the resurrection of Jesus Christ. Now, here comes a question which the Church has avoided answering. If Ref 3 is correct, then the Church has to bear the responsibility that they peddled a fake narrative on the resurrection of Jesus Christ, for the Resurrection of Jesus Christ is the Central theme in Christianity. If that is unable to be defended, then the entire narrative of the religion fails. The article cited in Ref 3 was published in April 14, 2025 and the Express Newspapers UK is a quite renowned newspaper group in the world. If they have published a claim that the body of Jesus Christ is claimed to have been found in a tomb, then it is the responsibility of the Church to entertain the claim, and provide its scientific experimentation and scientific defense that the body in question is not the dead body of Jesus Christ. The Church cant brush it under the carpet or cover it up as a scandal as in Ref 4. Even if the Church pretends that none saw Ref 3 or none read Ref 3, the Church can be sure that we

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Editorial

shall frequently remind the Church for an answer to Ref 3, or failing which, the Church can shut down and request deregistration of the Church as a Society in all Nations and hand over all the lakhs and crores of hectares of land held by the Church to the respective National Governments. Its ok that we have also been cheated for 2000 years, but we cant be expected to accept to be cheated forever...

Now, the Church may be concerned why I brought this point up in this discussion.

Quote from Ref 5: “Ladies and gentlemen, nothing could be further from the truth. Yes, NATO is an association of Western countries. Yes, with the exception of secular Muslim Turkey, NATO is predominantly an Alliance of Christian countries. Each December, the NATO compound here in Brussels is illuminated by a huge Christmas tree.” End of Quote from Ref 5.

Now, what was the necessity for Turkey to send a warship to Karachi port, just days after the Pahalgam Terror Massacre? Ok goodwill visits are common. But, the timing is too suspicious especially when the Pahalgam Terror Massacre has just happened, and India has stepped up diplomatic strictures on Pakistan. The question of Turkish solidarity with Pakistan is just the tip of the iceberg, but what lay beneath it with reference to the Nato Collective Defense and Article 5 ? Even if one stray bullet from India had hit the Turkish warship, it might have caused the Nato Alliance of Christian Countries (with the exception of secular Muslim Turkey) to claim to rush to the rescue of Turkey, and hit India severely wherever it can hurt India.

Now, when India is retracing its ancient spiritual ways, and reclaiming its lost heritage, doesn't this amount to an act of attempting a religious war on India? Hideously orchestrated by the Church, but blamed on the Islamic Nations? And the fury of the Church can be understood from the act of the last surviving heir of an ancient bloodline to claim service of his mother's clan in the 1st Mahabharata war in healing and resurrecting the wounded and the dead. Though the claim could have been filed only on [5:02 PM · May 9, 2025](#) via Ref 1, there have been allegations that the Church was systematically erasing the male heirs in the mother's clan of the claimant (happening to be myself) including the systematic attempt to erase me under the guise of a family problem (similar to a Turkish Islamic Nation problem, when behind Turkey stood only the Nato Alliance of Christian Nations) for many years, by buying out my family, my relatives, my friends and neighbours and ensuring that I suffer a financial blockade for many years, to the point that I should have no food nor water. And the Church failed to erase me. And I've filed my claim to the Govt. of India on [5:02 PM · May 9, 2025](#) via Ref 1. So the Church was sure that I'd assure my services to the Govt. of India for healing the wounded and resurrecting the dead soldiers in the event of war, and the Church wanted to land a pre-emptive strike even before we got ready?

The Church needs to note that I'm dependent solely on the energies of Ma Bagavathy, who's never claimed to have been resurrected, and no committee voted for Her as a Goddess. She was a Goddess and she remained a Goddess and no mummified body of Ma Bagavathy is going to

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Editorial

be found under any Giza pyramid. So, there's no point in staging any drama, and attempting to bring a religious war on India, by perfectly staying out of the suspicious loop and claiming holiness sainthood and sanctity.

The Church may turn a blind eye to these questions, but coz His Holiness The Pope Leo XIV @Pontifex has been invited to the discussion by directly addressing him, these questions will continue to be posed to the Church, until they are answered.

Now, the Govt. of India may please think, whether under all of the circumstances discussed above, will the next Mahabharata war be a religious war again or will it be a war that arose out of India's reaction to a terror attack?

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

The 100% saffronization of India via the scientific approaches to Ma Bagavathy and the consequent existential threat to the Church in India accompanied with the Church's own fears on Pope Leo XIV being the last Pope, and in their fear, attempt to end the world, as a prelude to end of the Church?

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1921898349633872083>

Ref 1: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1921538342400716839>

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1920804093821415443>

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Ref 4: <https://youtu.be/Mm1fHfBDKjk> (Whistleblower EXPOSES Vatican Most Terrifying Secret: They Summon Lucifer with the Grand Grimoire)

Ref 5: <https://www.msn.com/en-in/news/world/nostradamus-chilling-predictions-is-pope-leo-xiv-the-final-pontiff-prophecies-point-to-the-world-s-end-in-2027/ar-AA1EzkD8?ocid=msedgntp&pc=U531&cvid=0f5f95383d5f4c20ac641f204c13d2a8&ei=10>

Ref 6: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/2042098/Jesus-Christ-ancient-Egypt-expert>
(Ancient Egypt bombshell as 'Jesus Christ's body found' in hidden chamber, claims expert)

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(Ancient Egypt bombshell as 'Jesus Christ's body found' in hidden chamber, claims expert)

Ref 9: <https://carnegieendowment.org/russia-eurasia/politika/2023/01/why-the-russian-orthodox-church-supports-the-war-in-ukraine?lang=en>

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Editorial

Your Excellency @DrMohanBhagwat, Your Holiness Pope Leo XIV @Pontifex, Your Eminence Grand Imam @AlimamALTayeb & @HumanFraternity , Your Holiness @DalaiLama, Your Holiness @MAHASHRAMAN, Your Excellencies @NarendraModi Bhai, @AmitShah Bhai, @RajnathSingh Bhai, @NSitharaman Didi, Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn @JM_Scindia Bhai, @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, @AshwiniVaishnaw Bhai, @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India, @FinMinIndia, @DOT_India & @HMOIndia & The Secretaries & Officials at the @RashtrapatiBhvn & The Secretary & Officials at @DOT_India & @BSNL_TN and the Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn and The Secretary & Officials @DOT_India & @BSNLCorporate & @BSNL_TN & @MOMAIndia & Dr @MKStalin & Shri R.N. Ravi @rajbhavan_tn & @Jishnu_Devvarma Bhai & @Revanth_Anumula Anna Garu & @dpradhanbjp Bhai & The Secretary & Officials at @EduMinOfIndia

In humility the following submission please.

Since its always better to invite all to the Table and have an open discussion, this communication also invites all to the Table, coz as a matter of tradition, we don't talk anything behind the back of anyone. We always give them a chance to change for the better.

The proposal for the Search and Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Universe is a technical document and is not a marketing document. Consequently, the benefits or beneficial effects have been modestly expressed, but the time has now come to discuss more openly, for reasons, that the Church could have felt threatened that a 100% saffronization of India may cause the Church to shut shop in India. The number of official Christians in India is estimated to be about 28 million. This number does not include those Christians who bear hindu certificates, but profess Christianity. Include this with 7 crore hectares of land in India owned by the Church (<https://www.mediaonline.com/en/catholic-churches-owns-more-land-than-waqf-board-284873>)

The analysis as reflected in Ref 1, provided an insight that Christianity itself should have arisen from the stories and tales about the healing and resurrection of Pandava soldiers in the first Mahabharata war in 5561 BCE. Until Ref 2 was filed, everyone knew bits and pieces, but it required the blessing of Ma Bagavathy to understand the entirety, and strangely Ma Bagavathy did not bless them with the knowledge of the entirety, coz they were trying to achieve worldly pleasures through it. Even though Ref 2 was drafted by me, it was still elusive until Ma Bagavathy revealed it and caused me to draft it. And, it was such precious knowledge, that Ma Bagavathy did not reveal it for 7500 years to anyone, including those who were born in the same clan too, for reasons that, they had to maintain their integrity, and should not abuse such grace from Ma Bagavathy for achieving the monetary or sexual pleasures of the world. Even those who hunted us down, knew only bits and pieces, and none was given the grace to understand the entirety. In such a situation, how could those who attempted to create a religion from gossips and word of mouth tales know the entirety? They didn't know. Consequently, they

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should have been able to generate only a loosely woven narrative on healing and resurrection, and also proposed a Son of God, elected via a committee so many years later. Wherever, they knew that their loosely woven narrative would be contested, they wrote a safeguard that the devil will deceive and make people ask such questions. And further that God should not be questioned. And the books should not be questioned, and their clerical authority should not be questioned. Everything should be accepted as it is. But all this can be done only when they pose complete authority over the world. The medieval empires helped them a lot. The European colonisation also helped them a lot. The weaknesses in us, manifesting as a fantasy for the fair western skin, also helped to enslave us to them. But, its possible to fool some section of the people, for some portion of the time, and its not possible to fool all of the people for all of the time. So, at some point, the truth might blow out, and no amount of “The devil deceives man and sows doubt in him” can control it. One such example is the claim by a British Anthropologist that dead mummified body of Jesus Christ has been found in a pyramid (Ref 6). Though they have not given attention to it so far, it still has potential to cause great damage in the days to come. And at one time or the other, they have to attend to it.

On a different parallel, a few who mistakenly thought that healing and resurrection can be obtained through tantric practices, also went a different way, though we are not sure if they achieved any good result. Coz, if they had achieved any good results through tantric practices, then I wouldn't be here writing this and u wouldn't be here reading this. Perhaps, this is what caused Ref 4.

But one thing is sure. The Church should have been rattled that what they tried to hide over so many centuries, by uniquely targeting a clan for extinction, has now spilled out in public and one of the surviving members of the clan is blessed by Ma Bagavathy to understand everything and reveal it to the Govt. of India inspite of him being hunted for so many years, harassed and left to die, and also attempted to be killed by poisoning him 11 times. By this time, the victim should have been scared, and fallen at the feet of the Church, he will be least expected to go to the Govt. Of India and present himself as one of the last surviving members of a very ancient clan that served in the First Mahabharata war in 5561 BCE, offering to the Govt. of India, on behalf of his clan, the same service of healing and resurrection, though this time via scientific methods tapping Ma Bagavathy as electromagnetic radiation, instead of relying of prayers and incantations to Ma Bagavathy, taking into consideration, the sheer volume of human population and other life forms, that could have gone up to so many crores compared to the smaller volume of humans and other life forms in 5561 BCE. If it pleases the Govt. of India, we can revert to the ancient methods but it will be time consuming, considering the volume of the population, or if it pleases the Govt. of India, we can go ahead via scientific means, using the Electromagnetic radiations from Ma Bagavathy.

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Further, this might also explain the presence of the Turkish Warship to Karachi port, as a trick to bring in the Nato against India as explained in Ref 1.

The questions for the Church have already arisen, though they have made no attempt to address them.

As with all fake narratives, the narrative of the Church has already been shaken to its core with the claim by a British Anthropologist that the dead mummified body of Jesus Christ is found hidden in a pyramid (Ref 8)

Also, if anyone has any doubt whether the Church, led by such graceful saintly humans would indulge / promote war, their attention is kindly led to Ref 9.

Especially, when there are suspicions whether Pope Leo XIV is the last Pope, as per Nostradamus prophecy Ref 5, we can be sure that the people concerned will want the world to end before the Church ends, so that no body will ever realize the thousands of years of fake narrative that they fed the world. Hence, we can be sure that the Church will indulge in more acts like the Turkish warship in Karachi port to trigger Nato response against India or blatant war promotion as in the Russia-Ukraine conflict Ref 9.

Now, what are we going to do? Are we going to gather the Church on the Mount, and give them the sermon on the mount, that they should not do such hideous wrong things or are we going to let them have a chance to correct themselves, in which time, we go back to our roots, and invite Ma Bagavathy to come and live with us, as our Mother and we live in unity and peace as Her Children (without any discrimination or disunity amongst us), and initiate the Search & Application for the Electromagnetic radiation of Ma Bagavathy and heal the Universe.

At this point of time, I seek to humbly submit to the Govt. of India that western education influenced scientists may be skeptic regarding the proposed effort. I seek to present that only the one ordained (as in priestly terms), will be given the knowledge by Ma Bagavathy to use Her directly for the benefit of the Universe only if She has complete faith in him that he wont use that knowledge for the indiscriminate accumulation or indiscriminate achievement of monetary or sexual pleasures of the world.

Also, I seek to submit that I'm not trying to do this for any worldly fame or recognition, for the priestly recognition that Ma Bagavathy bestowed on me by revealing all of this is sufficient for me, coz no worldly recognition can be greater than the recognition from Ma Bagavathy.

Perhaps, this is the reason, why she kept me alive, inspite of frequent bouts of poisoning by the hostile groups.

Jai Mata Di !!!

In humility copy @BishopDavidT @Pontifex @AlimamAlTayeb @HumanFraternity @DalaiLama @Mahashraman @PMOIndia @HMOIndia @FinMinIndia @RashtrapatiBhvn @DoT_India @dir_ed @NIA_India @CMDBSNL @MTNLOfficial @BSNLCorporate @BSNL_TN @BSNL_CHTD @EKMBSNL

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Editorial

Resubmitting the entirety of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe (Ref 1), with specific reference to <https://dhunt.in/10ihpl>, coz the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy may be the much needed solution to the points raised in <https://dhunt.in/10ihpl> verbatim.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922255200997318884>

Ref 1: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/108cmLqqwjW-afXRVshgpaBfUCto2eArR/view?usp=sharing>

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Jai Mata Di !!!

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<https://1drv.ms/b/s!AgLOT7GpDPHXipMQjJjUOXJVOJ3DyA?e=NZi2Hd>

Editorial

Scientists are just starting to get confused about their cosmological understanding. Let them get confused for some more time. Soon, all those confused Scientists will agree with us regarding the role of the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy in the creation / healing the Universe.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922274526718570826>

Ref: <https://youtu.be/oc1rd62gqkQ>

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In humility the following submission please.

Scientists are just starting to get confused about their cosmological understanding. Let them get confused for some more time. Soon, all Scientists will agree with us regarding the role of the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy in the creation / healing the Universe.

Let us prepare to welcome the original scientific Goddess, with no cooked up human narratives, called the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy.

Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

We may have to apply Quantum Reference Frame Theory to collapse the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe into reality, for, until we start the initiative, there may be too many options for the expected result. But only when we start the initiative, we can observe, that all possibilities have ceased to exist and only one possibility collapses into reality, and that is the Tapping of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and using it to heal the Universe.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922282847219396823>

Ref: <https://youtu.be/rZWDZYmenPA>

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In humility the following submission please.

We may have to apply Quantum Reference Frame Theory to collapse the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe into reality, for, until we start the initiative, there may be too many options for the expected result. But only when we start the initiative, we can observe, that all possibilities have ceased to exist and only one possibility collapses into reality, and that is the Tapping of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy and using it to heal the Universe, and the actual healing of the Universe can be observed only after we start applying the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Universe.

Jai Mata Di !!!

Editorial

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Editorial

Conveying a motherly tender reminder from Aapni Bhagavathy Ma to Aapna @NarendraModi Bhai as understood from a message delivered via the the divine messenger Hanumanji (today during morning walk)

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922633356228923555>

Ref 1: Hanumanji climbing down from the tree after reaching him

https://drive.google.com/file/d/10ygJVYdD8UneAdj4OHSkyRN_sANUkL75/view?usp=sharing

Ref 2: Hanumanji enjoying a cups of groundnut & onions sauted in oil, relishing them one by one.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/110vBfArvqYGBmMKeG_e6jtGWRyXgTkWC/view?usp=sharing

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1910969620040999402> (Requesting from Govt. of India please -- Visitor position for H.E. The President of India, Chairman of Interministerial Task force (already requested) for H.E. @PMOIndia, Convenor position for H.E. @HMOIndia & National Coordinator position for TN BJP President please, for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy / Ma Durga for healing the Universe please accompanied with suitable positions for Alliance & Opposition Leaders please.)

Ref 4: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916119943361216878> (Rahu Ketu Transit 26.04.2025 4:20 pm – as per Vakkiya panchang. The Original Holy Trinity of Lord Shiva, The Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy & Lord Kartikeya rise via the Rahu Ketu Transit 26.04.2025 4:20 pm.)

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Editorial

In humility the following submission please.

Today morning, strangely I felt fresh waking up. Had a cup of tea and started my regular morning walk, from home, to racecourse, one full round in the race course walking path, and back home.

The day was the same as any other day.

Told a “love u Ganpati” to Lord Ganpati, in the Ganpati temple at Race Course. Walked a few more metres, and noticed a family of monkeys. There were less people at that location, walking / jogging. Went near, all monkeys climbed up the tree. The older ones maintained a safe distance above, while a little kid monkey looked at me and started climbing down. Had only my water bottle with me. Gave it to him for playing, and noticing a street vendor selling greens soup, went to him and saw if he had anything to eat. Luckily, he had with him chickpeas and groundnuts sauted in oil. The fried brown color of the groundnuts was appealing. So got two cups of groundnuts and came back. The kid monkey saw that I had brought food, and slowly started engaging with me. I also waited for him to get comfortable. In a few seconds, he had come very near. Slowly placed the cups over a water pipeline junction, and moved a few feet backwards. He came, picked one groundnut, ate it, and then sat comfortably and started eating the groundnuts one by one. Perhaps it tasted good. I let him continue eating, and I resumed my walk. While walking, I remembered, as it usually happened in my life “when I go in search of the monkey, the Ganpati will come and stand in the middle of the road and say, take me take me”. Philosophically, Ganpati is the start and Hanumanji is the end. When I go in search of the andh or the end, the mula or the beginning or the Ganpati will come and restart everything. But what is this, the monkey has come and is eating happily. The end is eating food? Wait a minute, in every auspicious gathering, the end is food. But where has the auspicious gathering happened, that Hanumanji has come and is eating food?

Then remembered, wherever Hanumanji is present, there Sita Ma is also present. And Sita Ma can also be equivalently seen as The Shakti or as Ma Bagavathy. So Ma Bagavathy coming and having food. Wait, somewhere food has to be served to Ma Bagavathy, and someone has not yet remembered to serve food to Ma Bagavathy. If I was the concerned individual, then Ma Bagavathy might have come and given me a little food to eat (coz She knows my struggles) instead of coming and having food. So, who is the concerned individual who has to remember that he is yet to serve food to Ma Bagavathy?

Then my bulbs lit up. Searching for references from earlier sections of this document, while its just started to rain at Ramanathapuram, Coimbatore at 5:27 pm. (Blessings of Ma Bagavathy, showers of rain during the extreme dry hot summer. Incidentally, today is also the day of the Jupiter Transit as per Thirukanidha panchang. So, the Mother and the Guru merge together, in the Mata – Pita – Guru- Deivam. Mata & Deivam have already merged together. Today, the Mother and the Guru merge together. The day we enter the temple of the Shri

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Editorial

Ramanathaswamy Temple in Rameshwaram, all would have merged into one, viz., the unity of the Mata Pita Guru Deivam.) Got Ref 3 & 4.

Quote from Ref 4: “Also, would it be possible to place three thrones in each of the aforesaid temples in the main hall of the Temple and also in the dining space (we shall be blessed to dine with Them)” – one each for Ma Bagavathy, Lord Shiva and Lord Kartikeya.

In such case, who has to serve them, the Chief Executive of the Nation only has to serve them. To make things convenient, the Chief Executive of the Nation, viz., H.E. @NarendraModi Bhai has been requested to serve as exofficio Chairman of the Inter-Ministerial Task force for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, and also exofficio Secretary or exofficio Secretary General of International Efforts that may arise out of this project initiative. Then, as per protocol, H.E. @NarendraModi Bhai only has to serve food for Ma Bagavathy, while we attempt to capture this lovely moment with 360 degree ultraviolet cameras.

So, the message that Hanumanji brought today is that Aapni Bhagavathy Ma is waiting for H.E. Aapna @NarendraModi Bhai to serve Her food at the Kumari Bhagavathy Amman Temple at Kanyakumari as exofficio Chairman of the Inter-Ministerial Task force managing the project & ex-officio Secretary / ex-officio Secretary General of International Efforts arising out of the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy.

And I've conveyed it please.

Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

And Ma Bagavathy starts playing “Snake & Ladder” with the Cosmological Scientists. A sequel to “Scientists are just starting to get confused about their cosmological understanding. Let them get confused for some more time. Soon, all those confused Scientists will agree with us regarding the role of the Shakti aka Ma Bagavathy in the creation / healing the Universe.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922274526718570826>”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922702265992835189>

Ref: <https://youtu.be/hZCuaj9fXrE> (Nobel Winner Warns "IT'S ANOTHER UNIVERSE" James Webb Telescope Saw Strange Things Beyond the...)

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Scientists, based on scientific treatises, theories, theorems and mathematical formulations, with their limitations forgotten as the limit set by the Einsteinian constant “C” and the limit set by the observable universe, in their eagerness to study the Universe, have depended on past

Editorial

knowledge to study the future knowledge. They could have gone and surrendered to Ma Bagavathy to help them understand. Instead they chose to rely on the strength of their past scientific knowledge, forgetting that the Universe is a quantum phenomenon, where the past can influence the future, and the future can also influence the past. And they got confused seeing so many things using the James Webb Telescope.

On a comparative scale, the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy to heal the Universe, does not depend on past scientific knowledge, but only on the faith on Ma Bagavathy, that She shall help us. So, we are going to go into a future, where the future can also influence the past. Rephrasing in conventional form, we are looking at Ma Bagavathy to help us by descending in a form, that is convenient for us to handle, and we are not trying to tap Her in Her original form, so that we can heal the Universe, inclusive of all human and other life forms, and nature and environment and the planet and the Universe, inclusive of the multiverse and parallel universes, including the souls of the pitrus and those generations that are yet to be born. Now, lets apply the phenomenon that the future has power to influence the past, under the benevolence of Ma Bagavathy, which means that, the healed universe has power to influence the past, in which case, the healed universe of the future, has power to influence the disease proliferation and disease manifestation of the past, implying that the disease is going to control the disease from spreading. We are going to go into a future, where there was No COVID and there was No Spanish Flu too, and NO Cancer, NO diabetes and no other disease too, coz the diseases have disappeared/healed from the past, due to the influence of the future on the past. On a different parallel, there have been so many wars in the past, and so many soldiers could have died. We may stumble upon a reality, where those soldiers didn't die due to war, but all of them died only due to old age, implying that no deaths occurred due to wars.

In case, if its difficult to understand, how would u feel if Netaji Subash Chandra Bose appeared now in Parliament as a very grand old gentleman to greet the current Govt. of India, coz he didn't die during the time of the World War II?

In short, we are going to undo the diseases that are plaguing human and other life forms and other alien civilizations. Now if we try to mathematically model this using equations and theorems and treatises known to us, we are going to get as confused as those cosmological scientists who got confused beholding a universe, where they expected to behold a galaxy. So, in summary, its better for us, to go in faith on Ma Bagavathy, beseeching Her to descend in a form that we can handle, instead of trying to do any mathematical equations that can attempt to contain or predict Her behaviour as a quantum electromagnetic signal. Why should we unnecessarily tempt Ma Bagavathy to play Snake and Ladder with us, when we have the option of going in absolute surrender to Ma Bagavathy, instead of carrying with us our scientific and engineering knowledge, gathered over a university system in one universe?

Editorial

Once She heals the Universe, then we can request Her to teach us those Quantum Treatises & mathematical equations, that govern the creation and management of the multiverse. If it pleases Her, we can request Her to author a complete set of books which can be used for teaching a New Set of Degrees in Higher Education related to Quantum Technology. On a different parallel, we can also opt to hand over the microphone to Her, while we take a break in the last row in Class, so that She can take class too.

In humility, I hope that the Govt. of India will now be able to behold why, in such a big proposal, I didn't bring in any mathematical treatises or electromagnetic principles, or related scientific knowledge, coz I was just watching my Lakshman Rekha with Ma Bagavathy, for I have been made aware that the project that we are going to pursue with Ma Bagavathy's blessings, viz., the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, is going to be a revolutionary research pursuit, which has capability to change the entire past scientific knowledge of the world, which could have been influenced by vested groups, who gave more importance to their control of the world, instead of the knowledge as blessed by divinity. In such a case, it was safe for me to go in complete Trust and Faith on Ma Bagavathy...

Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

Balochistan? Autonomous State in India or Charter Member of the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter? What are our options in forging an alliance with the Balochs, especially with ref. to their Sanskrit roots? Revisiting “Sufficiency of Constitution of India / Requirement of UN Referendum for grant of accession request of friendly population in hostile territory, in case Pakistan collapses on implosion !!! <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1919826190132482229>”

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922975122568183925>

Ref 1: <https://tfiglobalnews.com/2025/05/14/balochistan-declares-indepndence-calls-for-un-forces-a-new-neighbour-of-iran-and-afghanistan/>

Ref 2: <https://dhunt.in/10jFRg> (உடைந்தது பாகிஸ்தான்.. உருவானது தனி நாடு, அறிவிப்பை வெளியிட்ட பவுசிஸ்தான்.. இந்தியாவுக்கு ஆதரவு)

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In humility the following submission please.

On [12:16 AM · May 7, 2025](#), the submission included the following extract .

Quote “ Lets move the scale to the most unlikely event and assess our preparedness for it. If its war, we retaliate in a controlled manner, to minimise civilian casualty. If its diplomatic manoeuvres, still, we retaliate as suitable. Assuming that the Nation of Pakistan implodes and ceases to exist, are we prepared to handle it? Who will guarantee the safety and lives and livelihood of the people there?

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Editorial

Is the Constitution of India sufficient to grant guarantees of safety to life and livelihood of the friendly people in hostile territory, if their Nation ceases to exist? Or will we require the people to complete accession formalities into the Union of India or will there be a necessity of a UN Referendum?

When we are so patient with the aftermath of the Pahalgam Terror Massacre, we will have to be equally or more patient with the friendly people in hostile territory, if Pakistan ceases to exist as a Nation, collapsing inwardly due to internal pressures.

Consequently, if it pleases the Govt. of India, the above topic of concern may also be brainstormed at suitable levels of authority, so that we don't let anyone down, and that includes that we don't let anyone down, even if they are a friendly population in a hostile territory.” End of Quote.

It just took 8 days for the event to collapse into reality. Now, as per Ref 1., Balochistan has declared independence. Do we have the political will, to stand by the Balochistanis who stood with us in our time of difficulty, or are we going to take a convenient stand, as dictated by the major powers of the world?

Will Balochistan be an autonomous state in India, with specific reference to their Sanskrit roots, or will Balochistan be a Charter Member of the Bharatiya Free Nations Charter?

Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

The Travesty of “Nothing can travel faster than the speed of Light”, its monotheistic connotation, and the impending merger of the Church into Hinduism. A Sequel to “And Ma Bagavathy starts playing “Snake & Ladder” with the Cosmological Scientists

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922702265992835189>

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1923010232046764423>

Ref1: <https://youtu.be/hZCuaj9fXrE> (Nobel Winner Warns "IT'S ANOTHER UNIVERSE" James Webb Telescope Saw Strange Things Beyond the...)

Ref 2: <https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/world/body-of-jesus-christ-found-in-hidden-chamber-under-great-pyramid-of-egypt/ar-AA1Db19w>

Ref 3: <https://www.gotquestions.org/council-of-Nicea.html>

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In humility the following submission please.

Again, we come to a situation, where we will have to invite all to the table and have an open discussion.

Lets start the discussion from Ref1 please. Lets assume that its indeed another Universe. If its another Universe, then how are we able to view it? And how did the signal from that Universe reach us?

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For, we are fundamentally constrained by the Einsteinian Constant “C” and the treatise that follows it, that “nothing can travel faster than the speed of light”. On a scientific context, when nothing can travel faster than the speed of light, then it gets restricted to the Universe from which observed. We will be able to receive signals only from our Universe.

On a western monotheistic context, “nothing can travel faster than the speed of light”, means the limit is the God that the west defined 2000 years ago, wherein God is equated to light, and the Devil is equated to the dark (or absence of light). Now, when something has travelled faster than light so that it could reach us from a different universe, then, their definition of God, as the ultimate, as the light, has failed.

On a parallel context, the narrative about Jesus Christ being the Son of God who gave his life for the sins of the world, and rose on the third day, has also failed, due to the scientific claim that the body of Jesus Christ has been found in a pyramid (Ref 2). Of course, the Church may have been silent about it, pretending not to notice it, but the silence of the Church has no value in this context, when it amounts to have peddled a fake story and cheating the world for 2000 years, until the Church is able to convince the world scientifically (without buying out the newspapers that published it, and using editorial privileges to retract the publication and without damaging the Scientist or his reputation or his family or his employer) that the aforesaid discussed body is not that of Jesus Christ. On a parallel context, it was affirmed in the Council of Nicea (325 AD), that Jesus Christ is the Son of God. Rephrased, a group of humans, convened a meeting and they gave out an opinion that Jesus Christ is the Son of God. If that’s how Jesus Christ became the Son of God, out of agreement among human beings, then the views proposed in this proposal for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, also gets an equivalent sacred dictum, when a few people can agree on it. And, a few people should have agreed on it, else, it might not have seen so many days, when it has been authored part by part. It might have died an early death, so many days ago itself. The reason why the agreement in the Council of Nicea is being discussed here, is coz, the next few paragraphs might be very difficult for the Church to digest, but at the same time, as an open discussion, we’ve been discussing a lot since the beginning of this proposal for the Search & Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe and hence we are discussing the rest also.

Now, lets revert to the discussion in the previous paragraphs, regarding light and its western monotheistic connotation. So, when a signal from a different Universe has reached us, it implies that the Einsteinian Constant “C” has lost its scientific merit and also its western monotheistic merit, implying that there can be something that can travel faster than light, in which sense, the western monotheistic definition of their God as light has also failed. So, that implies that there’s something more bigger than the God that they defined. Now lets look at a different scenario. The CERN was set up to investigate some intriguing phenomenon. But the International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

Scientific narrative of the CERN will never be permitted to go against the western monotheistic scientific definition of God. So, it could only be a start, a muddle, and no proper finish. However, the Search and Application of the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy for healing the Universe, can never be controlled by the western monotheists. And as the human author of this document, I am not attempting to confine Ma Bagavathy or her electromagnetic manifestation via any western scientific model or equation coz, this project has scope for altering many of the scientific treatises theorems equations, that the western monotheists promoted as science, which was actually a scientific representation of their monotheistic beliefs, which until this date is unable to be challenged, but, the day that the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy is obtained, it is expected that its going to challenge a lot many of the western school of thought in Science, Engineering, Medicine and Allied Disciplines.

And the only option that may be left to the Church is the honorable merger of the Church with Hinduism.

Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

Govt of India -- Taliban -- First Contact Reg. – Thanks to God. Thanks to Devi. Thanks to @DrMohanBhagwat Bhai. Thanks to @NarendraModi Bhai, Thanks to @AmitShah Bhai, Thanks to @RajnathSingh Bhai, Thanks to @NSitharaman Didi, Thanks to Murmu Didi @RashtrapatiBhvn Thanks to @DrSJaishankar Bhai Thanks to @JM_Scindia Bhai, Thanks to @PemmasaniOnX Bhai, Thanks to Dr @NeerajMittalIAS Bhai, Thanks to @AshwiniVaishnav Bhai, Thanks to @Murugan_MoS Bhai, & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @MIB_India & Thanks to The Secretaries and Officials @RashtrapatiBhvn, Thanks to The Home Secretary & Officials at @HMOIndia Govt. of India, Thanks to The Finance Secretary & Officials at @FinMinIndia & Thanks to The CMOBihar & Secretaries & Officials @OfficeCMBihar, Thanks to The DGP Bihar & Officials at @Bihar_Police & Thanks to The Secretary & Officials at @DoT_India & @BSNL_TN and Thanks to the Secretary & Officials @MOMAIndia & Thanks to the Secretary Dept. of Posts, Ministry of Communications Govt of India and Thanks to the Taliban

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1923237422189449365>

Ref 1: https://www.telegraphindia.com/world/s-jaishankar-speaks-with-afghan-minister-in-first-public-contact-with-taliban-regime-by-india-prnt/cid/2100101#goog_rewarded

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1916769339107430692> (Requesting Govt. of India to please invite the Afghan/Taliban Islamic Scholars for the International Diplomatic/Judicial Conclave under Article 51 A(h) to discuss the Waqf Amendment Bill 2025)

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Jai Mata Di !!!

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Editorial

A New Bharatiya Science & Technology Commission -- While Ma Bagavathy enjoys playing “Snake & Ladder” with western scientists & while they are debating whether they were wrong again, lets go forward into the quantum future with facility to influence the past, with the grace & blessings of Ma Bagavathy, leading us in Her Radio Signal form.

<https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1923251635528122370>

Ref 1: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/emiKCiuMpeY?feature=share> (The James Webb Space Telescope has shaken up our understanding of the universe! Early observations showed massive galaxies that didn't fit with our theories, sparking a "crisis in cosmology." But new research reveals these galaxies were playing a cosmic trick)

Ref 2: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1923010232046764423> (The Travesty of “Nothing can travel faster than the speed of Light”, its monotheistic connotation, and the impending merger of the Church into Hinduism.)

Ref 3: <https://x.com/PrabhuBritto/status/1922702265992835189> (And Ma Bagavathy starts playing “Snake & Ladder” with the Cosmological Scientists)

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In humility the following submission please.

International Journal of BioSciences and Technology (2025), Volume 15, Issue 1, Page(s):1-127

Editorial

While Ma Bagavathy enjoys playing “Snake & Ladder” with western scientists & while they are debating whether they were wrong again, lets go forward into the quantum future with facility to influence the past, with the grace & blessings of Ma Bagavathy, accompanying us in Her Radio Signal form

Once we have been successful in tapping the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, we will need to establish a new Bharatiya Science & Technology Commission to investigate the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, and characterise it, to check for compliance to existing Scientific, Technological and Mathematical fundamentals, basics, theories, theorems, treatises, etc. and if unique characteristics are revealed by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy, we will have to extensively study it, and rewrite the entire course of Science, Technology & Mathematics, in accordance with the scientific characteristics as exhibited by the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy. Since existing Ministries or Departments may not have such a mandate incorporated into them, it may be essential to create and establish a new Bharatiya Science and Technology Commission, with an absolute mandate to investigate, experiment, characterise and formulate new treatises, theorems, fundamentals and formulae wherever needed and arrange to rewrite an entire set of textbooks (from primary education level to tertiary/ university education level) that conform to the new findings associated with the Radio Signal of Ma Bagavathy.

Jai Mata Di !!!

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